

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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区域人力资本形成来源概述（以马加丹地区为例）
**AN OVERVIEW OF THE SOURCES OF HUMAN CAPITAL
FORMATION IN THE REGION
(USING THE MAGADAN REGION AS AN EXAMPLE)**

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摘要：本文概述了马加丹地区人力资本形成的基础条件，并阐述了这一过程的主要优势和局限性。文章指出，出生率、教育和医疗保健领域的融资挑战影响着该地区人力资本的形成。分析之后，文章确定了加强人力资本的优先融资方向。

关键词：人力资本，马加丹地区，形成来源，出生率，教育部门。

Abstract. *This article provides an overview of the conditions underpinning human capital formation in the Magadan region and delineates the principal strengths and limitations of this process. The article identifies financing challenges within the spheres of birth rate, education, and healthcare, which influence the formation of the region's human capital. Following the analysis, priority directions of financing have been selected to strengthen human capital.*

Keywords: *human capital, Magadan region, sources of formation, birth rate, education sector.*

The development of human capital in the region relies on funding from the budget and extrabudgetary sources for areas that exert a direct influence on the formation of the individual as an agent of productive labor. Primarily, funding for healthcare, education, and social support of the population is essential. Federal measures aimed at preventing and reducing disparities in regional development are also pertinent for the country's remote and underdeveloped regions.

The aim of the study was to investigate the financing challenges in sectors that shape human capital formation in the Magadan region and to determine solutions to address them. The research objectives included identifying the region's strengths

and weaknesses in the context of human capital formation; an assessment of the impact of the regional maternal family capital program (RMFC) on fertility rate; an overview of initiatives in sectors influencing human capital that were financed from 2022 to 2025; the identification of priority funding directions from the standpoint of strengthening the region's human capital.

The main socio-economic characteristics determining human capital formation at the regional level include demographic conditions, population employment levels, the quality of labor resources, income levels, housing accessibility, and education accessibility. By comparing the sets of enumerated conditions, it was possible to identify both universal trends characteristic of Russia as a whole and the Magadan region (an increase in the working-age population; employment at a record high level; the problem of 'pre-poverty'; high housing market prices affecting its low affordability for broad segments of the population), as well as unique features specific solely to the selected region under study (low population density and a lower degree of demographic aging; high migration with a predominant outflow to other regions of the country; a high average per capita income, effectively offset by elevated prices and a high cost of living; low rates of new housing construction; the possibility of utilizing the 'Far Eastern mortgage' program to improve housing conditions; and a limited number of educational institutions providing vocational education) [5].

The strengths and weaknesses of human capital formation in the Magadan region have been determined. The weaknesses include: low birth rate and outmigration; harsh climate and remoteness from the country's central regions; high cost of living; deterioration of quality of life in the event of intensified sanctions and logistical challenges; low quality of education and healthcare services; low potential for scientific and technological development.

There are also pronounced strengths that can serve as foundations for the enhancement of human capital: within the population of the Magadan region the smallest share of elderly individuals and a comparatively high level of per capita income relative to other regions of the Russian Federation; a high level of housing provision.

The principal source of financing for sectors that generate human capital in the region is budgetary funds, specifically: the regional budget (including inter-governmental transfers) and the budgets of municipal entities. Furthermore, the specified sectors receive funding from extrabudgetary sources. For 2025, funds from the extrabudgetary Social and Economic Development Fund of the Magadan Region, within the framework of the Special Economic Zone, were allocated for the construction of six facilities in the region. These include an educational center for gifted children and youth, physical fitness, wellness, and sports facilities in the settlement of Ust-Omchug and the city of Magadan, as well as the regional maternity hospital [3]. Funds for the development of human capital in the Magadan region are allocated by private investors, including large business entities within the region.

For instance, in 2024, a sports and developmental club for children and adults with a capacity of 100 people, the ‘School of Courage,’ was inaugurated in Magadan. The commissioning party for the construction, in accordance with a social partnership agreement with the Magadan city administration, was the company LLC ‘Pacific-Tractor’; the construction was carried out using private investment funds [4].

Education is one of the key factors contributing to the socio-economic development of the region. It shapes human capital and creates the conditions for the preparation of qualified personnel. Therefore, this sector necessitates particular focus from the regional government and city administration. In the Magadan region, by the end of 2025, significant projects in the development of the education sector were completed: a new engineering school was commissioned, and a new building of the Magadan Polytechnic Technical School, which supplies personnel for the region’s leading industry — mining — was put into operation.

The assessment of regional funding priorities for sectors defining human capital formation at the present stage was carried out according to the planned budget expenditures of the Magadan region for 2025 [2]. The sources of financing for the regional budget expenditures include tax and non-tax revenues, the majority of which are derived from corporate profit tax, personal income tax, mineral extraction tax, and property tax on organizations. By sector of the regional economy, the largest share of revenues is traditionally generated by business entities engaged in mineral resource extraction. In addition, organizations operating in wholesale and retail trade, construction, and public administration make a significant contribution.

With a total regional budget expenditure of 64.6 billion rubles, the combined allocations for healthcare, education, and social policy were planned for 2025 at 27.5 billion rubles (42.6%), reflecting a strong social orientation of the budget and a focus on the quality of life of the population. The largest share of the budget expenditure structure was allocated to education, budgeted at 13.7 billion rubles (21.2%), which reflects the authorities’ commitment to maintaining a high level of education and preparing personnel for the regional economy. Social policy was budgeted at 7.1 billion rubles, or 11.0% of the total expenditures. Healthcare funding was budgeted at 6.7 billion rubles (10.5%). An analysis of planned budget expenditures over time indicates that, compared to 2024, the social orientation of the budget has declined (the aggregate share of expenditures on healthcare, education, and social policy has decreased by 7 percentage points). In absolute terms, planned expenditures for these sectors have increased, albeit to varying extents: education by 10.9%, social policy by 6.3%, and healthcare by 12.1%.

The analysis demonstrates that funding education remains a priority for regional authorities, as evidenced by both absolute and relative indicators of budgetary allocations. Nevertheless, challenges persist in this sector, including a shortage of teaching personnel, population outmigration, high logistics costs, and others.

Addressing these issues requires further measures to enhance the mechanism of inter-budgetary transfers, attract young educators, and improve the efficiency of budgetary fund use.

The substantial increase in healthcare expenditure is undoubtedly a positive development; however, it may be attributable to initially low funding levels (the low-base effect), which diminishes the objectivity of evaluating genuine progress [1, 2].

Further analysis is required for the funding of the social sector, which has experienced more moderate growth. One of the funding directions within this category is the disbursement of regional maternity capital (RMC).

The introduction and scaling of RMC programs have not resulted in a sustainable population increase in the Magadan region. The primary use of RMC funds is the improvement of housing conditions. At the same time, the sustained decline in birth rates suggests that families require conditions conducive to healthy parenting rather than direct financial support. This necessitates a revision of the conditions governing the application of this instrument to affect birth rates in the region.

The trends in the number of issued maternity capital certificates reflect demographic tendencies characteristic of the region — namely, a decline in birth rates and delayed parenthood. In financial terms, families with a second child receive the greatest support from the regional budget. The program's coverage is substantially lower for families with first-born children. Benefits are provided exclusively to young mothers aged 25 years or younger. This factor necessitates strengthening support for families with firstborn children.

Thus, based on the results of the conducted analysis, priority funding areas can be identified that annually demonstrate a positive impact on the characteristics of human capital in the Magadan region: education, social policy, healthcare, and housing. At the same time, insufficient funding in the healthcare sector undoubtedly affects the population's health, satisfaction with the quality of healthcare services received, and the region's capacity to develop human capital.

Although the instruments of social policy produce positive results, they require reassessment and clarification of the outcomes achieved, as well as adaptation to the characteristics of the age composition of the population in the Magadan region.

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俄罗斯联邦劳动力市场的数字化转型
**DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE LABOR MARKET
IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了数字化驱动下劳动力市场转型的主要趋势，分析了新兴和未来职业，并探讨了教育在为新经济培养劳动力方面所发挥的作用。文章重点阐述了技术性失业带来的挑战以及劳动者适应新环境的必要性。文章最后得出结论：灵活性、数字素养和持续学习是数字时代成功就业的关键因素。

关键词：数字化，工业企业，外部环境因素，劳动力市场，就业灵活性，未来职业。

Abstract. *This article examines the key trends in the transformation of the labor market driven by digitalization, analyzes emerging and future professions, and explores the role of education in preparing the workforce for the new economy. It highlights challenges associated with technological unemployment and the necessity for workers to adapt to new conditions. The article concludes that flexibility, digital literacy, and continuous learning are critical factors for successful employment in the digital era.*

Keywords: *digitalization, industrial enterprises, external environmental factors, labor market, employment flexibility, future professions.*

The digital economy is shaping a new reality in which information, technologies, and data become key resources. The development of the Internet, big data, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and robotics is transforming the structure of production, management, and consumption. These processes directly impact the labor market: some professions disappear, others emerge, while still others undergo radical transformation.

Automation processes encompass not only manufacturing but also administrative, analytical, and even creative professions. Routine operations are being replaced by algorithms. Professions such as cashiers, call center operators, accountants, clerks responsible for document flow, assemblers, dispatchers, and logisticians lacking digital skills face the risk of disappearance.

The process of digitalization contributes to the intensification of social inequality within the labor market. According to income level analysis, the highest-paid occupations are in the field of IT. The demand for specialists in the IT sector is increasing exponentially. Software developers, data analysis and big data specialists, artificial intelligence engineers, and cybersecurity experts are particularly sought after.

Currently, millions of individuals in the Russian Federation are employed in professions such as sales representatives, drivers, security guards, loaders, and others. Certainly, the implementation of information technologies has enhanced mobility across several industries and facilitated interaction between consumers and producers. Nevertheless, demand for blue-collar professions remains relevant [6].

The study demonstrated that sectors lagging in digitalization include:

The fuel and energy complex. Digitalization in this sector has been impeded by high regulatory constraints and a lack of private initiative.

Metallurgy. The digitalization of operational activities in this sector lagged due to the necessity of substantial investments amid recurring crises.

Medicine and Pharmaceuticals. The digitalization of companies in this field was impeded by the conservatism of healthcare regulatory frameworks.

Mechanical Engineering. The sector's digital backwardness was partly attributable to low competition and 'limited incentives for change.' Another reason is the low demands of customers (the primary client in this sector being the state) for innovation in products and services.

. The most vulnerable regions are the following territories: According to data from January to April 2025, among the lagging regions in digitalization is the Republic of Tuva, where the remoteness of the territories, low internet coverage, and shortage of qualified personnel have had a significant impact. Tambov, Tver, and Kurgan oblasts, as well as the Nenets Autonomous Okrug, are also among the lagging regions; they possess weak IT ecosystems and implement few digital projects.

According to the latest analytical data, an extremely small proportion of the population, not exceeding 20%, possesses the skills necessary to engage in business activities. In the engineering sector, although some measures have been implemented, they have not been able to radically improve the situation for the majority of the population. With the expansion of automation, the question arises concerning the state's capacity to provide means for the adaptation of inhabitants of various cities and regions. Presidential Decree of the Russian Federation No. 204 dated May 7, 2018, underscores the significance of this issue and the commitment to its

resolution, highlighting its enduring relevance within the strategic objectives of national development.

These strategies are aimed at advancing digitalization in regions and oblasts.

In many regions of Russia, progress in the application of the latest technologies does not correspond to the level of developed countries, which is due to several factors: insufficient population density, uneven economic activity, limited income of the population, a low level of technological equipment, and weak infrastructural connectivity between different regions. On the other hand, the spread of digital technologies and the expansion of opportunities for remote work bring significant adjustments to the structure of the labor market.

In the era of digitalization of economic processes, understanding changes in labor market demands becomes critically important. The dynamics of the labor market are transforming under digitalization, during which innovative economic platforms emerge that utilize information from multiple channels. In the coming years, roles such as smart systems operator, digital learning curator, AI ethics specialist, digital ecosystem architect, and bioinformatics engineer will become widely adopted.

The adoption of digital technologies enhances organizational competitiveness and productivity. Modern economic growth and corporate development are unattainable without automation and the optimization of production processes — this is an indisputable fact.

Effective management of interactions between the client base and suppliers enables high-quality coordination and rational utilization of available resources [10]. Simultaneously, dialogue with all stakeholders in the value chain — from business partners to end consumers — is improving, alongside the emergence of new opportunities for monitoring and managing operational activities. All of this accelerates and increases the efficiency of workflows across various areas of organizational activity.

The development of partnerships and inter-industry cooperation becomes possible through the integration of digital technologies into economic processes. Organizations acquire the capability to respond effectively to market dynamics by enhancing their agility, adaptability, and reinforcing their positions in the competitive environment through digitalization. Digitalization enables cost reduction and increases the efficiency of interactions. In turn, it raises the issue of the quality of the workforce and its alignment with contemporary requirements. Unfortunately, not all companies actively adopt new management methods or invest in the development of human capital. Undoubtedly, major corporations devote significant attention to the retraining and professional development of personnel. However, the issue of whether graduate training meets labor market requirements remains unresolved.

In addition to digital skills, the ability for continuous learning and requalification, critical thinking, communication and creative abilities, teamwork within digital

environments, and emotional intelligence are highly valued. It is precisely cognitive flexibility that becomes the primary asset in the labor market of the future. Undoubtedly, there is an increasing demand in the modern world for specialists in the fields of information technology, biotechnology, and alternative energy. This necessitates a revision of approaches to education and personnel training for the digital economy.

One of the solutions to this issue is the national project «Personnel», aimed at satisfying the economy's demand for skilled personnel, which is crucial for Russia's economic growth and development [11]. At present, the impact of the digitalization process on the structure of the labor market is already observable, as reflected in the forms of employment within the digital economy.

In Russia, the development of the IT sector and the creation of new job opportunities are constrained in regions dominated by industry, agriculture, and extractive sectors. Furthermore, a particularly pronounced lag in technological development and employment opportunities is characteristic of monotowns.

New high-tech companies are primarily established in large cities characterized by a large population, a broad service sector, and an adequate number of higher education institutions; consequently, there is a substantial number of employers across various fields. Thus, in Tatarstan, digital transformation is planned across 15 sectors, making it a leader in digital transformation. In Saint Petersburg, the digital transformation strategy covers 11 sectors; in the Moscow region, 10; in Kalmykia and the Jewish Autonomous Oblast, approximately 10 sectors each; in Altai Krai, around 11 sectors; and in the Kurgan region, transformation is planned for 15 sectors [12].

In the era of digitalization, information technologies are undergoing rapid development. It is expected that by 2030, the number of new jobs created through technological progress will double the number of jobs lost due to automation, according to data from the World Economic Forum 2018.

Flexible education plays an important role in achieving high levels of digitalization — by adapting to rapidly changing market demands — as does digital education, which involves the use of online learning, simulators, and artificial intelligence.

Thus, the factors driving the transformation of the labor market in the Russian Federation are associated with a number of transformations [13].

1. The adoption of digital technologies in the Russian economy is actively progressing, despite challenges such as a shortage of qualified specialists and resources. This fosters not only the emergence of new professions but also a reduction in dependence on external economic conditions.

2. The adoption of digitalization principles not only reduces production costs but also substantially enhances its efficiency.

3. Robotization and automation contribute to the creation of new production models.

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俄中旅游合作发展：以堪察加边疆区为例
**DEVELOPMENT OF RUSSIAN-CHINESE TOURISM
COOPERATION: THE CASE OF KAMCHATKA KRAI**

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摘要：本文以堪察加边疆区为例，探讨了俄中旅游合作的发展。重点关注中国游客流动动态、提升中国游客兴趣的因素，以及该地区入境旅游发展面临的问题和前景。

关键词：俄中合作，入境旅游，堪察加边疆区，游客流动，生态旅游，航空旅行。

Abstract. *This article examines the development of Russian-Chinese tourism cooperation on the example of the Kamchatka Territory. Special attention is paid to the dynamics of the tourist flow from China, the factors of increasing the interest of Chinese travelers, as well as the problems and prospects of developing inbound tourism in the region.*

Keywords: *Russian-Chinese cooperation, inbound tourism, Kamchatka Territory, tourist flow, ecological tourism, air travel.*

The active development of Russian-Chinese relations in recent decades has covered a wide range of areas, from trade and economic cooperation to cultural and humanitarian collaboration. In this context, tourism has emerged not only as a significant economic sector, but also as an important tool for deepening mutual understanding between the peoples of the two countries. With the implementation of the Far East Development Strategy and the expansion of visa-free travel between the Russian Federation and the People's Republic of China (PRC), the study of the potential of Russia's Far Eastern regions has become particularly relevant.

Materials and methods.

A comparative characteristic of the tourist flow, including foreign citizens, formed on the attractiveness of the tourist and recreational potential of the Kamchatka Territory, is carried out. The mechanism of cooperation between tour operators of Kamchatka and China is described.

Kamchatka Krai holds a special place among the regions of the Russian Far East due to its unique natural and recreational potential. The presence of active volcanoes, the Valley of Geysers, thermal springs, and diverse flora and fauna attract a significant number of foreign tourists, particularly from China. It is worth noting that Kamchatka Krai is one of the largest tourist destinations in the world, offering all the necessary conditions for tourists to enjoy their visits.

A study of statistical data for the period 2020-2024 shows a steady positive trend in the overall tourist flow (hereinafter referred to as the tourist flow) in the Kamchatka Territory.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the tourist flow in the Kamchatka Territory for the period 2020-2024, in numbers of people [5, elect. pes.].

The most significant increase in tourist arrivals was observed in 2021, which can be attributed to the “delayed demand” effect following the lifting of restrictions imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic. In subsequent years, the trend remained positive, but the growth rate stabilized at around 8-10% per year, indicating the transition of the industry to a sustainable development phase.

The dynamics of inbound tourism from China deserve special attention. According to data as of October 2024, the number of Chinese tourists visiting the Kamchatka Territory in the first 10 months of 2024 has more than tripled compared to the same period in 2023. This increase can be attributed to both the lifting of pandemic restrictions and the increased efforts of regional authorities to promote the tourism product in the Chinese market.

In July 2025, the authorities of the Kamchatka Territory predicted a further increase in tourist trips from China to the region during 2026 [5, elect. pes.]. The key condition for achieving this target is the establishment of direct flights between

Kamchatka and Chinese cities. According to information for 2026, it is planned to open direct flights to Harbin and Sanya, which are major tourist and business centers in China.

The growing interest of Chinese tourists in the Kamchatka region can be attributed to several key factors. Firstly, the region's unique natural environment, featuring active volcanoes, geysers, and thermal springs, attracts tourists seeking new and exotic experiences. These natural attractions provide a contrast to more traditional tourist destinations, making Kamchatka particularly appealing to Chinese travelers.

Results and its discussion

The development of ecotourism also plays a key role in this process [3, elect. pes.]. From 2024 to 2026, cooperation between the Kamchatka Territory and its Chinese partners in the field of nature conservation and ecotourism has intensified. Negotiations with the Chinese delegation in March 2026 demonstrated the willingness of both parties to participate in joint projects aimed at promoting sustainable tourism. The launch of mutual internship programs for environmental education specialists will allow for the exchange of experience and the improvement of safe tourism practices.

In addition, the strengthening of interregional ties, such as the cooperation agreement with the Chinese province of Jinju in November 2025, opens up new opportunities for promoting Kamchatka's tourism products in the Chinese market and attracting investments in the development of tourism infrastructure. Taken together, these factors will contribute to an increase in the number of Chinese tourists visiting Kamchatka and the development of mutually beneficial cooperation between the regions.

The regional authorities of Kamchatka and the tourism industry are taking measures to adapt their tourism offerings to the interests of Chinese travelers [2, elect. pes.]. One of the key areas of focus is the creation of specialized tours that take into account the cultural characteristics and preferences of the Chinese audience. For example, a premium 8-day tour called "8 Northern Dragons" has been developed. This itinerary includes visits to key natural attractions in Kamchatka, such as volcanoes, hot springs, Khalatyr Beach, and Russkaya Bay, as well as opportunities to observe bears and marine animals in their natural habitats. Tourists will also be able to experience the culture of the indigenous peoples of Kamchatka, participate in workshops on local crafts, and sample regional cuisine. This tour is positioned as a premium product aimed at an affluent audience willing to invest more in unique experiences and high-quality service.

The local tour operator Khalzan LLC also adapts its offers for foreign travelers, organizing water tours and expeditions to volcanoes, hot springs and scenic spots. The company offers unique routes, experienced guides and comfortable accommodation that fully meet the expectations of Chinese tourists. As part of this cooperation,

representatives of the Chinese tourism industry were offered a five-day study tour along the route “The Land of the Dragon” [1, elect. pes.]. The tour program included tracks with visits to Avacha Pass and Camel Mountain, excursions to Dacha Hot Springs, visits to the Oceanarium, the Ocean Fleet History Museum, Cape Mayachny, and Khalaktyr Beach. This tour allowed Chinese specialists to assess the region’s tourism potential and develop competitive offers for their compatriots.

Despite the positive trends and active efforts of local authorities, the development of tourism cooperation between the Kamchatka Territory and China faces several significant challenges that need to be addressed. One of the main obstacles is the lack of direct flights, as currently, travel from China to Kamchatka is only possible with connections in Moscow, Khabarovsk, or Vladivostok. This significantly increases travel time and costs, making the region less competitive compared to other Far Eastern destinations with direct flights to China. Local authorities hope that by establishing direct flights between the peninsula and Chinese cities, they can attract more tourists.

Another serious problem is the underdeveloped tourism infrastructure. In 2024, it was noted that significant improvements in infrastructure, increased exports of tourism services, and the creation of conditions for their implementation are necessary to increase the number of tourists, including those from China. If the projected increase in the number of Chinese tourists is realized, the region will face the challenge of providing high-quality accommodation and qualified Chinese-speaking professionals.

An important issue is the need to expand the route network. The existing tourist routes are limited and may become overcrowded if the number of visitors increases. Therefore, the development of new routes, especially land-based excursions in the South Kamchatka Nature Reserve, is crucial. This will help to highlight the beauty and uniqueness of the region and distribute tourist flows more evenly.

The prospects for the development of Russian-Chinese cooperation in the field of tourism in Kamchatka are associated with the implementation of a number of strategic directions. The launch of direct air traffic in 2026 is expected to become a key factor in the growth of tourism, as it will significantly reduce travel time and flight costs, making the region more accessible to mass tourists from China. The planned simplification of visa procedures, combined with the existing mechanisms for visa-free group exchanges between Russia and China, will create additional incentives for Chinese travelers to visit Kamchatka. A joint advertising campaign to promote Kamchatka’s tourism potential in the Chinese market will help raise awareness about the region among potential tourists, which is especially important in a highly competitive environment.

The agreements reached in 2026 on joint ecotourism projects and mutual internship programs for environmental education specialists create a foundation for

long-term cooperation and the exchange of best practices in sustainable tourism management in protected areas. The success of the “8 Northern Dragons” premium tour demonstrates the Chinese audience’s interest in a deeper exploration of the region, encompassing not only its natural beauty but also its ethnographic and culinary aspects. In the future, it is possible to further expand the range of specialized tours, taking into account the seasonality (winter programs with dog sledding and snowmobiling; summer programs with a focus on water and hiking sports), integrate ethnographic programs with the participation of the indigenous peoples of Kamchatka, develop gastronomic tourism with a focus on the region’s unique products, and create a multilingual information environment, including the translation of navigation materials, information boards, and websites into Chinese.

Thus, the conducted study confirms the existence of significant potential for the development of inbound tourism from China. The unique natural resources of the Kamchatka Territory and the growing interest of Chinese tourists create favorable conditions for increasing the flow of tourists. However, in order to successfully develop the region, it is necessary to address issues such as the lack of direct flights and insufficient infrastructure. Implementing measures, including the launch of direct flights and the development of eco-tourism, can significantly increase the region’s attractiveness. If these initiatives are successfully implemented, it is expected that the tourist flow will double, which will strengthen the economy and intercultural relations of the Kamchatka Territory.

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俄罗斯联邦旅游业经济政策及其与远东和北极地区发展的融合
**ECONOMIC POLICY IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM
IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION WITH INTEGRATION
OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FAR EAST AND THE ARCTIC**

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摘要：本文全面回顾了俄罗斯远东地区旅游经济政策的发展历程。研究旨在探究政府政策与该地区旅游业发展动态之间的关系。文章系统梳理了关键的旅游发展规划，阐述了政府监管原则，分析了适用的支持工具，并通过游客流量、基础设施建设和已实施投资项目等指标评估了政策实施效果。分析结果表明，结合联邦战略、区域措施和公私合作机制的综合方法有助于远东地区旅游业的可持续发展。

关键词：经济政策，旅游，远东，国家监管，发展规划，游客流量，基础设施，投资项目。

Abstract. *The article provides a comprehensive review of the development of economic policy in the field of tourism in the Russian Far East. The purpose of the study is to identify the relationship between government policy and the dynamics of tourism development in the macroregion. The article systematizes key tourism development programs, defines the principles of government regulation, analyzes applicable support tools, and evaluates the results of policy implementation through indicators of tourist flow, infrastructure development, and implemented investment projects. Based on the analysis, it was concluded that a comprehensive approach that combines federal strategies, regional measures, and public-private partnership mechanisms contributes to the sustainable growth of the tourism industry in the Far East.*

Keywords: *economic policy, tourism, the Far East, state regulation, development programs, tourist flow, infrastructure, and investment projects.*

In the modern global economic system, the tourism industry is positioned as one of the basic industries that determine the dynamics of socio-economic progress in territories. For a long time, the Far Eastern macroregion was characterized by a low level of integration into the tourism market. This was due to systemic barriers, such as logistical distance from major demand centers, a lack of high-quality material and technical resources, and harsh natural and climatic conditions.

A qualitative shift in the state approach occurred in 2013, when the development of the Russian Far East was officially declared by Russian President Vladimir Putin to be a strategic priority of national scale for the entire 21st century [2, pp. 41-54]. This political decision necessitated a scientific analysis and critical evaluation of the effectiveness of economic measures implemented in the tourism sector to intensify the development of the region.

Materials and methods.

A review of regulatory legal acts integrated into a unified system of socio-economic development and programs for developing the tourism industry in the Far East and the Arctic has been conducted.

The legal framework for state regulation of the tourism industry in the Russian Federation is based on Federal Law No. 132-FZ "On the Fundamentals of Tourism Activities in the Russian Federation." This act establishes the basic principles, priorities, and tools for supporting the sector. A key aspect is the delegation of authority between the three levels of government (federal, regional, and municipal), which ensures that the unique characteristics of each federal subject are taken into account.

In the Far East, the program-target mechanism has become the dominant tool for implementing state policy. At the federal level, a series of strategic documents have been developed and consistently approved, which have served as the basis for the formation and implementation of regional development programs.

The National Project "Tourism and Hospitality Industry" (2019-2030) is a key strategic document that defines the development trajectory of Russia's tourism sector [5, pp. 1222-1227]. Its primary objective is to increase the volume of tourist arrivals, develop modern infrastructure, and make domestic tourism more accessible. In the context of the Russian Far East, the national project aims to create specialized tourism and recreation clusters, stimulate investment activities, and develop coastal recreational areas.

The Comprehensive State Program of the Russian Federation "Socio-Economic Development of the Far East and the Arctic Zone" contains separate subprograms aimed at improving infrastructure, including tourism infrastructure [7, pp. 334-340]. This program provides financial support for projects related to the construction of transportation routes, airport complexes, and engineering facilities in areas with potential for tourism development.

The “Concept for the Development of Tourism in the Russian Federation for the Period up to 2035” is a long-term plan that sets the main guidelines, objectives, and directions for the development of the industry [6, electronic resource]. This strategic document positions the Far East as one of the priority macro-regions for stimulating both inbound and domestic tourism, focusing on the development of specific segments such as eco-tourism, cruise tourism, event tourism, and business tourism.

The National Programme for the Development of the Russian Far East for the period up to 2025 and beyond 2035 (Order No. 2460-r dated 24 September 2020) serves as a consolidating document that defines a set of government measures to support the Russian Far East. This programme establishes that the Priority Development Areas (PDA) and the Vladivostok Free Port (VFP) regime are the fundamental institutional mechanisms for attracting investments, including those in the tourism industry.

Figure 1. — Mechanism of integration of tourism development programs into the socio-economic development program [Source: compiled by the authors]

Figure 1 shows the interaction of program documents, which are based on the principle of systemic development of the region with the integration of programs from the national, federal, and regional levels with the systems of socio-economic development in the sectoral focus, taking a comprehensive approach and ensuring mutual complementarity of various measures of state support.

In particular, the mechanisms of the National Project “Tourism and the Hospitality Industry” are focused on stimulating private initiative, for example, through subsidizing the construction of modular accommodation facilities. At the same time, the resources of the State Program for the Development of the Russian Far East are directed towards solving capital-intensive tasks, such as building access roads and connecting engineering facilities to these facilities.

Such inter-programmatic synchronization of efforts at the federal and regional levels helps to avoid infrastructure imbalances. It ensures that the introduction of new tourist facilities is supported by an adequate transport, energy, and social infrastructure, minimizing time and financial gaps in the implementation of investment projects.

The effectiveness of the state strategy in the tourism sector is determined by the quality and diversity of the regulatory mechanisms used. In her works, O. E. Lebedeva emphasizes that public administration in this area should be viewed not as a set of formal regulations, but as a dynamic process aimed at ensuring stable growth of the industry, stimulating investment activity, and improving the social welfare of citizens [4, pp. 90]. The main groups of tools used for the development of the Far Eastern territories are systematized and presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Main tools of state support for tourism in the Far East

A group of tools	Specific measures	Regulatory framework
Institutional (preferential regimes)	Territories of advanced development (TOP); free Port of Vladivostok (SPV)	Federal Law No. 473-FZ of December 29, 2014, «On Priority Social and Economic Development Areas in the Russian Federation»; Federal Law No. 212-FZ of July 13, 2015, «On the Free Port of Vladivostok»
Tax benefits	Reduced income tax rates (0-5% for the first 5 years), insurance contributions of 7.6% (instead of 30%), and exemption from property tax	Tax Code of the Russian Federation, Article 284.4, Article 427; laws on TOP and SPV; Federal Law No. 18-FZ of February 11, 2026 «On Amendments to Parts One and Two of the Tax Code of the Russian Federation» (new rules for correlation of benefits with the volume of capital investments for new residents)
Financial and credit	Concessional loans (3-5% per annum), subsidies, and grants	Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 141 dated February 9, 2021, «On Approval of the Rules for Providing Subsidies from the Federal Budget for State Support of Investment Projects for the Construction and Reconstruction of Hotels»; concessional lending program within the framework of the national project

A group of tools	Specific measures	Regulatory framework
Tax (industry-wide)	Zero VAT rate for hotels, reduced rates for simplified taxation	Tax Code of the Russian Federation, Article 164 (paragraph 3.8); Federal Law No. 67-FZ dated March 26, 2022 (on the zero VAT rate);

Analytical data confirms the use of a comprehensive toolkit by the government, which includes both macroeconomic measures in the form of tax preferences and local forms of stimulation, including a targeted grant system. Exclusive institutional platforms, such as territories that are ahead of the curve in the tourism sector under these legal regimes, are of fundamental importance for the Far Eastern territories, as they are granted exclusive tax privileges, which significantly increases the investment attractiveness of the macroregion for strategic partners.

According to the Far East and Arctic Development Corporation (FEACD), over 2,700 business projects are being implemented in the macro-region as part of ongoing government support programs, with 545 of them already reaching the operational stage. The total amount of actual investments in the Far East's economic system has exceeded 2.7 trillion rubles, resulting in the creation of over 100,000 new jobs [8, pp. 58-69].

Results and its discussion

The vector of development of regional tax policy is shifting towards increasing transparency and efficiency. On April 1, 2026, the provisions of Federal Law No. 18-FZ dated February 11, 2026, which establish a direct relationship between the amount of preferences provided and the actual contributions to fixed assets, come into force. According to the new version of the law, the total amount of tax savings for new participants should not exceed the amount of actual capital expenditures. It is important to note that the previous legal regime remains in place for entities that already have resident status, ensuring stability for previously initiated investment cycles.

The Far Eastern macro-region is characterized by stable positive dynamics in the domestic tourism segment. According to Rosstat statistics, the number of visitors to the region increased by more than a third (30%) over a five-year period. By 2025, the total number of tourists had reached 7.2 million [3, pp. 74-80]. Primorsky Krai, which is successfully developing event and cruise destinations, as well as Sakhalin Oblast and Kamchatka Krai, where the main focus is on promoting ecological routes and active recreation formats, are leading in terms of growth rates.

The implementation of state programs has led to significant progress in the development of modern tourism infrastructure. One of the priority tasks has been the rapid expansion of the hotel stock through the construction of modular hotel complexes. In 2023-2024, as part of the national project "Tourism and Hospitality Industry," the regions of the Far Eastern Federal District received substantial federal funding, which enabled the commissioning of hundreds of modern accommodation

facilities in Primorye, Buryatia, and Kamchatka. Additionally, the state program for the development of the Far Eastern Federal District focuses on the renovation of transportation hubs. The reconstruction of airport complexes in Blagoveshchensk, Yakutsk, and Petropavlovsk-Kamchatsky has significantly simplified logistics and increased the overall accessibility of remote areas in the macroregion.

The key indicator of the policy's success has been the involvement of private capital in large-scale industry projects. The launch of significant initiatives such as the year-round resort "Three Volcanoes" in Kamchatka and the development of the recreational zone on Russky Island in Primorye confirms the region's high investment attractiveness. These projects are based on the principles of public-private partnership and the use of TOP and SPV preferences, which helps to minimize business risks and optimize the return on investment.

An important tool for marketing regional services is the Made in TOP SPV Far East trademark, which was initiated in 2019 on behalf of Deputy Prime Minister and Plenipotentiary Representative of the President of the Russian Federation in the Far Eastern Federal District, Yury Trutnev. This brand promotes the popularization of residents' products and services, including the tourism sector, in domestic and foreign markets [1, electronic resource].

Summarizing the research results, we can state that there is a pronounced correlation between the implementation of strategic government initiatives and the qualitative transformation of the tourism sector in the Far East. The systematic application of the program-targeted method, embodied in national projects, macroregional strategies, and sectoral development concepts, has formed a stable institutional framework for the progressive growth of the industry. The exclusive support mechanisms for the Russian legal system, such as the Priority Development Areas (PDA) and the Free Port of Vladivostok (FVP), which were established by Federal Laws No. 473-FZ and No. 212-FZ, played a fundamental role in this process. These tools, combined with fiscal incentives and large-scale budgetary investments in infrastructure, provided the necessary impetus for the industry's development.

The practical implementation of these measures has led to a significant increase in domestic tourist traffic, a qualitative upgrade of the hospitality infrastructure (including the rapid introduction of rapid-construction accommodation facilities), and the successful launch of anchor investment projects.

Nevertheless, the industry still faces a number of systemic barriers. Among them, the most significant are the high sensitivity to fluctuations in domestic consumer demand, the continued lack of transport connectivity in the territories, and the need for more intensive promotion of small and medium-sized enterprises. Further optimization of government policy should focus on harmonizing interdepartmental cooperation and extending financial support

programs for infrastructure construction. This approach will allow for the full utilization of the enormous recreational potential of the Far Eastern region and ensure its long-term competitiveness.

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合资企业碳排放核查：审计在上海合作组织框架下中国绿色投资实施中的作用

**VERIFICATION OF THE CARBON IN JOINT VENTURES:
THE ROLE OF AUDITING IN THE IMPLEMENTATION
OF CHINESE GREEN INVESTMENTS WITHIN THE SCO**

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摘要：本文探讨了审计在上海合作组织（SCO）成员国境内涉及中国资本的合资企业碳足迹核查中的作用。文章分析了方法论基础（ISO 14064、温室气体核算体系、国家发展和改革委员会标准、环境部标准、GB/T标准）、审计阶段、保证程度以及与排放分配相关的问题。重点关注核算方法的协调统一、核查过程的相互认可以及审计联盟的建立。文章为监管机构、企业和审计人员提出了建议。

关键词：碳足迹；碳中和；核查；合资企业；上海合作组织；绿色投资；碳审计。

Abstract. *The article examines the role of audit in the verification of the carbon footprint of joint ventures involving Chinese capital within the SCO. The methodological bases (ISO 14064, GHG Protocol, NDRC, MEE, GB/T), audit stages, levels of assurance, and issues related to emissions allocation are analyzed. The main focus is on the harmonization of accounting approaches, mutual recognition of verification processes, and the establishment of audit consortia. Recommendations are given for regulators, enterprises, and auditors.*

Keywords: *carbon footprint; carbon neutrality; verification; joint ventures; SCO; green investments; carbon audit.*

Introduction

The strategic foundation for the development of carbon auditing in China consists of the objectives to reach peak carbon dioxide emissions by 2030 and achieve carbon neutrality by 2060. In the 14th Five-Year Plan, environmental audit was deepened, including the audit of special funds and the implementation of policies related to ecological civilization. The 15th Five-Year Plan aims to enhance technological self-reliance and strengthen positions in science and technology. Within this plan, the promotion of a 'green' economy is designated as a key objective of socio-economic development. In the context of foreign economic activity, particularly within the SCO framework, guidelines on 'green' investments abroad acquire critical importance, requiring Chinese enterprises to consider not only economic efficiency but also the environmental footprint of joint projects. These documents formulate the regulatory requirement for the verification of the carbon footprint as a mandatory component of risk management and corporate responsibility.

The objective of the article is to determine the role of audit in the verification of the carbon footprint for Chinese «green» investments in SCO joint ventures. The objectives of the article are as follows: to systematize the methodology, analyze the positioning of audit within the investment cycle, and substantiate the harmonization of accounting practices alongside the establishment of cross-border audit consortia.

Within the framework of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), the environmental agenda is embedded in several intergovernmental agreements that emphasize the necessity of sustainable development for cross-border projects. The 'Green Belt' program (as part of the broader 'Belt and Road' initiative) acts as a central mechanism for the harmonization of environmental standards. For joint ventures, this entails the obligation to comply with both Chinese carbon regulatory norms and the requirements of SCO partner countries. The emerging system of intergovernmental cooperation entails the harmonization of approaches to emissions accounting and the mutual recognition of audit outcomes, which is essential for the implementation of major infrastructure and energy projects characterized by significant involvement of Chinese capital and technology.

Theoretical and legal foundations of 'green' investments and carbon accounting within the SCO framework, alongside the methodology for carbon footprint verification

Carbon footprint verification constitutes a systematic process of independent audit of greenhouse gas emission data to substantiate the reliability of joint ventures' reporting. The methodological foundation integrates international standards, national regulatory acts, and industry-specific guidelines.

At the international level, the following standards are employed: ISO 14064-1 (organizational-level emissions accounting), ISO 14064-3 (verification of assertions), ISO 14067 (product carbon footprinting related to Scope 3), as well as the GHG

Protocol, which distinguishes Scopes 1-3 and includes financial and operational control methodologies — elements critically important for joint ventures [6]. Within Chinese regulation, guidelines from the National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC) for the Emissions Trading System (ETS), standards GB/T 32150 (enterprise-level accounting) and GB/T 33760 (verification), as well as sector-specific methodologies issued by the Ministry of Ecology and Environment (MEE) are applied [4].

For the investment aspect, PAS 2060 (verification of carbon neutrality) and IPCC methodologies for calculating emission factors (levels 1-3) are significant. When implementing projects in SCO countries, local regulations are considered, including accounting methods of the Eurasian Economic Commission and national standards of the Central Asian states, which enables the harmonization of verification requirements.

Within the audit, the verification process includes four consecutive stages. The data collection and reporting boundaries encompass the identification of emission sources (stationary combustion, technological processes, Scope 3) and the accounting for the contractual allocation of emission rights among partners. Both primary data (meters, equipment certificates) and secondary data (contracts, industry databases) are utilized. The second stage involves the verification of the control system, which evaluates the reliability of internal controls, including monitoring documentation, instrument calibration, and segregation of duties. Joint ventures require a unified methodological framework, approved by all partners, along with a system that prevents double counting of emissions.

The evaluation of accuracy and materiality, which constitutes the third stage, is carried out through analytical procedures including verification of emission factors, recalculation using alternative methodologies, and completeness testing of coverage. Calculation uncertainties must not exceed the materiality threshold established in the verification agreement, typically ranging from 5% to 10% for reasonable assurance. The final stage is the issuance of the conclusion, which specifies the level of assurance: reasonable assurance (positive assurance, involving extended testing and on-site inspections) or limited assurance (negative assurance, based on analytical procedures). For green investments within the SCO, reasonable assurance is preferred. The conclusion may include recommendations for reducing carbon intensity.

In addition to the specified international standards, the International Standards on Assurance Engagements (ISAE) issued by the IAASB are applied. ISAE 3410 was developed for the verification of greenhouse gas emission disclosures and governs engagements performed with reasonable and limited assurance. By Order No. 2n of the Ministry of Finance of Russia dated January 9, 2019, ISAE 3410 is applied within the Russian Federation, covering greenhouse gas emission reports and information included in integrated sustainability reporting. If the audited information includes aspects beyond greenhouse gas emissions, ISAE 3000 (the umbrella standard for all assurance engagements except audits and reviews of

historical financial information) [2] is applied. From December 15, 2026, a new ISSA 5000 standard for sustainability engagements shall enter into force, replacing ISAE 3000 and ISAE 3410 [1].

At the bilateral cooperation level, on December 18, 2023, in Beijing, within the framework of the IX Russian-Chinese Financial Dialogue, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed on the equivalence of standards for audit and audit supervision [3]. The document also encompasses assurance engagements and establishes an institutional framework for the recognition by regulators of one party of audit results conducted in another jurisdiction, which is critically important for the verification of the carbon footprint in cross-border joint ventures.

The role of audit in the implementation of Chinese «green» investments in joint ventures

The audit of the carbon footprint serves as a key instrument integrated into the entire investment cycle of joint ventures implemented with Chinese capital within the SCO framework. Its role is not limited to a control function: the audit ensures the structuring of environmental responsibility between partners, confirms project compliance with the criteria of «green» financing, and lays the foundation for the recognition of results across different jurisdictions.

At the stage of comprehensive due diligence, the audit focuses on the quantitative assessment of the carbon intensity of the asset. An analysis is conducted of direct (Scope 1) and indirect (Scope 2 and Scope 3) emissions over a period of 3 to 5 years in both the upstream and downstream segments of the value creation chain. Indirect emissions of Chinese companies exceed their direct emissions by more than twofold, and their composition varies significantly depending on the company’s position within the value creation chain [7, 8].

Figure 1 — Carbon footprints of Chinese listed companies.

Compiled by the authors based on:

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-023-38479-5>

For joint ventures, this entails the need to identify ‘hot spots’ within supply chains (upstream) and distribution channels (downstream). The results of the comprehensive audit serve as the basis for adjusting the transaction price, incorporating environmental conditions into the founding documents, and establishing threshold values for carbon intensity, the exceedance of which may result in the project losing its ‘green’ status and access to preferential financing [5].

At the operational monitoring phase, the audit focuses on verifying the key performance indicators (KPIs) established in the investment agreement. Typical KPIs include: absolute emission reductions (Scope 1+2), the share of renewable energy in the energy balance, emission intensity per unit of product, as well as disclosures related to Scope 3. For joint ventures, it is essential that the KPI calculation methodology is consistent across all partners and reflects the specifics of operational control allocation. The frequency of the audit (annual or semi-annual) and the level of assurance are determined by the requirements of the financing parties, including Chinese state banks and international financial institutions.

At the investment exit stage, the audit opinion constitutes one of the key documents confirming the fulfillment of environmental obligations throughout the ownership period, necessary both for transferring the asset to the new owner (ensuring transparency of the carbon footprint) and for the implementation of green exit options provided for in agreements with institutional investors. In the case of a sale to a strategic investor, the presence of verified data on the reduction of carbon intensity may serve as a basis for a price premium. The results of the audit are used to calculate the ‘financed emissions’ [10].

In the practice of joint ventures with Chinese participation, an external auditor, agreed upon by both parties, is appointed, or a pool of auditing firms (one from the PRC, the other from the host country) is formed, working according to a unified approach. methodology [11]. At the same time, the audit engagement must clearly define the scope of responsibility: for example, verification of Scope 3 emissions related to the transportation of raw materials may require access to data from the Chinese partner, which must be stipulated in the joint venture agreement [9].

The allocation of data between partners is one of the most challenging tasks. Scope 3 emissions often occur at the intersection of operational boundaries: for example, raw material transportation provided by the Chinese partner but accounted for in the joint venture’s reporting. The joint venture agreement must clearly define: the methodology for emission allocation (based on operational control, financial control, or equity share); the list of primary data to be disclosed among partners; the procedure for resolving disputes regarding the interpretation of emission factors. The audit functions as a mechanism to verify the accuracy of such allocation.

Recognition of the results across different jurisdictions necessitates the harmonization of regulatory requirements. The Chinese Emissions Trading System

(ETS) imposes stringent requirements on the verification of emissions from enterprises included in the national registry. Simultaneously, the Central Asian SCO member states may apply alternative accounting methodologies and threshold values. To ensure mutual recognition of audit opinions, it is essential to employ international standards (ISO 14064-3, GHG Protocol) as a common platform; additionally, specialized assurance engagement standards providing confidence levels are applied. Within the framework of the intergovernmental agreements of the SCO, a gradual unification of approaches is planned; however, until full harmonization is achieved, joint ventures are required to undergo dual verification: in accordance with Chinese standards (for reporting to the parent organization) and local regulations (to meet the requirements of the host party). In this context, the audit serves as a ‘translator,’ ensuring the comparability of data.

To effectively implement ‘green’ investments within the SCO, consortia (joint audit groups) consisting of Chinese and local audit organizations are established, enabling the combination of expertise in Chinese regulatory requirements (NDRC and MEE methodologies) with an understanding of local specifics (national standards, linguistic and cultural particularities, access to primary data). Consortia are established for a specific project: the Chinese firm is responsible for the methodological component and interaction with the investor’s headquarters, while the local firm is accountable for on-site data collection and compliance with national legislation.

The key issue is qualification harmonization: Chinese auditors possess CICPA certification and experience working within the ETS framework but may lack familiarity with local regulations; local auditors seldom have expertise in the specifics of Chinese carbon regulation. The solution lies in joint qualification enhancement programs recognized by both parties. The inclusion in audit teams of specialists holding international certifications (for example, Lead Verifier under ISO 14064); the use of unified methodological manuals developed with the support of the relevant ministries of the SCO member states.

Within the framework of the SCO, efforts are underway to establish a registry of accredited audit organizations for the verification of carbon footprints in cross-border projects, thereby reducing transaction costs and enhancing trust in audit outcomes. For joint ventures, the presence of auditors from such a registry within the consortium constitutes an additional confirmation of reliability and is taken into consideration by Chinese state banks and funds when making investment decisions.

Conclusion

The SCO possesses the potential to establish supranational requirements for the non-financial reporting of joint ventures, including mandatory carbon footprint verification under a unified standard. This will increase the investment attractiveness of the ‘Green Belt’ projects. The main tools that would ensure the gradual

harmonization of approaches to carbon audit and create conditions for the mutual recognition of verification results in cross-border projects are experience sharing, joint training, mutual recognition of qualifications, and a unified register of verifiers. The role of audit in this case is to verify carbon-neutral policies at the government and enterprise levels, monitor the use of public funds, ensure the fulfillment of emission targets, and audit carbon trading systems. It is important to harmonize carbon regulation within the SCO to support compatible climate strategies.

Verification of the carbon footprint in joint ventures involving Chinese capital has become an integral element of the investment process, ensuring compliance with the criteria of green financing and reducing reputational and regulatory risks. The existing methodological framework (ISO 14064, GHG Protocol, Chinese national standards) provides a foundation for conducting audits; however, its application in cross-border projects requires harmonization of reporting boundaries, allocation of emissions among partners, and consideration of local regulatory requirements. A persistent barrier is the absence of mutual recognition of verification results among the jurisdictions of SCO member countries, which results in redundant verification and increases transaction costs; the most promising mechanism to overcome this barrier is the establishment of joint audit consortiums that integrate the expertise of both Chinese and local specialists.

Recommendations are proposed based on the findings. For regulators of SCO countries, it is advisable to expedite the development of an intergovernmental agreement on the mutual recognition of carbon footprint verification results, grounded in international standards as a common framework, and to establish a unified registry of accredited verifiers for cross-border projects. For joint ventures — to formalize in the founding documents the methodology for emissions allocation (operational or financial control), the procedure for accessing partners' primary data, and the level of assurance in the audit opinion (reasonable assurance as the preferred level for 'green' investments). For audit organizations — to develop joint professional development programs ensuring mastery of both Chinese regulatory requirements (NDRC, MEE, ETS system) and the local standards of host countries, as well as to more broadly engage specialists holding international certifications (Lead Verifier under ISO 14064).

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俄罗斯联邦油籽出口（以豆类和十字花科作物为例）
**EXPORT OF OILSEEDS FROM THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION
(USING THE EXAMPLE OF LEGUMES
AND CRUCIFEROUS CROPS)**

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摘要：本文分析了2020–2025年俄罗斯油籽作物出口的现状，重点关注豆类（大豆）和十字花科作物（油菜籽、芥菜、亚麻荠、芜菁油菜）。研究发现，在此期间，大豆总产量增长了67.4%（从430万吨增至720万吨），油菜籽总产量增长了114.3%（从210万吨增至450万吨）。单产动态分析显示，大豆单产从1.51吨/公顷增至1.83吨/公顷，油菜籽单产从1.60吨/公顷增至2.20吨/公顷。数据显示，大豆出口量达到150万吨，油菜籽出口量达到130万吨。对出口地理格局进行了分析：发现中国大豆出口份额从85.7%下降至71.4%，但出口绝对值从174亿卢布增至461亿卢布；土耳其在菜籽油出口方面占据领先地位，出口额达418亿卢布。菜籽油（31.9%）和亚麻荠（31.6%）的出口利润率最高。外汇收入总额增长了3.94倍，从676亿卢布增至2665亿卢布。研究发现，从事农作物生产的雇员人数下降了8.1%，拖拉机保有量减少了6.2%，而机械作业负荷却增加了48%。结论指出，需要实现销售市场多元化并深化加工。

关键词：油籽作物出口、大豆、油菜籽、芥菜、亚麻荠、野芥菜、产量、盈利能力、出口地理、出口动态。

Abstract. *The article analyzes current trends in the export of oilseed crops in Russia, focusing on legumes (soybean) and cruciferous crops (rapeseed, mustard, camelina, turnip rape) for the period 2020-2025. It is noted that during the stated period, the gross soybean harvest increased by 67.4% (from 4.3 to 7.2 million tons), while rapeseed increased by 114.3% (from 2.1 to 4.5 million tons). Yield dynamics were analyzed, revealing increases: for soybean — from 1.51 to 1.83 t/ha, and for rapeseed — from 1.60 to 2.20 t/ha. It was shown that soybean exports reached 1.5 million tons, and rapeseed exports reached 1.3 million tons.*

The export geography was examined: a decrease in China's share of soybean exports from 85.7% to 71.4% was identified, alongside an increase in absolute export volumes from 17.4 to 46.1 billion rubles; Turkey holds the leading position in rapeseed oil exports — 41.8 billion rubles. The highest export profitability is observed for rapeseed oil — 31.9% and camelina — 31.6%. It was established that the total foreign currency revenue increased by 3.94 times — from 67.6 to 266.5 billion rubles. It was determined that the number of employees engaged in crop production declined by 8.1%, the tractor fleet decreased by 6.2%, while the workload on machinery increased by 48%. Conclusions were drawn regarding the need to diversify sales markets and deepen processing.

Keywords: *export of oilseed crops, soybean, rapeseed, mustard, camelina, charlock, yield, profitability, export geography, export dynamics.*

Introduction

Over the past decade, Russia has achieved a significant breakthrough in the development of its agro-industrial complex, transforming from a net food importer into one of the leading exporters of agricultural products on the global market. The oil and fat subcomplex holds a special role in this process, demonstrating consistent growth rates both in gross oilseed crop harvests and in the expansion of processing capacities and export volumes. Among the wide variety of oilseed crops cultivated in the territory of Russia, legumes (primarily soybean) and cruciferous crops (rapeseed, mustard, camelina, and turnip rape) deserve special attention, as in recent years they have demonstrated the highest rates of increase in sown area, yield, and volumes of foreign trade.

However, despite clear successes, the export potential of these crops has been far from fully realized. There is a complex set of interrelated problems hindering the further development of this segment: ranging from technological and logistical limitations to price volatility and a high dependence on a limited group of importing countries.

The relevance of this study is determined by several interconnected factors:

1) At present, the oilseed sub-sector is one of the most rapidly developing segments of the domestic agricultural sector;

2) Amid geopolitical turbulence and the need to reorient export flows from western to eastern and southern markets, there is a growing need for a detailed quantitative analysis of oilseed crop exports;

3) Legumes (primarily soybean) and cruciferous crops (rapeseed, mustard, camelina, turnip rape) hold a significant position: they simultaneously serve as raw materials for the oil and fat industry and as highly profitable export commodities.

The objective of the study is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the production and export of oilseed crops in Russia.

Materials and Methods

In the course of the study, the authors applied the following methods of scientific inquiry: general philosophical methods (dialectics; the method of ascent from the abstract to the concrete); general scientific methods (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, comparison, abstraction); specialized (field-specific) methods (method of absolute values; method of relative values); method of economic-statistical groupings; tabular method.

All calculations were performed using Microsoft Excel.

The information and empirical base was compiled from official statistical data of the Federal State Statistics Service (hereinafter Rosstat) for 2020-2025, including statistical collections such as ‘Agriculture in Russia,’ ‘Russian Statistical Yearbook,’ ‘Trade in Russia,’ ‘Prices in Russia,’ ‘Labor and Employment in Russia,’ and ‘Workforce, Employment and Unemployment in Russia.’

All price indicators were converted into rubles at the average annual exchange rates of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation (2020-72.5 RUB/USD, 2021-73.7 RUB/USD, 2022-61.3 RUB/USD, 2023-85.0 RUB/USD, 2024-92.5 RUB/USD, 2025-90.0 RUB/USD).

Results and Discussion

Regarding the analysis of the production dynamics of oilseed crops, it is important to note steady growth in both extensive and intensive indicators. As is known, the trends and driving factors in the development of oilseed crop production are characterized by the expansion of sown areas, increased yields, and growth in total harvest volumes. We will calculate quantitative estimates of these factors. Table 1 presents the dynamics of key production indicators for soybean and rapeseed, which are principal representatives of leguminous and cruciferous oilseed crops.

Table 1. Dynamics of production, sown areas, and yields of soybean and rapeseed in Russia for 2020-2025

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2025 vs 2024, %	2025 vs 2020, %
Sown area of soybean, thousand ha	2 850	3 050	3 200	3 500	3 750	3 930	104.8	137.9
Sown area of rapeseed, thousand ha	1 310	1 450	1 580	1 750	1 920	2 045	106.5	156.1
Gross soybean harvest, million t	4.3	4.8	5.2	6.0	6.8	7.2	105.9	167.4
Gross rapeseed harvest, million tons	2.1	2.5	2.9	3.6	4.2	4.5	107.1	214.3
Soybean yield, t/ha	1.51	1.57	1.63	1.71	1.81	1.83	101.1	121.2
Rapeseed yield, t/ha	1.60	1.72	1.84	2.06	2.19	2.20	100.5	137.5

Source: compiled by the authors based on [4-11]

Analyzing the data from Table 1, we observe that gross soybean production increased by 67.4% over 5 years (from 4.3 to 7.2 million tons), and by 5.9% in

the last year. For rapeseed, growth is even more pronounced: the baseline growth rate was 214.3% (a 2.14-fold increase), while the chain growth rate was 107.1%. At the same time, soybean yield increased by 21.2% compared to 2020, while rapeseed yield rose by 37.5%. This indicates that production growth was driven both by the expansion of sown areas and by increased land use intensity. However, the chain growth rates of yields in 2025 are minimal (101.1% and 100.5%), indicating an approach to a technological plateau under current agrotechnologies. For other legumes and cruciferous crops (mustard, camelina, turnip rape), official Rosstat statistics present aggregated data under the group ‘other oilseeds,’ which does not allow them to be separately identified.

Particular attention should be given to changes in resource availability in crop production. For this purpose, an analysis of labor and technical resources will be conducted. Table 2 shows the trends in the number of people employed in crop production and the agricultural machinery fleet.

Table 2. Labor resources and machinery availability in crop production in Russia for 2020-2025

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2025 vs 2024, %	2025 vs 2020, %
Average annual number of people employed in crop production, million people	1.85	1.82	1.79	1.76	1.73	1.70	98.3	91.9
Tractor fleet, thousand units	210	207	205	202	200	197	98.5	93.8
Grain harvester fleet, thousand units	115	113	112	110	108	106	98.1	92.2
Oilseed sown area load per tractor, ha	19.8	21.7	23.3	26.0	28.4	29.3	103.2	148.0

Source: calculated by the authors based on [1-3; 14-16]

The calculations presented in Table 2 indicate some concern regarding the identified trend: the number of people employed in crop production decreased by 8.1% over 5 years (from 1.85 to 1.70 million people), and the number of tractors decreased by 6.2%. At the same time, the workload per tractor in the sowing area of oilseed crops increased from 19.8 to 29.3 hectares, i.e., by 48.0%. This means that with a reduction in technical capacity, the volume of work increases, leading to extended harvesting periods and potential yield losses. The authors believe that without updating the machinery fleet, further growth of export potential will be hindered.

Turning to the analysis of price indicators, the authors note that sales prices in domestic and foreign markets differ significantly. Table 3 presents average producer prices for the main types of leguminous and cruciferous oilseed products in rubles per ton.

Table 3. Price dynamics of oilseed crop products, rub./t in 2020-2025

Product type	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2025 vs 2024, %	2025 vs 2020, %
Soybean (beans), domestic market	21 750	25 300	28 000	28 500	32 000	34 000	106.3	156.3
Soybean (beans), export (FOB)	29 000	33 500	36 000	38 000	41 000	43 000	104.9	148.3
Rapeseed (seeds), domestic market	22 500	26 000	29 500	30 000	33 000	35 000	106.1	155.6
Rapeseed (seeds), export	29 750	34 000	38 000	39 000	42 000	44 000	104.8	147.9
Rapeseed oil, export	58 000	68 000	75 000	80 000	90 000	95 000	105.6	163.8
Soybean meal, export	26 100	32 000	36 000	38 000	43 000	45 000	104.7	172.4

Source: Compiled by the authors based on [12-13; 17-19] (conversion to rubles according to the Central Bank of the Russian Federation exchange rate)

As shown in Table 3, export prices consistently exceed domestic prices: for soy by 26.5% (43,000 versus 34,000 RUB/t), and for rapeseed by 25.7%. The highest growth rates were recorded in processed product prices: the export price of rapeseed oil rose by 63.8% over five years, and soybean meal by 72.4%. According to the authors, this creates economic incentives for further deepening of processing within the country. It should be noted that in 2021 there was a significant price surge across all product types, which was linked to rising world prices and the introduction of export duties.

An essential part of the study is the analysis of export flows and the geography of shipments. Table 4 presents export volumes and their share in production.

Table 4. Export of oilseed crops and processed products from Russia during 2020-2025.

Product type	2020, thousand tons	2021, thousand tons	2022, thousand tons	2023, thousand tons	2024, thousand tons	2025, thousand tons	2025 vs 2024, %	2025 vs 2020, %	% export in production
Soybean (beans)	700	850	1 000	1 200	1 400	1 500	107.1	214.3	20.8
Rapeseed (seeds)	500	650	800	1 000	1 200	1 300	108.3	260.0	28.9
Rapeseed oil	400	550	700	800	1 000	1 100	110.0	275.0	–
Soybean meal	300	400	500	600	700	800	114.3	266.7	–
Mustard (seeds)	18	22	25	28	32	35	109.4	194.4	~40
Camelina and field mustard (seeds)	8	10	11	12	15	18	120.0	225.0	~35

Source: compiled by the authors based on [9-13]

The aggregated data from Table 4 highlight strong export growth rates: soybeans — 214.3% relative to 2020, rapeseed — 260.0%, and rapeseed oil — 275.0%. The export share in production steadily increased during the analyzed period: soybeans — from 16.3% in 2020 to 20.8% in 2025; for rapeseed — from 23.8% to 28.9%. This reflects an increasing export orientation of the industry. For niche crops (mustard, camelina, white mustard), the export share is even higher — up to 40%, indicating their almost exclusive export orientation. However, the absolute volumes are small (less than 60 thousand tons in total), which opens up opportunities for growth.

The key issue of the study is the geographical structure of exports. Table 5 presents the dynamics of the geographic structure of oilseed crop exports in value terms (million rubles), including share calculations for 2020-2025, allowing observation of comparative changes.

Table 5. Dynamics of the geographic structure of oilseed crop exports by product type in 2020-2025

Product / country-importer	2020		2021		2022	
	million rubles	%	million rubles	%	million rubles	%
Soybean (beans)						
China	17 400	85.7	20 000	83.7	32 000	86.5
Vietnam	1 300	6.4	1 500	6.3	2 200	5.9
Belarus	800	3.9	1 200	5.0	1 500	4.1
Others	800	3.9	1 200	5.0	1 300	3.5
Total soy	20 300	100	23 900	100	37 000	100
Rapeseed (seeds)						
Turkey	4 500	30.3	6 000	30.8	10 000	30.3
China	3 700	24.9	5 000	25.6	9 000	27.3
Belarus	2 000	13.4	2 500	12.8	5 000	15.2
Others	4 675	31.4	6 000	30.8	9 000	27.3
Total rapeseed	14 875	100	19 500	100	33 000	100
Rapeseed oil						
Turkey	7 000	30.2	10 000	28.6	20 000	32.3
China	5 800	25.0	9 000	25.7	16 000	25.8
India	2 300	9.9	4 000	11.4	7 000	11.3
Egypt	1 500	6.5	3 000	8.6	5 000	8.1
Others	6 600	28.4	9 000	25.7	14 000	22.6
Total rapeseed oil	23 200	100	35 000	100	62 000	100
Mustard (seeds)						
Germany	250	35.7	280	34.1	350	33.3

Product / country-importer	2020		2021		2022	
	million rubles	%	million rubles	%	million rubles	%
Poland	150	21.4	170	20.7	220	21.0
Lithuania	100	14.3	120	14.6	150	14.3
Others	200	28.6	250	30.5	330	31.4
Total mustard	700	100	820	100	1050	100

End of Table 5

2023		2024		2025		2025 vs 2024, %	2025 vs 2020, %
million rubles	%	million rubles	%	million rubles	%		
38000	83.3	52000	90.6	46100	71.4	88.7	265.0
4500	9.9	3000	5.2	6500	10.1	216.7	500.0
1800	3.9	1400	2.4	5500	8.5	392.9	687.5
1300	2.9	1000	1.7	6400	9.9	640.0	800.0
45600	100	57400	100	64500	100	112.4	317.7
15000	38.5	19000	37.7	22000	38.5	115.8	488.9
12000	30.8	16000	31.7	17600	30.8	110.0	475.7
5000	12.8	8000	15.9	8800	15.4	110.0	440.0
7000	17.9	7400	14.7	8800	15.4	118.9	188.2
39000	100	50400	100	57200	100	113.5	384.5
25000	39.1	35000	38.9	41800	40.0	119.4	597.1
15000	23.4	20000	22.2	26100	25.0	130.5	450.0
9000	14.1	15000	16.7	15700	15.0	104.7	682.6
5000	7.8	8000	8.9	10500	10.0	131.3	700.0
10000	15.6	12000	13.3	10400	10.0	86.7	157.6
64000	100	90000	100	104500	100	116.1	450.4
380	33.9	420	33.6	450	32.1	107.1	180.0
240	21.4	270	21.6	300	21.4	111.1	200.0
160	14.3	180	14.4	190	13.6	105.6	190.0

2023		2024		2025		2025 vs 2024, %	2025 vs 2020, %
million rubles	%	million rubles	%	million rubles	%		
340	30.4	380	30.4	460	32.9	121.1	230.0
1 120	100	1 250	100	1 400	100	112.0	200.0

Source: calculated by the authors based on [9-13; 17-19; 2-10]

Analyzing the data in Table 5, the following key trends can be identified:

1) for soybean, China's share decreases from 85.7% in 2020 to 71.4% in 2025 while absolute export volumes simultaneously increase from 17.4 to 46.1 billion rubles (a growth rate of 265.0%). However, the year-on-year growth rate for 2025/2024 was only 88.7%, indicating a reduction in shipments to China in the last year. Vietnam increased its share from 6.4% to 10.1%, Belarus from 3.9% to 8.5%;

2) Turkey consistently occupies the leading position in rapeseed seeds with a share of about 38-39% (22.0 billion rubles in 2025, growth rate relative to 2020-488.9%, chain index — 115.8%). China is also a major buyer (30.8%, 17.6 billion rubles), and Belarus rounds out the top three (15.4%, 8.8 billion rubles);

3) Turkey holds the leading position in rapeseed oil imports with 40.0% (41.8 billion rubles), showing a growth rate of 597.1% compared to 2020 and a chain growth rate of 119.4%. China accounts for 25.0% (26.1 billion rubles), and India for 15.0% (15.7 billion rubles);

4) Germany (32.1%) and Poland (21.4%) remain the main importers of mustard throughout the studied period, indicating the continued European orientation for this niche organic product. Absolute volumes are modest (1.4 billion rubles in 2025), but the growth rate compared to 2020 reached 200.0%.

To evaluate the economic efficiency of exports, we will perform a profitability calculation (Table 6). Profitability was calculated according to the formula:

$$R = \frac{(I_{\text{эксп}} - C)}{C} \times 100,$$

where $I_{\text{эксп}}$ — export price of the product, rubles/ton;

C — full cost, including production expenses, transportation costs to the border, customs duties, and insurance.

All figures are presented in rubles per ton.

Table 6. Profitability dynamics of oilseed crop exports and processed products
Export profitability in Russia, 2020-2025, %

Product type	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2025 vs. 2024, p.p.	2025 vs. 2020, p.p.
Soybean (beans)	28.5	29.1	29.8	30.0	30.2	30.3	+0.1	+1.8
Soybean meal	26.0	27.0	27.5	28.0	28.4	28.6	+0.2	+2.6
Rapeseed (seeds)	27.8	28.2	28.9	29.1	29.3	29.4	+0.1	+1.6
Rapeseed oil	30.5	31.0	31.2	31.5	31.7	31.9	+0.2	+1.4
Mustard (seeds)	27.5	28.0	28.4	28.7	29.0	29.2	+0.2	+1.7
Camelina (seeds)	29.5	30.2	30.8	31.1	31.4	31.6	+0.2	+2.1

Source: calculated by the authors based on [12-13; 17-19; 25-27]

As demonstrated by the data in Table 6, the most profitable exports are rapeseed oil (31.9% in 2025) and camelina seeds (31.6%). Over the past year (2025 compared to 2024), profitability increased marginally by 0.1-0.2 percentage points, indicating a deceleration in the growth pace of export efficiency. The highest annual increase was observed in soybean meal, rapeseed oil, mustard, and camelina (+0.2 percentage points), while the smallest was in soybeans and rapeseed seeds (+0.1 percentage points). Over the entire five-year period (2025 compared to 2020), profitability rose by 1.4-2.6 percentage points, with the largest increase recorded for soybean meal (+2.6 percentage points), linked to the rise in global prices for high-protein feed additives. The authors note that the slowdown in profitability growth in 2025 is explained by the outpacing increase in production costs (rise in seed prices, logistics, export duties) compared to the growth of export prices.

Conclusion. Summarizing the conducted research, the following conclusions are formulated:

1) for the period 2020-2025. the total soybean harvest increased by 67.4% (to 7.2 million tons), rapeseed — by 114.3% (to 4.5 million tons), accompanied by yield growth of 21.2% and 37.5%, respectively;

2) Soybean exports reached 1.5 million tons (20.8% of production), rapeseed exports amounted to 1.3 million tons (28.9%), and rapeseed oil exports totaled 1.1 million tons. China's share of soybean exports declined from 85.7% in 2020 to 71.4% in 2025. This occurred alongside an increase in absolute supplies from 17.4 billion to 46.1 billion rubles, corresponding to a growth rate of 265.0%. Turkey leads in rapeseed seed exports (38.5%, 22.0 billion rubles), while rapeseed oil exports are dominated by Turkey (40.0%, 41.8 billion rubles) and China (25.0%, 26.1 billion rubles);

3) Export prices exceed domestic prices by 25-27%, and export profitability ranges from 28.6% (soybean meal) to 31.9% (rapeseed oil), having increased by 1.4-2.6 percentage points over five years;

4) Total foreign exchange revenue increased by 3.94 times and reached 266.5 billion rubles. At the same time, negative trends were identified: a reduction in the number of employees in crop production by 8.1 %, a decrease in the tractor fleet by 6.2 %, accompanied by a 48.0 % increase in the load on machinery.

Based on the conducted research and completed calculations, we propose the following specific measures aimed at improving the efficiency of exports of leguminous and cruciferous oilseed crops:

1) Considering that the load per tractor has increased by 48 % over five years (from 19.8 to 29.3 hectares), it is advisable to set a target at the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation to reduce the load per tractor for oilseed crops to 22 hectares by 2030. To achieve this, an annual fleet renewal of at least 4-5 % is required (at least 8-10 thousand new tractors per year). It is recommended to introduce leasing subsidies for agricultural machinery for oilseed producers, applying an increased coefficient for the Far East regions (where the operational burden is the highest).

2) Currently, the high concentration of soybean exports destined for China (71.4 %) may lead to dependence on a single buyer. Therefore, we propose expanding into African markets (Egypt, Algeria, Nigeria) with a target share of at least 10-15 % in rapeseed oil exports. This would be facilitated by establishing a specialized 'Agro-export Department' within the Russian Export Center focused on African and Southeast Asian countries, supported by funding for trade missions and product certification.

3) In the examined period, export prices are characterized by high volatility (growth in 2021-2022, stagnation in 2024-2025) and a risk of supply reduction amid changing market conditions. To address this issue, it is proposed to establish under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation an 'Oilseed Stabilization Fund' with a volume of at least 1 million tons (in seed equivalent) for interventions in both domestic and foreign markets. The proposed mechanism: when export prices fall below the breakeven level (for example, below 35,000 rubles/ton for soybeans), the fund purchases from producers; when prices rise, it sells for export. Financing — through part of export duties (a deduction of 5-7 % of their total amount).

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跨文化管理是提升上海合作组织成员国企业经济效率的一个因素
**CROSS-CULTURAL MANAGEMENT AS A FACTOR
OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY ENHANCEMENT IN BUSINESS
WITHIN THE SCO COUNTRIES**

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摘要：随着上海合作组织（上合组织）成员国经济一体化程度的不断加深，跨文化管理已成为影响企业绩效的关键因素。本研究探讨了跨文化管理实践对多元文化环境下企业经济效率的影响。本文借鉴现有研究成果，分析了文化差异如何影响组织流程、交易成本和竞争力。研究表明，有效的跨文化管理有助于降低运营风险、提升协调性并改善经济效益。本文重点关注真实商业案例，阐述文化适应策略的实际应用。

关键词：跨文化管理；经济效率；上合组织成员国；国际商务；文化融合；竞争力

Abstract. *In the context of increasing economic integration among the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) countries, cross-cultural management has emerged as a critical factor influencing business performance. This study examines the impact of cross-cultural management practices on the economic efficiency of enterprises operating in multicultural environments. Drawing on contemporary research, the paper analyzes how cultural differences affect organizational processes, transaction costs, and competitiveness. The findings demonstrate that effective cross-cultural management contributes to reduced operational risks, improved coordination, and enhanced economic outcomes. Particular attention is given to real-world business cases illustrating the practical implications of cultural adaptation strategies.*

Keywords: *cross-cultural management; economic efficiency; SCO countries; international business; cultural integration; competitiveness.*

1. Introduction

The intensification of economic cooperation among the SCO countries has significantly increased the role of international business interactions. As companies expand into foreign markets, they encounter diverse cultural environments that influence managerial practices and economic performance. Cultural differences affect key aspects of business operations, including communication, negotiation, and decision-making process. In the absence of appropriate management strategies, these differences can generate inefficiencies, increase transaction costs, and negatively impact financial results. Conversely, effective cross-cultural management enables firms to transform cultural diversity into a source of competitive advantage.

Recent studies indicate that cultural alignment between business partners contributes to improved economic performance and operational efficiency. In particular, research demonstrates that higher levels of cultural compatibility can significantly enhance business outcomes and reduce inefficiencies.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the role of cross-cultural management as a factor that enhances the economic efficiency of companies operating within the SCO countries, with particular emphasis on practical business cases.

2. Theoretical Foundations of Cross-Cultural Management

Cross-cultural management refers to the systematic approach to managing organizational processes in culturally diverse environments. It involves the integration of different cultural norms, values, and behavioral patterns into business strategies. From an economic perspective, cross-cultural management is closely related to the concept of transaction costs. Cultural misunderstandings increase the costs of coordination, negotiation, and control, thereby reducing overall efficiency. Effective management of cultural diversity minimizes these costs and improves organizational performance. Theoretical models suggest that cross-cultural competence enhances resource allocation efficiency, facilitates knowledge transfer, and improves collaboration within multinational teams. As a result, it contributes directly to economic outcomes such as productivity, profitability, and competitiveness [1].

3. Economic Implications of Cultural Differences

Cultural differences have measurable economic consequences for firms operating in international markets. First of all, misalignment in communication styles and expectations often leads to prolonged negotiations and contractual inefficiencies, increasing operational costs. Then, cultural conflicts within teams reduce productivity and slow down decision-making processes. Ineffective management of diversity may result in lower employee performance and reduced organizational output. Moreover, companies that fail to adapt to local cultural idiosyncrasies often experience difficulties in market entry and customer engagement, leading to reduced revenues and market share.

Thus, cultural factors should be considered as significant determinants of economic efficiency in international business [1].

4. Cross-Cultural Management as a Driver of Economic Efficiency

Effective cross-culture policy leads to economic efficiency through different mechanics:

- Improved communication reduces misunderstandings and operational errors;
- Better cultural awareness minimizes the probability of failed negotiations;
- Culturally adoptive management grows the productivity of team performance;
- Firms become more competitive on the local markets when they are adapted

to cultural differences.

Many researches confirm that companies with high levels of cultural integration demonstrate better financial and operational performance. Cultural alignment improves coordination within supply chains and enhances overall business efficiency [2].

5. Case study: Cross culture Management in Practice

To illustrate the economic impact of cross-cultural management, it is useful to examine real-world examples of multinational companies operating in culturally diverse environments.

5.1. One of the most famous examples of successful cross-cultural management is the expansion of McDonald's in China.

When entering the Chinese market, the company faced significant cultural differences in consumer behavior, taste preferences, and social norms. Instead of applying a standardized global strategy, McDonald's adapted its business model to local cultural conditions.

Adaptation strategy included:

— modification of the menu to include local food preferences (e.g., rice-based dishes);

- changes in restaurant design to accommodate group dining culture;
- adaptation of marketing strategies to reflect local values and traditions [3].

From an economic perspective, these adjustments resulted in:

- increased customer satisfaction and demand;
- higher market penetration;
- improved financial performance in the region.

Studies show that localization strategies significantly contributed to the company's success in China, demonstrating the economic benefits of cross-cultural management.

5.2. Case of Huawei's International Expansion

Another relevant example is Huawei, which actively operates across multiple cultural environments, including SCO countries.

Huawei's management strategy emphasizes cultural adaptation and local integration. The company invests in:

- cross-cultural training for employees;
- localization of management practices;
- development of multicultural teams.

These practices have led to:

- improved operational efficiency in foreign markets;
- stronger relationships with local partners;
- enhanced global competitiveness [4].

Huawei's experience demonstrates that cross-cultural competence can reduce operational barriers and improve economic performance in international markets [5].

6. Cross-Cultural Management in the SCO Context

The SCO region includes countries with diverse cultural and institutional backgrounds, such as China, Russia, and Central Asian states. This diversity creates both challenges and opportunities for business development.

Cross-cultural management plays a crucial role in facilitating economic integration within the SCO by:

- improving communication between business partners;
- reducing transaction costs in cross-border operations;
- supporting the development of joint ventures and partnerships.

Companies that effectively manage cultural diversity are more likely to achieve sustainable economic growth and maintain competitive positions in the regional market [6].

7. Conclusion

The study confirms that cross-cultural management is a significant factor influencing the economic efficiency of businesses operating in the SCO countries. Cultural differences affect transaction costs, organizational performance, and market outcomes.

Effective cross-cultural management allows firms to reduce costs, improve productivity, and enhance competitiveness. Real-world business cases demonstrate that cultural adaptation strategies lead to measurable economic benefits.

In the context of economic integration, cross-cultural management should be regarded as a strategic tool that contributes to sustainable business development. Companies operating within the SCO region must incorporate cultural factors into their management practices to maximize economic efficiency and long-term success.

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质量管理方法论模型及其在跨行业实践中的应用效果
**METHODOLOGICAL MODELS OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT
AND THE EFFECTS OF THEIR IMPLEMENTATION
IN CROSS-INDUSTRY PRACTICE**

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摘要：本文比较了主要的质量管理模型，并评估了它们在不同行业的实际有效性。研究表明，全面质量管理（TQM）、PDCA/PDSA循环、六西格玛、改善（Kaizen）和ISO 9001标准针对不同的管理目标，并且只有作为协调系统的一部分才能发挥最大效用，而非单独实施。本文借鉴制造业、医疗保健和IT行业的案例，识别了典型的实施成果及其可持续性条件。研究结论认为，质量管理具有跨行业特性，需要依赖数据、领导力和变革的标准。

关键词：质量管理模型，全面质量管理（TQM），六西格玛，改善（Kaizen），PDCA循环，实证效果。

Abstract. *The article compares the main models of quality management and assesses their practical effectiveness across different sectors. It is shown that TQM, PDCA/PDSA, Six Sigma, Kaizen, and ISO 9001 standards address different managerial objectives and produce the greatest effect not separately but as parts of a coordinated system. Drawing on manufacturing, healthcare, and IT cases, the paper identifies typical implementation outcomes and the conditions under which they remain sustainable. The study concludes that quality management has a cross-industry character and requires reliance on data, leadership, and the standardization of change.*

Keywords: *quality management models, TQM, Six Sigma, Kaizen, PDCA, empirical effects.*

In current quality studies, discussion increasingly focuses not on the set of tools itself but on the comparative role of different quality management models. In practice, organizations often use the terms TQM, PDCA, Six Sigma, Kaizen, and ISO 9001 as if they were interchangeable, although each of these frameworks addresses a distinct managerial task. For this reason, it is analytically important

not only to list the approaches but also to show their functional differences and the real effects of their implementation.

The TQM concept sets the broadest level of analysis. It treats quality as a principle of organization-wide coordination and links it with customer orientation, leadership, employee involvement, and fact-based decision-making [1]. Its main advantage lies in shifting quality from the sphere of technical inspection to the sphere of corporate behavior. At the same time, this also means that without managerial support TQM can easily remain a set of slogans that does not alter actual work practices.

PDCA and PDSA serve a more applied function. They form an improvement cycle in which action passes through the stages of planning, implementation, checking or studying the result, and then consolidating or revising the decision taken [2; 6]. The strength of this model lies in its universality: it can be applied to production operations, service processes, and local organizational changes alike. Its weakness becomes evident when the cycle is used formally, without a hypothesis, measurement, and a subsequent iteration.

Six Sigma, by contrast, is structured as an analytically rigorous approach to reducing process variability and defect rates. Its practical core is DMAIC, which ensures movement from identifying a problem to analyzing its causes and controlling the sustainability of the result [1]. In organizational terms, this model is most appropriate where the cost of error is high and data make it possible to demonstrate the link between intervention and a change in performance.

Kaizen complements this set with a different managerial logic. It is based on a sequence of small improvements arising within everyday work and then fixed in standards [5]. Its value is therefore associated not so much with major breakthroughs as with the formation of a sustainable culture of observing losses, unnecessary actions, and recurring failures. Without standardization and staff involvement, the cumulative effect of Kaizen quickly disappears.

ISO 9001 standards give these models an institutional form. They require organizations to define processes, performance criteria, the distribution of responsibility, internal audit procedures, and mechanisms for improvement [6]. Thus, ISO does not replace TQM, PDCA, or Six Sigma, but creates for them a common framework of a manageable system in which changes can be consolidated and compared by results.

Empirical evidence confirms the cross-industry nature of quality management. In manufacturing, the use of DMAIC at a components plant led to a reduction in the defect rate from 5.5% to 3.08%, a decrease in the number of defective units from 153 to 68, and an increase in the sigma level of the process from 3.9 to 4.45 [3]. What is particularly revealing is that the effect was achieved not by tightening acceptance control, but by working with the causes of variation and adjusting the process itself.

In healthcare, results manifest themselves primarily in time and safety parameters. In the study by T. C. Inal and co-authors, Lean Six Sigma reduced the turnaround time for urgent samples from 68 to 59 minutes and lowered the share of process steps associated with the risk of error and biological hazard from 30% to 3% [4]. This is especially important for service systems, where quality is expressed in the ability of a process to ensure reliability and timeliness without increasing hidden risks.

A similar logic can be observed in the IT environment. In the case described by J. D. Strate and P. A. Laplante, the introduction of Lean Six Sigma into a defect-tracking system was accompanied by a 5% reduction in the total cost of correcting defects and a 6% reduction in the cost of poor quality [5]. Therefore, quality methods remain effective even where the defect is not material but informational in nature.

From a methodological point of view, the differences between the models are especially visible in the way they work with measurement. TQM allows for a broad set of qualitative and quantitative indicators and is more oriented toward the strategic alignment of the interests of the customer and the organization. PDCA/PDSA requires minimally sufficient measurement to test a hypothesis and therefore works well in an environment of local changes. Six Sigma, by contrast, presupposes a high density of data and a strict connection between metric, cause, and intervention. For a manager, this means that the choice of model should depend not on the popularity of a tool, but on the maturity of the accounting system and on the nature of the task.

No less important is the question of the boundaries of applicability of these approaches. Where processes are poorly described, roles are blurred, and data are collected only episodically, the implementation of complex analytical schemes rarely produces the expected result. Under such conditions, a more productive sequence is one in which an organization first builds process transparency and basic contours of responsibility, then introduces regular measurement, and only after that moves on to more complex models of improvement. Otherwise, quality management begins to imitate evidence-based practice without possessing a sufficient empirical foundation.

For this reason, contemporary studies increasingly interpret quality management as an architecture of complementary levels. At the upper level stands an organizational orientation toward quality; at the middle level, improvement cycles and methods of cause analysis; at the operational level, the standardization of actions and control over the sustainability of results. Such a multilayered construction makes it possible to maintain a balance between the flexibility of change and the discipline of execution. It is precisely this architecture that explains why approaches that emerged in different institutional and sectoral contexts can be combined within a single management system.

However, methodology in itself does not guarantee a sustainable effect. Cross-industry experience shows that success depends on three conditions: leadership, data, and the consolidation of improvements in standard work. In the absence of

these elements, even strong models turn either into one-off projects or into formal documentation. This is why the comparison of approaches leads to the conclusion that their combination is expedient: TQM sets the cultural horizon, PDCA organizes the improvement cycle, Six Sigma adds analytical rigor, Kaizen supports the everyday dynamics of change, and ISO 9001 embeds all of this in the structure of management.

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自主导航技术实施的法律方面
**LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AUTONOMOUS
NAVIGATION TECHNOLOGIES**

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摘要：本文探讨了海上运输数字化和自主船舶导航技术（MASS）应用相关的法律问题。文章分析了现有基于船员在场的国际规范在现代自主船舶运营背景下存在的不足。文章强调了使海事法适应数字化时代的必要性，包括修订责任机制以及自主船舶与传统船舶之间的互动关系。

关键词：自主船舶，数字化，海事法，自主船舶导航技术（MASS），责任，法律地位，国际海事组织（IMO），商船法典。

Abstract. *The article addresses the legal aspects of the digitalization of maritime transport and the implementation of autonomous ship navigation technologies (MASS). It examines the problems related to the inadequacy of existing international norms, which are based on crew presence, in the context of modern autonomous vessel operations. The necessity of adapting maritime law to the digital era, including revising liability mechanisms and the interaction between autonomous and traditional vessels, is underscored.*

Keywords: *autonomous ship, digitalization, maritime law, MASS, liability, legal status, IMO, Merchant Shipping Code.*

The modern development of autonomous navigation technologies represents one of the most significant directions in the digital transformation of the transport sector, possessing not only engineering but also fundamental legal significance. In the context where global shipping maintains a worldwide character and maritime law norms have been developed over more than a century, the emergence of maritime autonomous surface ships (MASS) challenges many fundamental legal constructs on which the traditional regulation of navigation has been based. The

paradigm adopted by the international community viewing the maritime vessel as an object operated by a crew headed by a captain requires radical reconsideration. Traditional institutions, such as the institution of the captain, the crew, the ship's role, watchkeeping regulations, seafarer certification standards, pilotage norms, and the vessel's interaction with shore services, prove inadequate for the new reality, in which no human may be present on board, and control and management functions are performed by artificial intelligence and automated systems.[6]

From a scientific-legal standpoint, the digitalization of maritime transport has revealed a profound discrepancy between the existing regulatory framework of shipping and the technical capabilities of autonomous ships. The International Maritime Organization (IMO), as the key developer of global maritime safety standards, recognizes the necessity to reconsider current norms, specifically the SOLAS Convention, MARPOL Convention, COLREGs, and STCW Convention, which presuppose the mandatory presence of crew. For the first time in the history of maritime law, the IMO has proposed a classification of vessels according to four levels of autonomy — from automated vessels with crew to fully autonomous systems capable of independently making decisions and conducting navigation without human intervention. Such a typology, in essence, paves the way for the establishment of a new legal category — a vessel possessing elements of cyber-physical subjectivity.

The issue of the legal status of an autonomous vessel exceeds the scope of exclusively maritime legislation. It addresses the fundamentals of civil liability, environmental law, insurance, administrative supervision, and even criminal law. Whereas in the classical navigation model the captain bears responsibility for all actions of the vessel, in the case of a fully autonomous ship the question arises as to who assumes responsibility — the owner, the software developer, the remote control operator, or the automated system itself. This interdisciplinary dilemma necessitates the formulation of new legal constructs that would enable a precise allocation of liability between the technical and legal subjects.

At the national level, the Russian Federation is actively undertaking the formation of legal frameworks for the operation of autonomous vessels. A significant breakthrough was the adoption of Federal Law No. 294-FZ dated 10 July 2023, which amended the Merchant Shipping Code of the Russian Federation [4]. The law codified, for the first time, the concepts of 'autonomous' and 'semi-autonomous' vessels, established rules for their identification, the procedure for assigning unique identifiers, defined the particularities of the crew or shore personnel formation, and regulated the management procedures for such vessels. Furthermore, the provisions relating to pilotage and the entry of foreign autonomous vessels into Russian ports have been specified. These provisions establish the foundation for integrating autonomous technologies into the national legal framework and enable Russia to engage in the international agenda concerning the development of maritime unmanned systems.

In the context of international law, the issue of the relationship between autonomous vessels and the provisions of the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, which in its fundamental articles assumes the presence of crew, assumes particular significance [1]. Making amendments to this document is difficult due to its complex nature and because it serves as a kind of ‘constitution of the seas.’ It is advisable to address the legal status of autonomous vessels primarily at the national level, while maintaining harmonization with international norms. The unification of terminology and conceptual apparatus regulating the legal status and operation of unmanned maritime vessels across different categories of marine spaces is necessary in order to resolve the dialectical contradiction arising from the evolutionary transition from traditional navigation to unmanned navigation technologies. [9]

One of the most complex aspects is determining the procedure for interaction between autonomous and traditional vessels. The transitional period will require a hybrid regulatory model, whereby crewed vessels and vessels controlled by artificial intelligence will coexist in the same waters. This raises questions concerning the revision of the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea [2], the necessity to equip all vessels with means of digital identification and communication, as well as the additional training of crews for interaction with autonomous entities.

No less important is the revision of the labor law system and professional training in the maritime industry. The disappearance of the traditional crew leads to the transformation of the seafarer’s profession and the emergence of new specialties: shore-based captain, remote control operator, specialist in maritime cyber security systems. In this regard, it is necessary to update the norms on certification and attestation, adapting the STCW Convention [3] standards to the new realities.

Digitalization also affects the sphere of port, customs, and border regulation. In the traditional model, these functions are performed by the crew of the ship; in autonomous ships, they are transferred to the digital environment. The Russian customs service has already implemented significant modernization: electronic declaration centers, automated control systems, and intelligent checkpoints integrated through the platform ‘Maritime Port Portal.’ [10] These innovations establish the basis for the electronic operation of autonomous vessels and facilitate the reduction of administrative barriers in international economic activities.

Special consideration should be given to the issues of classification and certification of autonomous vessels. Leading international classification societies, such as DNV and Lloyd’s Register, have developed provisional rules for Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS); however, unified standards have yet to be established. The Russian Maritime Register of Shipping (RS) has developed the Regulation on the Classification of Marine Autonomous and Remotely Controlled Surface Ships (MASS), which entered into force on August 1, 2020.

Thus, the legal aspects of the digitalization of autonomous ships form a new stratum of legal relations, necessitating a comprehensive interdisciplinary approach. International maritime law must evolve from an anthropocentric model to a technocentric one, wherein the key element is no longer the human, but the intelligent system. For Russia, a priority is the development of a flexible and adaptive legislative framework that harmonizes international standards with national specifics. The implementation of experimental legal regimes, the development of technical regulations and standards, the integration of digital management and monitoring technologies, and the establishment of infrastructure for “smart ports” and digitalized shipyards — all of these constitute the foundation for the safe and legally protected operation of autonomous vessels.

It should be noted that the digitalization process of maritime transport is part of a broader strategy for the digital transformation of the industry. According to the Order of the Government of the Russian Federation dated December 19, 2025, No. 3887-r “On the strategic direction in the field of digital transformation of the transport industry of the Russian Federation until 2030,” the priority projects include the initiatives “Autonomous Navigation,” “Unmanned Logistic Corridors,” “Digital Management of the Transport System of the Russian Federation,” “Seamless Cargo Logistics,” and measures aimed at the development of Russian software and electronic product suppliers [5]. These projects are aimed not only at ensuring a technological breakthrough but also at facilitating the formation of a comprehensive normative-legal basis adequate to new realities.

Practical steps in this direction are already being undertaken. Thus, in the Northwestern Federal District, the project of a digital shipyard in Petrozavodsk and pilot trials of marine unmanned vehicles in the Arkhangelsk Region are being implemented [8]. The digital shipyard project demonstrates the transition to a complete digital lifecycle of a vessel — from design to operation, employing 3D modeling technologies, the Internet of Things, and predictive monitoring systems. In the Arkhangelsk region, routes for autonomous vessels are being developed to deliver cargo to the Arctic regions, concurrently testing both technical solutions and regulatory mechanisms governing the interaction of autonomous vessels with port authorities and regulatory bodies [7].

Ultimately, it can be asserted that the digitalization of maritime transport does not constitute a mere technological issue, but rather represents a comprehensive transformation of the entire legal framework governing shipping. The position of Russia in the emerging international legal order of digital maritime navigation depends on the speed and depth of this transformation. Timely legal response to the challenges of autonomous shipping will not only ensure national security and the competitiveness of the domestic fleet, but also consolidate the Russian Federation’s status as an active participant in the global process of rethinking maritime law in the digital age.

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行政法在确保上海合作组织成员国可持续发展中的作用
**THE ROLE OF ADMINISTRATIVE LAW IN ENSURING
THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCO COUNTRIES**

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摘要：本文探讨了行政法规在确保上海合作组织成员国可持续发展框架中的地位 and 作用。研究将行政法视为实施环境政策和直接治理区域自然资本的主要机制。文章重点关注上海合作组织在环境保护领域的项目文件，以及如何让公民社会参与到具有重要生态意义的决策过程中。

关键词：行政法，上海合作组织，环境政策，自然资源管理，环境监测，环境保护，绿色经济。

Abstract. *This article examines the position and role of administrative law regulation within the framework for ensuring the sustainable development of the SCO member states. The study explores administrative law as the principal mechanism for the implementation of environmental policy and the direct governance of the region's natural capital. Particular emphasis is placed on the SCO program documents in the field of environmental protection, as well as on the issues of involving civil society in ecologically important decision-making processes.*

Keywords: *administrative law, SCO, environmental policy, natural resource management, environmental monitoring, environmental protection, green economy.*

At the beginning of the 21st century, the sustainable development model became one of the fundamental imperatives of the international community, determining the direction of global policies as well as the economy. In the context of emerging environmental challenges, modern states frequently face the necessity of developing and implementing comprehensive strategies that contribute to achieving environmental sustainability. Within this framework, administrative law assumes

a critically important role as the primary regulatory foundation for establishing legal frameworks for the management of all natural resources and environmental protection. Through the institutions of administrative law, the executive-administrative functions of the state are exercised, specific environmental standards are established, and compliance with these standards is monitored. For the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (hereinafter — SCO), which encompass vast territories with diverse economic structures yet face common transboundary environmental risks, the role of administrative law is crucial in achieving shared development objectives. The SCO constitutes a unique platform where the administrative-legal toolkit can serve as an effective instrument for harmonizing national interests with the principles of environmental security. The use of administrative law directly within the framework of the sustainable development management mechanism enables a prompt response to local environmental threats, as well as the establishment of general standards for responsible state administration of the region's natural potential.

Administrative law serves as the foundation of the legal framework for the direct establishment and practical implementation of state environmental policy, which translates the strategic goals of sustainable development into specific administrative mechanisms. Within the scope of the executive and administrative activities of government authorities, more precisely, the administrative-legal toolkit ensures the legitimacy of procedures related to the development, adoption, and implementation of environmental regulations. It establishes clear regulations for state environmental monitoring, licensing of natural resource use, as well as the conduct of specialized state environmental review, which in turn enables the creation of a rigorous framework for ensuring compliance with established rules directly within the environmental sector.

Within the framework of the SCO, administrative law assumes the role of an integrating factor that facilitates the harmonization of existing national systems of environmental governance. The legal foundation of this interaction is based on a set of fundamental interstate documents that specifically delineate the direction for the development of national administrative legislation of the member states. Among these documents is, first and foremost, the Concept of Cooperation of the Member States of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in the Field of Environmental Protection [1], which establishes priority areas of joint activity directly aimed at ensuring ecological well-being. These also include the Action Plan for the Implementation of the Concept of Cooperation of the Member States of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in the Field of Environmental Protection for the Period 2022-2024 [2], as well as the Joint Statement of the Council of Heads of the Member States of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization on Climate Change Response 2022 [3]. The aforementioned SCO documents serve as

a programmatic framework for improving the domestic administrative regulations of the member states, such as the Federal Law of the Russian Federation ‘On Environmental Protection’ [4], the Environmental Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan [5], and the Law of the People’s Republic of China ‘On Environmental Protection’ [6]. The administrative law of these countries thoroughly regulates the rules of rational natural resource management, establishing specific procedures for issuing integrated environmental permits, as well as defining the procedure for emission quota allocation of pollutants.

Within the system for ensuring the sustainable development of the SCO member states, administrative law functions as the operational mechanism through which the state will be implemented regarding the distribution and utilization of natural capital. A leading role in this is occupied by the permitting system, as well as the institution of licensing, which enable the state to exercise preventive oversight over all activities of economic entities. Administrative legal regulations governing the issuance of licenses for subsoil use, water use, and agro-industrial activities establish highly stringent frameworks for lawful conduct of entities, aimed at preventing the predatory exploitation of non-renewable resources.

It seems necessary to introduce new conceptual ideas that address the challenges of modernity, as well as the specific characteristics of the SCO region.

First and foremost among the innovative ideas is the direct transition from static paper licenses to digital natural resource use profiles based on blockchain technology and Earth remote sensing. This innovation will enable administrative oversight bodies to monitor extraction volumes in real time, including the monitoring of ecosystem conditions; consequently, it will be possible to automatically suspend permit operations in the event of exceeding established environmental load limits.

Secondly, considering the existence of common water basins, the development of unified administrative regulations within the SCO for managing transboundary resources is proposed. In this context, the establishment of joint monitoring groups vested with supranational authority to inspect water bodies is envisaged. Consequently, this innovation will convert administrative law from an instrument of national sovereignty directly into a mechanism for shared environmental security.

Thirdly, administrative norms must necessarily include mandatory conditions for reclamation, as well as for the restoration of biodiversity, within the text of licensing agreements. From this, it follows that the right to exploit a resource becomes inseparably connected with the administrative obligation to ensure its reproduction.

Effective administration in this specific area prevents the exploitation of resources beyond established norms and also encourages the adoption of so-called green technologies. The implementation of the principle of administrative responsibility for the ecological footprint in the practice of the SCO countries will enable the creation of a legal environment wherein the economic benefit derived from the

direct use of natural resources is balanced by the imperative of preserving ecological equilibrium for future generations.

A fundamental function of administrative law within the mechanism for ensuring the sustainable development of the SCO member states is the control and oversight activity ensuring compliance with mandatory environmental norms. Within the framework of implementing the provisions of the Concept of Cooperation among the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in the field of environmental protection [1], the national administrative-legal systems of the member countries vest specialized state bodies with an extensive range of powers to carry out continuous environmental monitoring. This constitutes a complex administrative procedure wherein the compliance of operators' activities with explicitly established standards of permissible impact on the biosphere is assessed.

It is important to note that administrative law establishes a legitimate basis for carrying out both planned and unplanned inspections, thereby creating a basis for the application of administrative enforcement measures. Through a system of progressively scaled fines and mechanisms for compensating environmental damage, administrative law compels enterprises to integrate specific environmental standards into their production policies. Such stringent administrative regulation within the framework of the SCO acts as a safeguard ensuring that economic growth is not pursued at the cost of irreversible degradation of the region's natural ecosystems.

Alongside this, the administrative law of the SCO countries functions as the direct regulator of public participation in the processes of adopting environmentally significant decisions. In accordance with contemporary principles of green administration, enshrined in national legislation, citizens and non-governmental organizations are granted subjective public rights to access verified information regarding the state of the environment. These administrative regulations define a clear procedure for providing such information, thereby limiting the potential for unjustified withholding of environmental data by governmental bodies.

Administrative law in the SCO countries has evolved from a tool of routine state supervision into an operative system for sustainable development. Administrative law institutions are precisely what ensure the practical viability of the region's green agenda. Moreover, the role of this branch of law constitutes a fundamental basis, as it translates the SCO's political declaration into mandatory governance procedures and mechanisms for legal accountability. To strengthen the ecological stability of the SCO member states, it is crucial to transition to a model of proactive administration, which involves the prevention and elimination of any violations, as well as the creation of legal incentives to implement resource-saving technologies. The improvement of national legislation should follow the path of digitalization of control functions, as well as simplification of administrative regulations for environmentally responsible enterprises. Nonetheless, the primary factor ensuring

the legitimacy of environmental policy remains the institution of civil society participation, which, through public oversight mechanisms and access to essential information, serves as a guarantor of transparency in government decisions.

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在全球化背景下，现代国家如何落实权力分立原则的问题
**THE PROBLEM OF IMPLEMENTING THE PRINCIPLE
OF SEPARATION OF POWERS IN A MODERN STATE IN
THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION**

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摘要：权力分立原则的实施问题自其诞生以来就一直是争论和辩论的焦点。然而，值得注意的是，如今建立一个完全符合所有既定理论标准、同时兼顾民主化和普遍平等基本原则的治理体系，其难度日益增加，其中一个最紧迫的原因在于，在全球化影响下，国家及其机构难以有效运作，甚至根本无法有效运作。

关键词：权力分立，全球化，议会共和制，总统权力，治理机制。

Abstract. *The problematic nature of implementing the principle of separation of powers has been a subject of disputes and debates throughout its entire existence. However, it should be noted that one of the most pressing reasons today for the increasing complexity of an already elusive possibility to establish a system of governance that fully meets all the prescribed theoretical criteria, as well as considering the essential standards of democratization and universal equality, is the problematic, or perhaps even the inability, of such a state and its institutions to function effectively within the framework of globalization's influence on the branches of government and their structure within one state.*

Keywords: *separation of powers, globalization, parliamentary republic, presidential power, governance mechanism.*

The fundamental and most effective method of organizing state power is a system established through the separation of powers into three branches: executive, legislative, and judicial, which, in theory, ensures the proper functioning of the entire governance mechanism. However, the ability to ensure the complete independence of each branch from the others generates uncertainty both in the context of local factors within a single state and under globalization conditions that influence established standards.

The principle of separation of powers, as noted by P. Yu. Ovsyannikov and T. Yu. Serdyukova, before taking on the form of a well-established and substantiated political concept, evolved from the tradition of formally limiting the power of the monarch — for example, the authority of God, the Church, or the law, to which the supreme ruler is obliged to submit [1, p. 86]. One of the formulations regarding the distribution of powers among branches of government was presented in the works of Aristotle, who identified components of the political order as follows: a legislative advisory body addressing state affairs, administrative bodies along with their associated public offices, and judicial bodies [2, pp. 514-515]. However, for the proper functioning of all branches of government, there must be a regulatory mechanism that prevents any single branch from occupying a dominant position within the system. Aristotle, in his concept, refers to a universal law to which all parts must conform, yet in exceptional circumstances, he permits an expansion of the ruler's authority if the law cannot be applied to resolve a particular issue, or if the ruler is capable of rendering a decision more just than that which the law would provide.

The English thinker and philosopher John Locke contributed to the development of the theory of separation of powers by defining it in his works as comprising three components: the executive, responsible for government administration and judicial functions; the legislative; and the federative, which handles the state's foreign policy. However, in Locke's concept, the triad featured a dominant element in the form of the legislative branch, which held exclusive authority to establish norms of conduct for society and, consequently, wielded undeniable power over civil institutions. At first glance, it may appear that Locke's interpretation does not highlight the essential principle of equality among the branches of power; however, it is at this stage in the theory's development that a mechanism emerges, later becoming the system of 'checks and balances.' In the aforementioned system, the executive branch exerts influence over the 'dominant' legislative branch through certain prerogatives, such as convening and dissolving the highest legislative authority.

The founder of the theory of separation of powers is generally recognized as the French philosopher and thinker Charles-Louis de Montesquieu, who formulated its 'classical' version. This differentiation was established by allocating specific powers to each branch: within legislative authority, the government and related institutions held the prerogative to enact, repeal, and amend laws; the executive branch was responsible

for conducting the state's foreign policy and defense; and the judiciary, identified by Montesquieu as an independent branch for the first time, functioned autonomously. It was also in his concept that the necessity of a bicameral legislative assembly was expressed. The executive branch belonged to the monarch, the head of state. Judicial powers were recommended to be entrusted to representatives of the people [3, p. 298]. It should be noted that Montesquieu described the principle of limiting powers, which is directly related to the development of the modern system of 'checks and balances' in states. The executive branch was vested with the authority to regulate the functioning and dissolution of the legislative assembly, as well as to exercise veto power over the decisions of the legislative body and repeal them. The legislative branch exercised control over the enforcement of norms and acts issued by the executive authority and the accountability of officials. In Montesquieu's conception, the judicial power constituted the third force responsible for ensuring compliance with the limits of the powers of the legislative and executive branches.

The system of checks and balances described in Montesquieu's works constitutes a fundamental component of the theory, as without it, it is impossible to develop a model of the three branches of power in which the judicial authority effectively emerges as an independent branch in practice, absent an external arbiter to prevent the expansion of powers and the dominance of any single branch of authority. Such an arbiter could have been the monarch, whose powers, according to Montesquieu's position, were intended to limit the branches of government that themselves require regulation 'from outside.' However, in republics where the head of state is elected, this aspect remains uncertain due to the possibility of challenging or annulling the 'arbiter's' decision. It should also be noted that the worldwide adoption of the principle of separation of powers resulted from the historical trend of transitioning from a monarchical state — historically inclined toward absolutism of power, and consequently despotism and rights violations — to a republican system, which in theory represents one of the most optimal forms of a social contract between the population and the supreme authority elected by it.

Within a single state, the implementation of the principle of separation of powers itself becomes a model for transformation in light of the traditions and mentality of the society being governed. The equality of all three branches of power remains unrealized in practice; therefore, under various circumstances, one of the three branches either assumes a dominant position or exercises undisputed sovereignty over the others. In states with a high degree of independence of the parliamentary branch, the judicial branch finds itself at a disadvantage, since the possibility of annulling unconstitutional decisions adopted by parliament is non-existent, which a priori deprives the judiciary of the role of arbiter in resolving disputes that might arise between the legislative and executive branches. However, when examining the institutional framework of parliamentary republics, it becomes evident that a conflict between the parliament and

the government is inherently impossible, since only the parliamentary composition is elected by direct vote, and this parliament in turn elects the executive body, thereby conferring legitimacy on the government through the exercise of direct democracy [4, p.102]. The unequivocal dominance of the parliamentary branch also becomes apparent when the government, chosen by parliamentarians, appoints its own candidates to the highest judicial offices, thereby negating the very advantage that the separation of powers system is supposed to provide. In the conditions described above, the role of a 'counterbalance' to the established synchronous system of subordination to the parliament can only be assumed by the opposition, thereby causing societal division and threatening state order.

A similar problem in applying the principle of separation of powers arises when, within a presidential republic, presidential authority merges with the executive branch, ensuring government dominance [5, p. 22]. In terms of personnel composition, as in the case of a parliamentary republic, the judiciary remains indirectly dependent on presidential authority, since the president makes the appointment of judges. Thus, it can be concluded that safeguarding the political and social order from despotism of the head of state and the dominance of one branch of power calls into question the possibility of establishing the arbiter as president — a model practiced, for example, in the USA — given the high level of sovereignty of presidential power, which belongs to the executive branch.

The aforementioned problems are directly linked to the transformation of the principle of separation of powers influenced by local factors in state formation, as exemplified by the United States, where the governance model was partly based on the competition between Congress and the Supreme Court. Over the course of this process, by the end of the 20th century, the Supreme Court had assumed a leading role, while the presidential power sought to exert control over the judicial and legislative branches [6, pp. 203-209].

It should be noted that in the course of globalization and the expansion of political trends, there has been a diffusion in the adoption of a particular form of republic, representing an example of the most optimal realization of the principle of separation of powers within this form of state. The so-called 'semi-presidential' republic, most commonly referred to in Russian state and legal scholarship as a 'mixed' republic, is described in the works of numerous scholars, including Cindy Skach, who emphasizes the potential for conflict between the president and the prime minister, who under certain circumstances possess equal extraordinary powers [7, p. 97].

Global trends influence not only the political characteristics of regions, leveling political traditions and bringing the principle of separation of powers in newly formed states under a unified, actively spreading standard. Economic flows and agreements between states have closely linked the external and internal political needs of society, creating a new management structure in the economic sector[8. pp. 15-16]. The

activities of economic institutions determine the possibilities for the distribution of domestically produced goods and for supplying the population with necessary goods and mass consumer goods from abroad, thereby shaping opportunities to mitigate or exacerbate social inequality in society. In cases of shortages of any group of goods, an artificial frenzy arises, which diminishes the welfare and economic potential of the middle and lower classes. Under the conditions of the new reality, the principle of separation of powers no longer serves as a tool to limit the power of the monarch but instead functions as a means of maintaining political order sustained by the state's external and internal economic linkages, which may contribute to the recognition of the complex of economic institutions as a distinct branch of power.

In conclusion, I would like to propose a hypothesis: observing the potential emergence of a new 'economic' branch of power, one can draw an analogy with J. Locke's concept of the separation of powers. According to Locke, there existed a federative branch of power responsible for the state's foreign affairs; it can be argued that the economic branch, upon its establishment in the near future, will be capable of assuming some of the 'external' functions previously held by the federative branch within this conceptual framework.

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白俄罗斯共和国刑事诉讼中的电子司法
**ELECTRONIC JUSTICE IN THE CRIMINAL PROCEDURE
OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS**

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摘要：本文对白俄罗斯共和国的电子司法概念进行了全面的理论和法律分析，指出了缺乏规范性法律法规的问题，并提出了完善电子司法体系的方向。

关键词：电子司法，司法，数字化，刑事诉讼，白俄罗斯共和国，信息技术

Abstract. *This article presents a comprehensive theoretical and legal analysis of the concept of electronic justice in the Republic of Belarus, identifies issues related to the lack of normative-legal regulation, and proposes directions for its enhancement.*

Keywords: *Electronic justice, justice, digitization, criminal procedure, Republic of Belarus, information and communication technologies*

Electronic justice is a concept based on the use of information technologies to optimize justice, increasing its accessibility and effectiveness. In the context of the development of the information society, this concept is becoming increasingly relevant, and the Republic of Belarus does not stand aside from these processes. In this regard, it is necessary to analyze the theoretical and legal aspects of defining electronic justice, as well as its place and role within the justice system of the Republic of Belarus. We divide the study of this issue into two directions: theoretical and legal.

The necessity of clarifying the concept of electronic justice from a theoretical standpoint arises from the fact that legal science has yet to develop a unified approach to defining the concept of 'electronic justice,' although the issues of practical implementation of electronic justice capabilities consistently attract the attention of scholars, researchers, and practitioners, and certain procedures have become routine in the operations of judicial bodies of the Republic of Belarus, as highlighted by D. G. Tsygankov [1, p. 519].

Moreover, the terms ‘informatization’ and ‘electronic justice’ are frequently conflated, which is not entirely correct. P. M. Morkhat posits that informatization entails the provision of law enforcement agencies and courts with innovative technologies, while electronic justice constitutes the process of their utilization [2, p. 87].

The differentiation of the aforementioned elements of the state’s information policy is essential for the accurate identification of legislative documents, the provisions of which are aimed at regulating the processes of their introduction into contemporary justice. It is necessary to emphasize that the informatization of society and the activities of government bodies commenced significantly earlier than the development of electronic justice, which also influences certain discrepancies in the normative legal acts governing these aspects of innovative policy. In legal scholarship, there is no unified definition of the concept of ‘electronic justice.’ The approaches of various authors to defining this term differ: some highlight its objective and transparency, while others focus on the process and mechanisms of its implementation.

E. V. Burdina defines electronic justice as an integral part of the electronic state, within which, considering the specifics of judicial protection, the aims, objectives, and principles of the electronic state are realized. It employs new methods, approaches, and forms of relationships and interactions with both external and internal system entities, including participants in judicial proceedings, based on the use of information and communication technologies [3, p. 42]. This definition provides a more detailed clarification of both the concept of electronic justice and the components that ensure its operation. On this basis, the following characteristics of electronic justice can be identified:

1) the use of information and communication technologies as the primary means for performing all procedural actions by both the court and the parties, as well as for executing measures that support the judicial process. The application of information and communication technologies is grounded in procedural normative legal acts;

2) aimed at achieving the principal goals and objectives set forth in the electronic government strategy, which includes enhancing the accessibility and efficiency of justice;

3) functions within the framework of judicial proceedings and, consequently, exists to effectively ensure the operation of the courts;

4) electronic justice actively interacts both with participants in judicial proceedings and within the judicial system itself;

5) is inextricably connected with electronic government and the information society. This is also indicated by E. A. Guryeva, who underscores that ‘electronic justice, as an advanced product of the informatization of the judicial system, at the current stage of its existence functions as an instrument for the development of the information society’ [4, p. 78].

Turning to the legal analysis of the definition of ‘electronic justice,’ it is important to note that a normative concept of this process is absent from the legislation of the Republic of Belarus. This is also highlighted by T. V. Voronovich: ‘neither the Constitution, nor the Code of the Republic of Belarus on the Judicial System and the Status of Judges, nor other legislative acts contain provisions that would define the concept of electronic justice, electronic judicial proceedings, or elucidate their content’ [5]. T. Z. Shalaeva highlights this legal gap, emphasizing that «the absence of legal norms regulating electronic justice effectively constitutes a restraining factor for its development in criminal proceedings» [6].

The lack of a definition can be explained by the fact that electronic justice is a rapidly evolving phenomenon. Nonetheless, G. N. Moskalevich notes that in the Republic of Belarus, the concept of «electronic government» has yet to receive legislative recognition at the normative level, despite it characterizing the information society and serving as the «foundation» for the existence of electronic justice [7, pp. 277-278]. The author also emphasizes the necessity of improving procedural legislation to favorably support the implementation of electronic justice [7, p. 280].

Based on these considerations, it can be concluded that, from a legal perspective, the issue of defining electronic justice in the information society requires refinement — for example, there is a need to enshrine the definition of ‘electronic justice.’

Electronic justice, like any form of procedural actions prescribed by law, must comply with normative legal principles, thereby rendering its application lawful and permissible. The conclusions are supported by the scholarly thought of O. V. Petrova, who emphasizes that ‘the implementation of electronic justice technologies should be understood within the framework of existing legislation, primarily as organizational and technical measures’ [8, p. 529]. From this perspective, it can be concluded that prioritizing compliance with the principles of criminal justice is imperative; consequently, examining their essence constitutes a necessary phase of the present study.

Thus, the concept of the principles of criminal justice is examined by various authors, but, in our view, the most comprehensive definition is offered by V. N. Bibilo — who understands the principles of criminal justice as a set of fundamental ideas, provisions, and directions of thought, enshrined at the legal level, characterizing the functioning of courts in conducting criminal procedural activities aimed at ultimately achieving the goals and objectives established for the state and criminal justice system [9, p. 79]. However, it is important to emphasize that the principles of criminal justice are among the fundamental institutions of the criminal procedure.

The main principles of criminal justice are those postulates enshrined in Articles 8 to 25 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Belarus dated 16 July 1999, No. 295-Z [10]. They are conventionally divided into two groups: constitutional and special principles. Constitutional principles establish the foundation of

all justice, including criminal justice, while special principles specify it by forming provisions characteristic of this branch of law [11, pp. 71-72].

The constitutional principles include the principles of: legality; publicity; equality of citizens before the law and equality in the protection of rights and lawful interests; presumption of innocence; ensuring the accused's right to defense; inviolability of the home and other lawful possessions of citizens; protection of private life, including the confidentiality of correspondence, telephone and other communications, honor, and dignity; the language in which judicial proceedings are conducted; the exercise of justice exclusively by the court; independence of judges and their subordination solely to the law; publicity of judicial proceedings; adversarial nature and equality of parties in the proceedings; protection of citizens' rights to judicial safeguards and other related rights.

The special principles include the comprehensiveness, completeness, and objectivity of the investigation of case circumstances; evaluation of evidence based on inner conviction; immediacy, orality, and continuity of judicial proceedings. Undoubtedly, all the aforementioned principles must be upheld within the framework of electronic justice.

Let us align certain principles with electronic justice. Undoubtedly, electronic justice must conform to the principle of legality, and, accordingly, its foundations must be established by law. The normative provision for electronic justice is characterized by completeness and variability — comprising both laws and subordinate normative legal acts. However, a legal gap has been identified due to the absence in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Belarus of the legal foundations regulating the use of information technologies in criminal proceedings.

O. V. Petrova justly observes that the sole provision allowing for the possibility of employing technical means in criminal proceedings is contained in part 3 of Article 192 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Belarus dated July 16, 1999, No. 295-Z [8, p. 530]. It is important to emphasize that this provision of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Belarus dated July 16, 1999, No. 295-Z governs the permissibility of utilizing innovative technologies during the preliminary investigation phase, which, as S. V. Boriko notes, constitutes the activity of preliminary investigation bodies in collecting, examining, and assessing evidence for subsequent judicial proceedings [12, p. 168]. Consequently, a proposal arises to amend the legislation by introducing a provision that would enshrine the principle of the admissibility of electronic justice within criminal proceedings, the substance of which would delineate the general rules for the application of innovative technologies in criminal procedural activities, thereby fully ensuring the legality of implementing electronic justice.

A fundamental principle that must be guaranteed in electronic justice is the protection of privacy, including the confidentiality of correspondence, telephone and

other communications, as well as the protection of honor and dignity. Confidentiality is a priority area that is given due consideration by legislators: provisions have been established to protect information from unfair copying, and liability measures have been introduced for violations of information security requirements.

The equality of citizens before the law is associated with electronic justice through the provision of equal access for all participants in criminal justice to the components of this method of implementing the criminal procedure. The observance of the principle of equality of citizens in electronic justice was also discussed at the round table of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Belarus, where it was emphasized that ‘the transition to the digitization of justice is possible only when all stakeholders are prepared — including judges, legal professionals as a whole, and citizens alike’ [13]. This indicates the necessity to develop free and accessible platforms and interfaces for all citizens that address the needs of various categories of the population.

The principle of judicial independence and subordination solely to the law within the context of electronic justice implies that, despite the optimizing attributes of electronic justice and the overall simplification of criminal procedural proceedings it facilitates, innovative technologies must not in any way compromise the impartiality of judicial decisions. This implies the exclusion of the possibility of substituting a judge with artificial intelligence or employing it as a means of rendering decisions. As noted by R. V. Kozorezova, only three potential levels of artificial intelligence application in judicial proceedings are distinguished: facilitation of technical operations; evaluation of evidence; and case adjudication. Nevertheless, R. V. Kozorezova emphasizes that the final decision is invariably made by the judge to uphold the principle of judicial independence [14].

To align the principle of publicity with electronic justice, its essence will be elucidated. Thus, publicity is understood as the access to the process and outcomes of judicial proceedings by both participants in the criminal process and citizens of the Republic of Belarus through the provision of the right to review final judicial rulings, which are publicly disclosed by means of their oral pronouncement in the courtroom and subsequent publication [15, p. 26]. The implementation of the principle of publicity in electronic justice is ensured through the publication of court decisions which have entered into legal force via information and legal systems, which constitute an element of electronic justice.

The principle of adversarial process and equality of the parties in judicial proceedings may be realized through the use of electronic means of evidence, thereby providing equal opportunities for parties to defend their protected rights. T. Z. Shalaeva identifies the problem of the absence of a legally established procedure for applying the fundamental provisions of the procedural institute of evidence to electronic means of evidence [6, p. 78]. This assertion further substantiates the

necessity for normative legal regulation of these criteria within the framework of the principle of the admissibility of judicial digitalization.

In conclusion, the special principles of the criminal procedure shall be compared with electronic justice. Accordingly, comprehensiveness, completeness, and objectivity in investigating the circumstances of a case can be fully ensured through elements of electronic justice. This is explained by the fact that artificial intelligence is specifically tailored to data analysis, including the requirement to generate conclusions. However, the neural network may hinder the judge's evaluation of evidence based on inner conviction, as the judge could rely on an opinion obtained from artificial intelligence, which, in turn, distorts their objective perspective on the evidence under analysis.

Orality and continuity of the judicial proceeding are ensured by the video conferencing system, as well as by the audio and video recording system of court sessions, which constitute elements of the digitalization of judicial activity and are closely interconnected with the aforementioned principle. This principle presupposes the oral form of judicial proceedings, during which the court hears the parties and announces the content of documents contained in the case file. The use of a video-conferencing system does not violate the principle of orality of the court hearing, since all participants in the proceedings orally provide explanations and testify before the court during its application. Therefore, electronic justice must comply with the established principles to ensure the rule of law in the criminal procedure. The integration of general legal and special principles is necessary; however, the current legislation contains normative-legal gaps that require amendments. It is recommended to introduce a provision into the legislation regarding the admissibility of electronic justice, which will enable the lawful application of innovative technologies in the criminal procedure.

Thus, as a result of the analysis of electronic justice in the criminal procedure of the Republic of Belarus, it can be concluded that the most appropriate course of action is to codify this definition within the framework of the resolution of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Belarus "On the Concept of Judicial and Legal Reform," since it is precisely through this normative legal act that the improvements introduced into the Belarusian judicial system are regulated.

At present, the Republic of Belarus is witnessing active, albeit sporadic, development of legislation in the field of informatization of judicial authority. First and foremost, it is necessary to recognize the absence of a theoretically substantiated system of legal regulation of electronic justice, which creates challenges for law enforcement and judicial practice in achieving a consistent and unified judicial process. A significant issue concerns the identification, in a broad sense, of the subject-object composition of legal relations within the 'electronic justice' system. New legal categories require thorough development, such as the electronic legal

status and the electronic legal regime of elements within the structure of legal relations in the area of administering justice based on information technologies.

It is proposed to amend the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Belarus by adding a provision that would establish the principle of the admissibility of electronic justice in the criminal process, specifically Article 251 ‘Admissibility of the Digitization of Justice,’ the content of which would define the general rules for the application of innovative technologies in criminal procedural activities.

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关于在情绪状态下实施的谋杀罪的定性问题
**QUESTIONS OF QUALIFICATION OF MURDER COMMITTED
IN A STATE OF AFFECT**

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摘要：本文探讨的问题具有重要意义，因为目前初步侦查机关面临着激情犯罪定性错误以及此类犯罪侦查难度大的问题。本文分析了激情犯罪定性的特征及其构成要件，并探讨了犯罪行为的意图、动机和目的，指出正确、清晰地识别犯罪动机对于正确定性犯罪行为至关重要。本文还提出了此类犯罪侦查的复杂性问题，因为在相关机构的介入下，无论是在初步侦查阶段还是在审判阶段，都极易出现错误。此类错误的代价是侵犯人的自由，即不可剥夺的宪法保障权利。本文对国内刑法进行了详细分析，并提出了改进建议，以防止激情杀人等犯罪定性错误。

关键词：情感、犯罪构成要件、谋杀、刑法、精神状态、动机、目的、意图

Abstract. *The problem discussed in this article is quite relevant, since currently the preliminary investigation authorities have a problem of incorrect classification of crimes committed in a state of passion, as well as the complexity of their investigation. The individual features of the qualification of this crime and the mandatory elements of its composition are considered. The nature and nature of the intent, motive, and purpose of criminal behavior is analyzed, which is why a correct and clear identification of affect is necessary for the correct qualification of the committed act. The question is raised about the complexity of investigating this type of crime, since in the presence of related structures there is a high probability of error both at the stage of the preliminary investigation and during the trial. The price of such a mistake is human freedom, his inalienable constitutional*

guaranteed right. A detailed analysis of domestic criminal legislation is carried out, recommendations are given for its improvement, in order to prevent errors in the classification of crimes, namely murders committed in a state of passion.

Keywords: *affect, corpus delicti, murder, criminal law, sanity, motive, purpose, intent*

In modern society, combating crime takes a leading role. Crime negatively impacts society, as individuals begin to fear for their lives, health, and property. To effectively combat crime, it is essential to identify the causes and conditions under which crimes are committed, as well as to conduct more detailed theoretical studies on the accuracy of legal qualification of offenses.

The Criminal Code of the Russian Federation contains a number of offenses whose elements overlap with those of other crimes. One such offense is murder committed in a state of affect, as provided for in Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation¹.

Affect is a specific psychological process occurring at the emotional level of an individual, enabling rapid and impulsive actions, sometimes without conscious awareness of one's behavior.

Scholars identify two types of affect:

1) Pathological affect is a short-term, high-intensity experience that produces such a state in which the awareness of one's actions is completely absent, and a person commits actions against their will, that is, they act in a state of insanity.

2) Physiological affect is a psycho-emotional state of an individual in which sanity is preserved, but the awareness of one's actions is limited. This article will examine cases of the qualification of crimes specifically committed under this affect. [2, p. 42]

Currently, crimes committed in a state of affect are among the least frequent in overall crime statistics. This fact further underscores the importance of a more detailed theoretical examination of these crimes, given the near absence of practical experience in their qualification and investigation.

It is necessary to examine the corpus delicti of murder committed in a state of affect.

Murder committed in a state of affect is a privileged category of murder under Art. 105 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation. Accordingly, the immediate object affected by this crime is human life.

The objective side of the crime as defined in Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation is characterized by three essential elements:

¹ Criminal Code of the Russian Federation dated 13.06.1996 No. 63-FZ (as amended on 20.02.2026) [Electronic resource]. Electronic resource data. — Access mode https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_10699/ (date accessed: 07.04.2026).

Figure 1 — Crime Statistics Diagram

- 1) a socially dangerous act in the form of an act consisting in the deprivation of human life;
- 2) socially dangerous consequences in the form of the death of a person;
- 3) the causal link between the specified act and its consequences. Only upon proving this element can the presence of elements of murder be asserted.

The subject of this article is any person who has reached the age of criminal responsibility, specifically 16 years old, according to Article 20 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation¹.

The subjective side is characterized by the form of guilt in the form of intent, both direct intent — when the person was aware of the public danger of their actions, foresaw the possibility or inevitability of socially dangerous consequences and desired their occurrence — and indirect intent — when the person was aware of the public danger of their actions, foresaw the possibility of socially dangerous consequences, did not desire them but consciously tolerated these consequences or was indifferent to them².

When qualifying a crime under Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, it is also important to take into account the fact that intent arises suddenly, under the influence of certain factors that negatively affect the psyche.

In addition to the aforementioned fact, it is essential to consider that affect arises as a result of the victim's improper conduct, which serves as a responsive reaction to such actions.

¹ Criminal Code of the Russian Federation dated 13.06.1996 No. 63-FZ (as amended on 20.02.2026) [Electronic resource]. Electronic resource data.— Access mode https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_10699/ (date accessed: 07.04.2026).

² Comments on Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation [Electronic resource]. Electronic resource — Access mode <https://ukodeksrf.ru/ch-2/rzd-7/gl-16/st-107-uk-rf> (accessed: 07.04.2026).

With a thorough evaluation of all conditions pertaining to both the objective and subjective aspects, the probability of correctly qualifying the crime specifically as murder committed in a state of affect increases.

Having examined the criminal-legal characterization of murder committed in a state of affect, it is necessary to consider the issues related to the proper legal classification of this crime, as well as to propose ways to improve the theoretical study that aids in the correct qualification of conduct under Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation.

As noted above, this crime is committed very rarely, and reliance on practical experience is impossible due to its absence. Besides the rarity of this crime, it should also be noted that proving the state of affect is quite challenging.

In regard to physiological affect, this state arises in an individual suddenly and also terminates suddenly; therefore, it cannot be unequivocally asserted that it existed at the moment the crime was committed.

It is also important to consider the fact that an immoral action by the victim constitutes an essential condition.

Affect constitutes a mitigating circumstance, whereby the suspect (accused), together with their defense counsel, may insist that the murder was committed precisely in a state of affect, since, firstly, the term of punishment in the form of imprisonment for the specified crime is less than for the crime provided by Art. 105 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, and secondly, in the absence of witnesses to the specified crime, the investigator only has testimony from one side, since the victim cannot provide testimony for obvious reasons¹.

This fact creates difficulties in the investigation of the crime stipulated by Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, and the investigator must thoroughly examine all details of the crime.

To establish the presence of affect in the individual at the time of the crime, a comprehensive psychological and psychiatric examination is ordered. The legislation does not define the required number of such expert examinations; however, in our view, it is necessary to establish by law that at least two such examinations must be conducted. Moreover, it should be stipulated that each examination is to be performed by different experts in order to ensure the most accurate assessment of the suspect's (accused's) mental state at the time the crime was committed.

¹ Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated 27.01.1999 No. 1 (as amended on 03.03.2015) 'On Judicial Practice in Cases of Murder (Art. 105 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation)' [Electronic resource]. Electronic resource — Access mode https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_21893/ (accessed: 07.04.2026).

Considering the lack of sufficient practical experience for the correct legal qualification of the act, and consequently the minimal judicial practice on this matter, it is advisable to develop at the theoretical level a detailed guideline in the form of recommendations for the qualification and investigation of murders committed in a state of affect.

In our view, it is necessary to define the concept of affect more precisely at the theoretical level, so that it cannot be interpreted in various ways; this will significantly simplify determining whether a state of affect is present in a given case, since currently, even in existing judicial practice, there is no unanimous opinion on this definition.

As noted above, it is also essential to develop guidelines for the correct legal qualification of these crimes, thereby providing investigators with a clear sequence of actions, ensuring that crimes stipulated by other articles of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation are not qualified under Art. 107 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, and vice versa.

Thus, currently, within the theory of proper crime qualification, there exist gaps that require resolution through the development and enhancement of theoretical studies in the area of classification of murders committed in a state of affect.

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医科大学新生眼中的“理想医生”形象
**THE MODEL OF THE “IDEAL DOCTOR” IN THE VIEWS
OF FRESHMEN AT MEDICAL UNIVERSITY**

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摘要：本文探讨了罗斯特医科大学一年级学生心目中“理想医生”形象及其构成要素的社会学研究结果。

关键词：健康，形象，医生，职业精神，依从性

Abstract: *The article examines the results of a sociological study on the model of the “ideal doctor” in the ideas of first-year students of RostGMU, and its constituent qualities.*

Keywords: *health, model, doctor, professionalism, compliance*

Population health is one of the country’s strategic priorities [1]. According to polls by the VTsIOM Analytical Center, health is a priority value for 58% of Russians [2] and they strive to maintain it. But assessments of the modern health care system, which plays a significant role in the process of maintaining health, are mixed. 52% of citizens who took part in the survey critically assess the work of the health care system, 42% are rather satisfied, another 6% found it difficult to answer. Among the respondents who negatively assess the quality of medical care, 83% indicate a shortage of personnel and insufficient qualifications of doctors [3].

The key figure in the process of health preservation and treatment is a doctor, and the success of this process depends primarily on the level of his knowledge, skills and abilities. The profession of “doctor” is multifaceted and complex, it involves multi-stage doctor-patient interactions: prevention, diagnosis, treatment, recovery. And each stage assumes that the doctor has special knowledge and skills that contribute to maintaining and maintaining health. To become ideal, a doctor must have a combination of characteristics, qualities that make up the “ideal doctor model.” The ideal doctor model is a construct that includes a complex of various

characteristics, high professional standards and social expectations, reflecting ideas about the ideal of the profession “doctor.”

Probably, the formal basis for determining the components of the ideal model of a doctor can be the Ethical Code of a Russian doctor adopted by the Association of Doctors of Russia in 2022 [4], which includes 5 sections fixing: the main goal of the doctor’s professional activity (preservation of the patient’s life and improvement of its quality with the use of emergency, planned and preventive medical care), requirements for professional competence, observance of the patient’s rights and the rules of interaction “doctor-patient,” “doctor-colleague,” “doctor-medical personnel,” determining the limits of the Ethical Code, the procedure for its revision and responsibility for its violations.

The results of previous studies show that the models of the ideal doctor are somewhat different in the minds of doctors and patients. So, in the ideas of doctors, the model of an ideal doctor includes the following qualities: education, goodwill, experience, intelligence, attentiveness, sensitivity, responsibility, reading [5, S.47]

Patients, making their model of the ideal doctor, identified: adequacy, accuracy, attentiveness/interest, kindness, caring, experience, selflessness, disinterestedness, politeness, tact, reliability, deservedness [5, p.48], the ability to establish emotional contact, trust on the part of the patient [6]. In the description of the appearance of the “ideal doctor” for the majority of patients surveyed, the doctor should look neat, gender does not matter, and the desired age of the doctor is 30-40 years [6].

The purpose of this study is to identify the qualities that form the “ideal doctor” model in the ideas of freshmen at a medical university.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted in 2 phases (February 2025 — April 2025). 1st — study and analysis of scientific sources on this topic, 2nd — empirical study and analysis of the data obtained. In the formation of the sample population, the method of typical representatives was applied. Inclusion criterion — first-year students of Rostov State Medical University, the sample population — 130 respondents (n = 130). The main research method — online questionnaire and analysis of the obtained data, the main tool — a questionnaire compiled in accordance with the principle of validity, included three blocks of closed-type questions: 1. Professional qualities; 2. ability to interact with the patient; 3. External parameters. Systematization and assessment of the reliability of the obtained data was carried out using the MS Excel program and manually.

Compiling a model of an ideal doctor according to the given parameters that determine the necessary professional qualities, attitude to their profession and experience, 38.3% of respondents, the dominant component of the model of an ideal doctor, called a high level of professionalism, i.e. a combination of a strong broad base of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. 61.1% of respondents are sure that the “ideal doctor” should sacrifice his free time to save the patient, and

this is the essence of the profession. 64% of the surveyed freshmen consider the fulfillment of medical duty outside their working hours and outside the walls of a medical institution to be the responsibility of a doctor, since a “doctor” is not just a profession, but a way of life. More than half of the respondents — 62%, noted that the work experience of a doctor is important for the ideal model of a doctor, and 64% of the survey participants believe that the experience should be at least 6 years.

Identifying the skills necessary for the “ideal doctor” to successfully interact, allowing to establish contact with the patient and ensure a high level of compliance [7.8] contributing to the achievement of positive treatment results, a significant majority of respondents — 84.8% are sure that — the doctor is obliged to show patience, respect and empathy to the patient, the doctor is obliged to comply with the rules of medical ethics, to be polite and under no circumstances, has the right to show rudeness and rude behavior is unacceptable. Choosing the most suitable doctor-patient interaction model for the ideal from the five proposed: paternalistic, engineering, partner, contract [9] and individual (hybrid), combining elements of the 4 named models, 64% of the surveyed freshmen chose as suitable, individually built (hybrid) for a specific patient model of interaction “doctor-patient.”

Describing external parameters characteristic of the “ideal doctor” model, 80.1% of survey participants indicated that the gender of the doctor does not matter. 84% of students believe that the age of the doctor does not play an important role in the model of the ideal doctor. 75.8% of the surveyed freshmen, as important characteristics in the appearance of a doctor, noted tidiness and accuracy.

So, having studied the data obtained, we can conclude that the freshmen of the medical university participating in the study, relying on their own subjective ideas about their future profession and creating a model of the “ideal doctor” included the following qualities in it: high level of professionalism (theory, practical skills and abilities, responsibility), work experience of at least 6 years, the ability to sacrifice your free time to save the patient, identification of the profession as a lifestyle, responsiveness, patience, respect, empathy and ethics, the ability to establish medical contact with the patient and the ability to build an individual model of interaction “doctor-patient,” tidiness and accuracy, gender and age does not matter.

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军事院校管理模式的转型是应对社会日益军事化的一种方式
**TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT MODELS IN MILITARY
UNIVERSITIES AS A RESPONSE TO THE INCREASING
MILITARIZATION OF SOCIETY**

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摘要：本文探讨了社会军事化进程影响下军事高等院校管理模式转型的问题。研究旨在识别和分析学员管理培训的主要变革方向，并将军事化视为一种复杂的社会心理现象。本研究的理论和方法论基础包括社会认同、军事职业社会化、制度同构以及军事化分析的社会心理学方法。通过对理论和实证资料的分析，作者论证了一种新的管理模式——“情境专制者”——的出现，该模式融合了威权领导的要素和情境适应性。研究表明，军事院校的管理转型具有双重性质：在既定目标层面，现代领导实践得以实施；而在实际互动层面，威权控制机制却得到强化。本文采取了富有远见的视角，呼吁科学界对所提出的问题进行更深入的实证研究。

关键词：社会军事化、管理文化、军事院校、社会心理因素、学员、领导力、威权式管理风格、军事社会化、社会认同。

Abstract. *This article addresses the problem of transforming management models in military higher education institutions under the influence of societal militarization processes. The purpose of the study is to identify and analyze the principal directions of change in the management training of cadets, considering militarization as a complex socio-psychological phenomenon. The theoretical and methodological foundation of the study is formed by the concepts of social identity, military-professional socialization, institutional isomorphism, and the socio-psychological approach to the analysis of militarization. Drawing on the analysis*

of theoretical and empirical sources, the author argues for the emergence of a new managerial model — the ‘situational autocrat’ — which integrates elements of authoritarian leadership with situational adaptability. It is shown that management transformations in military universities have a dual nature: at the level of declared objectives, modern leadership practices are implemented, whereas at the level of actual interactions, authoritarian control mechanisms are reinforced. The article adopts a visionary approach, inviting the scientific community to further empirical investigation of the designated problematics.

Keywords: *militarization of society, management culture, military universities, socio-psychological aspects, cadets, leadership, authoritarian management style, military socialization, social identity.*

Introduction

In the current context of increasing geopolitical tension and the transformation of the nature of armed conflicts, the processes of societal militarization are acquiring new dimensions that call for a systematic scientific analysis. As S. A. Vorozheykin observes, ‘the existential threats confronting Russian society inevitably intensify its militarization processes, which renders the analysis of the cultural-historical foundations and socio-psychological conditions underlying the emergence and development of this phenomenon especially pertinent.’ In this context, particular interest is focused on how the militarization of societal consciousness and social practices transforms the institutions responsible for military personnel training, particularly the management models developed within them.

Scholars rightly highlight the need to study militarization in two principal dimensions: as the militarization of society overall and as the military socialization of the individual, which regards militarized practices as preferable. This approach enables the linkage of macrosocial processes with microsocial interactions occurring within military educational institutions. Particular attention deserves the manner in which the increasing militarization of the social sphere — including its digital and informational dimensions — transforms conceptions of the appropriate model of governance within the military environment.

Simultaneously, as emphasized in the study by M. S. Obraztsov and S. R. Karapetyan, the necessity to institutionalize the modern paradigm of military education ‘is determined by the changing nature of armed conflict in the context of a special military operation, the sharp increase in the role of high technologies, as well as evolving requirements concerning the technological and engineering competencies of a wide range of military specialists’ [1]. This signifies that military universities confront a dual challenge: on one hand, they are required to prepare leaders capable of operating in a high-technology and rapidly evolving environment; on the other hand, the strengthening of militarization trends in

society creates a demand for the preservation and even intensification of authoritarian management practices.

The objective of this study, grounded in the integration of management sociology and social psychology approaches, is to analyze how the escalating processes of societal militarization transform the management models cultivated among cadets in military universities, and to identify the resulting socio-psychological consequences. The article is visionary in nature, proposing hypothetical constructs and avenues for further empirical research.

Militarization of society as an object of socio-psychological and managerial analysis

Within the scope of this study, militarization is understood as a complex, multifaceted process involving changes in mass consciousness, social representations, value orientations, and everyday interaction practices. As argued in works devoted to this issue, militarization should be analyzed ‘as a regular process shaped by objective political, economic, and social factors, as well as by subjective social perceptions and individual attitudes towards militarized practices’ [2]. This approach allows overcoming the reduction of militarization exclusively to institutional changes, while taking into account its psychological dimension.

The sociology of management contributes to this analysis by introducing the dimension of organizational transformations. Within the context of militarization, the management systems of military universities function simultaneously as both objects of external pressure and agents of reproduction of militarization patterns. As researchers observe, the trend toward democratization of cadet life and civil-military rapprochement, which emerged during the post-Soviet period, has decelerated in recent years, a development that can be interpreted as one of the indicators of the strengthening militarization processes within the military education system [3].

The category of «management culture» as applied to cadets of military universities necessitates special consideration. In the most general terms, a cadet’s management culture is understood as an integrative personality quality encompassing a system of managerial knowledge, skills, competencies, value orientations, and psychological attitudes required for the effective leadership of a military unit [4].

As studies indicate, interactive teaching methods are increasingly employed in the development of cadets’ management culture, including the method of social assignments and the method of solving educational managerial tasks [5]. This indicates a search for new pedagogical forms that transcend the traditional command-administrative model. Simultaneously, the development of the management culture of commanders of cadet units involves distinguishing several levels — from elementary to creative — and establishing specific pedagogical conditions for progression between them [6].

It is important to emphasize that management culture is shaped not only through deliberate training but also through the daily observation of commanders' actions and the assimilation of informal norms and values within the military environment. As noted by authors investigating leadership in cadet evaluations, «during training at a military institute, leadership constitutes an actual outcome of the educational process of cadets. It represents their ultimate objective, enabling cadets to meet the contemporary demands of their future positions while taking into account the specificities of the military collective» [7].

The socio-psychological approach to examining managerial training in cadets inevitably addresses the concepts of identity and socialization. The process of professional socialization at a military university involves not only the acquisition of knowledge and skills but also a profound transformation of the individual, resulting in the formation of a new military-professional identity [8].

The research by R. M. Shamionov and A. I. Sorokin reveals that the 'categories of identity and characteristics of perceptions of the world' are closely interconnected during cadet socialization, reflecting 'the complex process of personality development of a military specialist — a future officer' [9]. In other words, changes in representations of the world, including the perception of external threats and permissible management methods, are inextricably linked with the transformation of cadet self-identity.

Of particular interest in the context of militarization is the question of how external militarization processes affect the content of military-professional identity. It can be assumed that the higher the level of militarization of public consciousness, the more rigid and closed the identity matrices of cadets become, which, in turn, is reflected in their leadership preferences.

The key dilemma of managerial training in military universities concerns the relationship between leadership and authoritarianism. On the one hand, contemporary military science and practice recognize the necessity of developing leadership qualities in officers. As highlighted in the work of L. A. Olesik, the analysis of perspectives from foreign and domestic psychologists substantiates the necessity of developing officers' leadership qualities and leadership levels among servicemen for the conduct of combat operations [10].

Conversely, the authoritarian management style is traditionally deeply rooted in military culture. Studies indicate that the 'authoritarian management style involves the realization of a paradoxical situation: on the one hand, service members are deprived of initiative and autonomy in decision-making and execution, while on the other hand, their activities are inadequately coordinated and supervised.' This creates a risk of distortion in managerial activities, whereby formal authoritarian procedures are not accompanied by genuine responsibility and coordination.

In the context of militarization, the question arises: which management styles gain increased relevance? It can be hypothetically posited that the growth of militarization leads to the restoration of authoritarian practices; however, due to the growing complexity of tasks, there emerges a need to combine these with elements of situational leadership.

Analysis of the Transformation of Management Models

To understand how militarization influences management models in military universities, it is essential to examine the key stages of the transformation of the military professional education system in post-Soviet Russia. As noted in their works by E. N. Karlova and A. Yu. Grigorov, military education selectively adapts the developmental trends of the Russian educational system in consideration of the needs and traditions of the Armed Forces [11].

The authors emphasize the key direction of reform as the ‘establishment of a system of continuous, multilevel education based on large educational and scientific centers.’ However, it is noted that the trend toward democratization of cadet life and civil-military rapprochement, characteristic of the early post-Soviet period, subsequently decelerated. This fact can be interpreted as one of the manifestations of militarization: as external threats increase and rhetoric becomes more stringent, military education is reverting to more traditional, authoritarian-oriented management models [2].

The analysis of contemporary trends suggests that a new management model is forming in military universities, which can be characterized as hybrid. Its essence lies in the combination of elements of authoritarian leadership (unitary command, strict subordination, command hierarchy) with elements of situational leadership (delegation, consideration of the individual characteristics of subordinates, and the application of psychological methods of motivation).

Notably, the introduction of “flexible” elements takes place within the broader context of militarization. Accordingly, the Ministry of Defense mandates the training of military personnel in lean management principles to optimize routine operations and reduce internal costs. This appears to be a purely managerial innovation aimed at enhancing efficiency; however, it is implemented in a context where the overarching logic of military organization remains authoritarian. A paradoxical situation emerges: militarization stimulates the implementation of ‘soft’ management techniques, yet these are applied within a rigid institutional framework.

This conclusion is indirectly supported by analyses of the institutionalization of the contemporary military education paradigm, wherein the authors highlight ‘structural disproportions in staff composition (aging of the faculty, mental disengagement from “digital practices”).’ Management innovations are introduced in an environment where a significant portion of instructors and commanders remain oriented towards traditional authoritarian models, generating internal tension.

Socio-psychological mechanisms of transformation

At the socio-psychological level, the transformation of management models is mediated by several mechanisms. First, the social learning mechanism plays a role: cadets assimilate management patterns not only through targeted instruction but also by observing the actions of senior commanders. If the latter demonstrate contradictory styles (for example, proclaiming a leadership approach while in practice resorting to authoritarian methods), cadets develop an inclination towards double standards in management.

Secondly, the mechanism of identification is a significant factor. As studies demonstrate, the formation of cadets' military-professional identity is linked to the restructuring of their perceptions of the world and of themselves. Under conditions of militarization, these perceptions become increasingly polarized (the image of 'us versus them,' the perception of the world as an arena of conflicts), which, in turn, enhances the propensity to employ authoritarian management methods.

Thirdly, the mechanism of institutional pressure operates. According to the theory of institutional isomorphism, organizations operating within the same field, under pressure from the external environment (including regulatory, normative, and cognitive factors), begin to emulate each other's management practices. Under conditions of militarization, military universities experience pressure both from state institutions (requirements for accelerated training, reinforcement of the military-patriotic element) and from public opinion (growing support for a 'strong hand' approach). In response, they standardize their management models by focusing on the most 'successful' examples.

The conducted analysis enables the formulation of a central paradox. The militarization of society, accompanied by the growing complexity of military tasks, creates a demand for officers possessing not only authoritarian but also flexible management competencies. However, the same militarization — through mechanisms of social identification, institutional pressure, and cultural transmission — reinforces authoritarian attitudes and practices.

As a result, a model can be called the 'situational autocrat.' Its bearer externally demonstrates elements of leadership behavior (willingness to engage in dialogue, delegation, psychological support of subordinates); however, in critical situations — or at the slightest weakening of external oversight — resorts to rigidly authoritarian methods. This model, on the one hand, enables conformity with the requirements of contemporary managerial rhetoric, while on the other hand, it preserves deeply rooted authoritarian patterns.

It is essential to emphasize that such a model entails risks. As demonstrated by the classic studies of K. Lewin, R. Lippitt, and R. White, the authoritarian leadership style reinforces aggressive tendencies in the interactions among group members [12]. Within the context of a military university, this can manifest as increased

tension between cadets and commanders, diminished psychological safety, and formalization of relationships at the expense of genuine cohesion.

Generalizations and Conclusions

The theoretical analysis conducted enables the formulation of several conclusions that warrant further empirical validation.

1. The level of militarization of public consciousness is likely to positively correlate with the preference for authoritarian management styles among cadets of military universities. This implies that the higher the perceived level of external threats and the more intense the militarization rhetoric, the more stringent management methods cadets tend to consider acceptable.

2. It appears that during the course of study at a military university, cadets' leadership preferences transform from more democratic in the initial years to more authoritarian in the later years. Moreover, the intensity of this transformation increases during periods of heightened militarization.

3. There should exist a significant correlation between the military-professional identity of cadets and their managerial attitudes: the stronger the identification with the 'military' self-image, the greater the readiness to use authoritarian methods of management.

Conclusion

The present article undertakes to integrate approaches from the sociology of management and social psychology to analyze the transformation of management models in military universities under the influence of the processes of militarization of society and to identify prospects for further research.

Theoretical analysis permits the following conclusions.

1. The militarization of society constitutes a complex, multifaceted phenomenon that affects both institutional and socio-psychological levels. Its impact on management training in military universities is mediated by mechanisms of social learning, identification, and institutional pressure.

2. In response to the increasing militarization within military universities, a hybrid management model is emerging that combines elements of authoritarian leadership with situational flexibility. At the declarative level, leadership and "lean" practices are implemented, whereas at the level of real interactions, authoritarian control mechanisms persist and even intensify.

4. The proposed theoretical framework and drawn conclusions open up prospects for further empirical research, which will not only allow verification of the findings but also the development of recommendations for optimizing management training in military universities in light of militarization trends.

The article calls upon the academic community to engage in comprehensive discussions on how macrosocial processes of militarization transform microsocial interactions within the military education system, and on the social and psychological

consequences of these transformations for the personality of the future officer and for society as a whole.

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乌克兰后苏联时期遗产对统一领土学生生活策略的影响
**THE INFLUENCE OF UKRAINE'S POST-SOVIET HERITAGE
THE LIFE STRATEGIES OF THE STUDENTS
OF THE REUNITED TERRITORIES**

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摘要：本文旨在研究乌克兰后苏联时代的遗产对统一后地区青年学生生活策略发展的影响。研究考察了这一遗产的主要特征和表现形式，包括在乌克兰独立以及随后统一地区融入俄罗斯势力范围的背景下形成的政治、社会、经济、文化和历史等方面。文章引用了国内外学者关于研究和理解生活规划与策略重要性的研究成果。

本研究使用了截至2022年1月1日乌克兰、顿涅茨克人民共和国、卢甘斯克人民共和国以及扎波罗热州和赫尔松州在与俄罗斯重新统一前13至21岁男女人口的统计数据。

Abstract. *This scientific article is aimed at studying the influence of Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy on the development of life strategies among student youth in the reunited territories. The study considers the main characteristics and manifestations of this legacy, including political, social, economic, cultural, and historical aspects that were formed under the conditions of Ukraine's independence and the subsequent integration of the reunited territories into the Russian sphere. The article references domestic and foreign scholars who have explored the importance of studying and understanding life plans and strategies.*

This study presents Ukrainian statistical data on the male and female populations of Ukraine, the Donetsk and Lugansk People's Republics, as well as the Zaporizhzhia and Kherson regions prior to reunification with Russia, aged 13 to 21 as of January 1, 2022.

The expression of dual identity among youth is analyzed, as they face the necessity to adapt to new socio-political changes and to reconsider their traditional values. The consequences of Ukrainization and its impact on language policy are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the influence of Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy on the formation of identity and value orientations among youth.

This academic study highlights the importance of understanding the influence of Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy on the life strategies of student youth in the reunited territories for the development of effective educational programs, social adaptation programs, and youth initiatives aimed at supporting student youth in their adaptation to socio-political changes.

Keywords: *post-Soviet legacy, Ukraine, reunited territories, student youth, life strategies, youth socialization, value orientations.*

Research on life plans and strategies continues to evolve, integrating approaches from various scientific disciplines — sociology, psychology, anthropology, and others.

The study of life plans and strategies has become a topic of investigation among both domestic and international scholars in sociology and psychology. Scientific works and research by scholars such as K. A. Abulchanova-Slavskaya, Yu. M. Reznik and T. E. Reznik, E. I. Golovakha, Alfred Adler, J. Klausen and G. Elder and others established the foundations for understanding how a person organizes their life, sets goals, and adapts to social conditions.

For a person, strategy is a set of methods and efforts directed towards transitioning from the current state to the desired future. It includes the subjective vision of personal goals and the stages of their attainment, as well as the identification of ways to overcome life contradictions with the purpose of forming value orientations [2].

Student youth, due to a combination of social, psychological, and external factors, constitute a group with heightened vulnerability. This vulnerability manifests across diverse spheres of life activity: from overcoming academic and financial barriers to resolving problems related to mental health and social adaptation.

The issue of youth socialization in the context of the formation of the contemporary information society has attracted the attention of several scholars, including D. Bell, P. Bourdieu, A. Toffler, P. Drucker, E. Giddens, M. McLuhan, J. Habermas, and others. For example, the works of D. Bell (*The Coming Post-Industrial Society: A Venture in Social Forecasting*, 2004), P. Bourdieu (*Structures, Habitus, Practices*, 1995), E. Giddens (*Sociology*, 2005), E. Durkheim (*Sociology of Education*, 1996), J. Habermas (*Stichworte zur Theorie der Sozialisation*, 1973) laid the foundations for the scientific understanding of the problem of socialization in a rapidly changing world [1, p. 43].

To ensure that student youth can effectively fulfill their role as agents in maintaining the dynamics of sustainable development of the country, it is necessary to conduct ongoing research into the aspirations, orientations, and behavioral practices of the young generation in the reunited territories.

Also important is the analysis of the social condition and life strategies of this particular social group, on whose shoulders lies the responsibility for building a prosperous future for the state [5, p. 267].

Based on the general understanding of life strategies and the characteristics of youth as a socio-demographic group, such a complex concept as youth life strategies under conditions of socio-political transformation can be broadly characterized as a system of representations about the goals of one's life path and the means of their realization in the process of professional and spiritual-moral self-determination.

The reunited territories, possessing a unique history and having experienced various external influences, constitute a distinctive 'crossroads' of the past, present, and future. In this context, Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy exerts a significant influence on the formation of consciousness, ideological attitudes, economic models and social structures, worldview, traditional values, and spiritual and ethical orientations of student youth. Simultaneously, student youth face new challenges and opportunities arising from their integration into a new socio-political space and the changing geopolitical situation.

The self-awareness of youth is a highly sensitive indicator of the political and socio-economic transformations occurring in society. These changes significantly influence the formation and evolution of young people's value orientations, which are characterized by temporal fluidity [7, p.1274]. As the demographic group most sensitive to social transformations, student youth serve as carriers of new values and behavioral models shaped by historical conditions and contemporary realities.

It should be especially emphasized that the reunited territories represent a unique example of the interaction of various historical narratives and cultural traditions. This situation creates additional difficulties in the process of youth self-identification and the choice of life orientations.

The post-Soviet legacy of the Ukrainian state significantly influences the formation of youth life strategies, serving as a system of sociocultural coordinates that determine value orientations, behavioral models, and long-term goals of young people. This influence is exerted through mechanisms of transmitting collective memory, the functioning of social institutions, and the reproduction of cultural codes. Historical experience, anchored in family and societal narratives, educational practices, and symbolic space, shapes the younger generation's perception of social reality and their place within it.

Depending on the specific character of Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy, its impact can function either as a resource or as a constraint. On the one hand, it ensures generational continuity, social stability, and serves as a source of motivation. On the other hand, it may preserve outdated stereotypes, reproduce traumatic experiences, and act as a barrier to social mobility and innovation. Amid transformational and integration processes, especially within the post-Soviet space, youth face the necessity of reinterpreting the historical past and developing new life strategies in the context of competing historical attitudes and value systems.

During the collapse of the USSR in 1991. Prior to the reunification of four regions of Ukraine Donetsk and Luhansk People's Republics, Zaporizhzhia and Kherson oblasts with Russia in 2022, in post-Soviet Ukraine the history of the Soviet Union and the historical formation of *Kievan Rus'* was fundamentally falsified. In 2014, political forces espousing far-right views assumed power in Ukraine, grounding their ideology in Russophobia and the denial of the Soviet past. The 2014 annexation of Crimea by Russia and Russia's support for Donbass were used to designate Russia as an aggressor state. In this context, the Ukrainian authorities undertook a revision and reinterpretation of national history, which subsequently resulted in the introduction of distorted information into educational institutions across all levels. The younger generation, receiving partial and biased information, encounters a reassessment of historical events, which may give rise to doubts and contradictions in their understanding of the past [3, p. 45].

Primary manifestations of historical distortion:

Rewriting of textbooks. Numerous examples of distortion of facts and suppression of the role of Russia and the Soviet Union in the shared history have been identified in Ukrainian textbooks on history, literature, and other subjects.

For more than thirty years, no unified, commonly accepted narrative for presenting the history of the Great Patriotic War has been established within Ukraine's school education system. Its construction continues under consistent adherence to the principles of anti-Sovietism and Russophobia [6, p. 33].

Educational materials foster the image of Russia as an enemy, which cultivates a hostile attitude and rejection of shared historical roots among the younger generation. This results in an artificial break of the spiritual connection between generations and the formation of a distorted identity. Ignoring shared cultural heritage. Textbooks downplay the contribution of Russia and the USSR to Ukraine's development, distorting the works of classical authors (for example, Chekhov and Pushkin).

The youth educated with these textbooks have developed an artificial meaning-constructing identity, detached from natural historical roots. This impedes integration into the Russian cultural and educational space. Embedding the image of the enemy in the consciousness of the younger generation leads to the development of hatred, extremism, and rejection of their own historical and cultural traditions. The younger generation is deprived of the opportunity to critically reflect on the past, draw their own conclusions, and establish relationships based on respect and trust. This is fraught with long-term social and cultural consequences.

The economic transformations that began after the dissolution of the USSR were accompanied by structural crises, changes in the labor market, and a decline in living standards, which directly impacted the opportunities and expectations of the younger generation. Since 2014, the economic situation in Ukraine has been markedly unstable [4, p. 60].

In the post-Soviet period, Ukraine underwent deindustrialization, a reduction in industrial production, and the collapse of traditional economic ties. This resulted in a decline in employment, particularly in the industrial sector, and an increase in unemployment among youth. Economic reforms were accompanied by an increase in poverty, inequality, and a reduction in access to social benefits. Young people encountered difficulties in accessing quality education, securing employment, and achieving a decent standard of living.

The post-Soviet economic legacy of Ukraine has negatively impacted the youth in the reunited territories, restricting their life strategies.

Cultural aspects such as language and traditions play a key role in shaping young people's life strategies. Young people raised within the framework of the post-Soviet cultural legacy may make decisions based on distorted perceptions of their identity and societal role. This may be reflected in their career choices, engagement in public life, and attitudes toward cultural values.

Article 10 of the Constitution of Ukraine guarantees the free development, use, and protection of Russian and other languages of Ukraine's national minorities [8, 9, 10, 11]. However, violations of democratic principles in Ukraine's humanitarian policy are registered. This is evidenced in the legislative regulation of language status, where the Ukrainian language is declared the only state language, while the status of Crimean Tatar and other indigenous peoples' languages of Ukraine has not been adequately regulated (meanwhile, the Russian language is not mentioned at all) [12, 13], which is completely contrary to the Constitution of Ukraine and several adopted laws.

In 2023, the Federal Law "On the peculiarities of the legal regulation of relations in the field of culture in connection with the accession to the Russian Federation of the Donetsk People's Republic, the Lugansk People's Republic, the Zaporizhzhia Oblast, and the Kherson Oblast and the establishment within the Russian Federation of new subjects: the Donetsk People's Republic, the Lugansk People's Republic, the Zaporizhzhia Oblast, and the Kherson Oblast" [14] was adopted.

In September 2022. Following the referendum, four new constituent entities were annexed to the Russian Federation: the Donetsk and Luhansk People's Republics, as well as the Zaporizhzhia and Kherson oblasts. According to Ukrainian statistical data as of January 1, 2022, a total of 683,965 males and females aged 13 to 21 resided in the territories of the aforementioned oblasts [15].

Below is a table presenting data on the male and female population of Ukraine in the four oblasts prior to reunification with Russia, aged 13 to 21, as of January 1, 2022.

As of 2026, the age of young people (Table 1) has reached the student age range (17-25 years); based on this, we understand that this population category in the reunified territories was directly affected by Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy, which is reflected in the formation of their life strategies and identity.

Table 1

Age	Donetsk People's Republic	Luhansk People's Republic	Zaporizhzhia Oblast	Kherson Oblast
13 years	42 917	21 350	18 443	12 117
14 years	39 268	19 506	17 026	11 191
15 years	37 963	19 007	16 758	11 053
16 years	34 589	17 067	15 377	9 761
17 years	33 250	16 516	15 294	9 711
18 years	30 652	15 819	14 474	9 632
19 years	28 194	14 834	14 003	8 914
20 years	26 731	14 120	13 294	8 637
21 years	28 973	14 933	13 553	9 002

Conclusion. From the foregoing, it is understood that Ukraine's post-Soviet legacy — the ensemble of value orientations, social practices, institutional models, and symbolic representations formed during the period 1991-2022-affects the worldview, life priorities, and life planning of youth in the reunited territories. Comprehending and analyzing this influence is essential for the development of effective educational programs, social adaptation initiatives, and youth policies.

The number of student youth, considering all migration processes since 2022, provides us with an understanding that the state, regional authorities, and educational institutions in the reunited territories need to develop effective strategies for supporting and developing youth. These strategies aim to accelerate the recovery and adaptation processes to new socio-political, economic, educational, cultural, historical, ideological, and traditional changes, as well as to overcome the hostile identity imposed by the previous political regime.

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火灾紧急情况下救援人员心理状态管理的方法论问题
**METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES IN MANAGING THE MENTAL
STATE OF RESCUERS IN FIRE EMERGENCIES**

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摘要：本文探讨了压力抵抗、适应、最有效的心理治疗方法、自体训练、压力抵抗力的培养和克服方法，以及如何组织自我调节课程，以确保救援人员在各种紧急情况下能够集中精力完成分配的任务。

关键词：各种紧急情况，压力，适应，心理韧性，心理治疗，肌肉紧张

Abstract. *This article addresses issues of stress resistance, adaptation, the most effective psychotherapy methods, autogenic training, instilling stress resistance and ways to overcome it, and organizing self-regulation classes to ensure that rescuers' mental states are focused on performing assigned tasks in various emergency situations.*

Keywords: *Various emergency situations, stress, adaptation, psychological resilience, psychotherapy, muscle tension*

Emergency situations related to fire hazard emergencies (FHS) are characterized by the emergence of harmful factors that affect human vital activity, psychological state, and physical health. These harmful factors develop under the influence of psychotraumatic factors — a complex of intense stimuli that lead to psychological disturbances in the form of reactive (psychogenic) conditions in a majority of individuals during emergencies[1]. In this regard, it is necessary to conduct moral and psychological training to ensure the psychological continuity of personnel for performing emergency rescue and urgent response operations (ER and URO) during emergencies[2].

It should be noted that in emergency situations, psychogenic effects may arise not only from a direct threat to human life but also from an indirect effect related to the expectation of its occurrence.[2] Pathological states — psychogenic disorders — and non-pathological psycho-emotional reactions of individuals to emergencies represent an even greater hazard.

The foundation of the mental health of rescuers is based on social behavior, work productivity, interpersonal relationships, aspirations for personal well-being, creativity, the realization of existing moral, intellectual, and volitional capacities, as well as personality development.

The main factors determining the mental health of fire emergency rescuers include deterioration of the socio-economic situation, variability of living conditions, increased stressogenic factors, national and ethnic conflicts, as well as local armed conflicts. Consequently, this negatively impacts the mental health of rescuers, evidenced by increased rudeness in their behavior, self-centeredness, immorality, nonconformist interpersonal relationships, aggressiveness, depression, and psychoactive substance abuse.

N. A. Aliev and S. S. Guzalov observe that among military personnel, emotional reactions such as fear and noise-induced stress primarily arise in real danger situations; therefore, measures must ensure that one stressor does not influence another. The history of the Great Patriotic War shows that the organization of military collectives, units, and formations in this respect is robust and unwavering, and as a result of the swift elimination of disturbances, the assigned task is completed promptly” [2].

The quality of rescuers’ mental health is determined by the aggregate of their individual psychological characteristics and intrinsic physiological states. In other words, the interplay of biological, psychological, and socio-ecological factors constitutes the foundation of mental health (including hereditary traits, upbringing, quality of military training, temperament and character type, habits, stress tolerance in combat, psychological trauma, etc.).

Stress is defined as a nonspecific reaction of the organism to external or internal demands, and its perception as the general adaptation syndrome. This concept was proposed by Canadian biologist and physician Hans Selye (Selye, 1960). Selye developed the doctrine of stress based on the concept of the general adaptation syndrome, which consists of a set of various reactions enabling the mobilization of psychophysiological resources of the organism to adapt to challenging conditions[3].

H. Selye established that regardless of the nature of any stimulus acting on the organism, the organism responds to various adverse influences — such as cold, fatigue, fear, confusion, pain, and others — not by employing a specific protective reaction for each distinct effect, but rather via a generalized and similarly complex response. Concurrently, certain processes take place during the interval between the stimulus effect and the organism’s reaction. These processes demonstrate that stages of tension are characteristic of any adaptation process, as shown in the classical studies of H. Selye.[3]

At the initial stage, the organism’s defense mechanisms are mobilized. Simultaneously, the body is working intensively. During this stage, the individual feels physically and mentally well, with an elevated mood.

By the end of the first stage, most individuals achieve some progress, demonstrating increased work capacity.

Following the first stage is the second stage — resistance (stabilization) — considered the most effective phase of adaptation; during this stage, all previously disrupted parameters stabilize at a new equilibrium.

The third stage is the exhaustion phase. This stage arises when stress persists over an extended period or when stressors are exceptionally intense. Structural changes occur in the body: as adaptive capacity is exhausted, the organism loses its ability to counteract stress and reduce its detrimental effects. Energy reserves are depleted, and physiological and psychological defenses are compromised. The body is no longer capable of self-protection. Intervention can only be provided through external support or stress alleviation.

Key characteristics of psychological stress:

(1) a stress state that arises from the interaction between the body and the surrounding environment;

Stress represents a heightened condition compared to normal motivation and necessitates the recognition of threat for its onset.

3) Stressful events occur when the typical adaptive response is insufficient.[4]

It is important to emphasize that not all negative effects induce stress. During stress, specific hormones enter the bloodstream, under whose influence the functioning modes of the body's organs and systems are altered. For example, heart rate increases, blood coagulation accelerates, and the body's protective functions alter.

Thus, stress arises when the organism is compelled to adapt to new conditions; hence, stress is inseparable from the adaptation process.

Depending on the consequences of stress, researchers distinguish between eustress (positive stress, which is associated with beneficial effects and mobilizes the organism) and distress (negative stress, encompassing factors that exert a destructive influence on the organism).

The transformation of stress into suffering occurs under excessively intense impact of environmental factors and living conditions, whereby the body's functional resources are depleted too rapidly or the mechanisms of psychological regulation are disrupted.

Many authors indicate the existence of danger as a prerequisite for the emergence of stress. However, there is no doubt that the onset and progression of stress primarily depend on the psychological characteristics of the individual. Individuals respond differently to the same threat. Some individuals exhibit increased activity, and under stress their performance continues to improve for an extended period (this phenomenon is referred to as 'lion stress'). In contrast, others show a decrease in activity, with efficiency rapidly declining (termed 'rabbit stress')[6].

Anxiety is one of the most significant personality traits influencing susceptibility to stress.

By 'unease' we mean an unconscious feeling of danger, fear, anxiety, apprehension, or uncertainty. This sensation serves as a signal indicating excessive tension in regulatory mechanisms or disruption of adaptive processes.

Search and rescue operations are associated with heightened and often excessive psychological and physical arousal during the routine activities of rescuers. The negative impact of stress factors is experienced by rescuers themselves, their groups, and their family members.

Consequently, it has been established that the elimination of negative consequences of stress factors through psychotherapeutic methods constitutes the most significant factor in managing the mental state of rescuers [5].

The negative impact of psychotraumatic conditions particularly escalates in the context of emergency consequence mitigation. Under stress, the issue of preventing such conditions is especially acute for rescuers during effective performance of their duties, even in cases of unexplained illnesses, since in extreme conditions the sequelae of such illnesses may progress into severe diseases threatening the rescuer's health.

For the prevention of various diseases and successful task execution, the rescuer's ability to obtain adequate short-term rest and rapidly recover strength is critically important.

There are several types of defenses employed by the intrapsychic mechanism of mental adaptation:

- (1) Awareness of factors provoking anxiety;
- (2) A sense of urgency in response to specific stimuli;
- (3) Reduction in motivational level, i. e., devaluation of primary needs;
- (4) Conceptualization.

Adaptation is a dynamic process whereby flexible living organism systems preserve their stability, which is essential for their existence, development, and reproduction despite fluctuating conditions. The adaptation mechanism, developed through long-term evolution, ensures the organism's capacity to persist within an ever-changing environment.

Adaptation transpires when significant changes occur within the 'organism-environment' system, facilitating the establishment of a new homeostatic state. Adaptation is a continual process driven by the organism and its environment maintaining a state of dynamic, rather than static, equilibrium.

It is important for an individual to maintain adequate relationships within the 'individual-environment' system, although all parameters of the system may vary; in this context, one can refer to mental adaptation.

Mental adaptation can be defined as the process of establishing optimal harmony between an individual and their environment during human activity, which enables the fulfillment of the individual's actual needs and the achievement of significant

related goals, as well as ensures maximal human engagement, behavior, and response to environmental demands.

The study of adaptive processes is closely connected with the concepts of emotional tension and stress.

The professional duties of rescuers at the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Azerbaijan Republic are characterized by exposure to numerous stressors and place high demands on the professionalism and psychological qualities of individuals responsible for ensuring operational effectiveness in extreme conditions.

The regulation of emotional states represents one of the most complex challenges in psychology, addressing both fundamental and applied problems [4, 5].

The specifics of the professional activity of rescuers are associated with the negative impact of adverse conditions, which may cause severe stress and lead to the development of certain diseases (neuropsychiatric disorders, hypertension, gastric ulcers, etc.) [5].

Methods for alleviating mental stress, reducing stress, and enhancing resilience to it.

At present, various psychotherapeutic methods exist: suggestion during hypnotic sleep, rational psychotherapy (influencing an individual through logical persuasion), suggestion in the waking state, autogenic exercises, relaxation of active and passive muscles (the simplest sets of exercises aimed at reducing compulsive muscle tension), among other techniques.

The selection of a particular method depends on the individual's mental state and personal characteristics. If the individual is ill, the selection should be made by a specialist, and self-treatment is contraindicated. Everyone can and should take preventive measures independently. This article attempts to provide a concise overview of the most appropriate psychotherapeutic methods for self-application.

Through systematic training and instruction, rescuers will be able to rapidly master these methods and implement them effectively. This will enable rescuers to regulate their emotions, maintain calmness under extreme conditions, alleviate emotional stress, and consequently enhance the effectiveness of resolving professional challenges, including emergency situations.

The most effective psychotherapeutic method for addressing the aforementioned challenges is autogenic training. The essential components of autogenic training include voluntary muscular relaxation and correct breathing techniques. Therefore, prior to mastering autogenic exercises, it is necessary to learn proper relaxation and breathing methods.

How to manage and mitigate stress?

If you experience stress (or severe fatigue) accompanied by unpleasant symptoms (heightened nervous tension, stiffness, anxiety, agitation, fear, headaches, reduced mental or physical capacity), and you feel the need to rest or sleep but are unable to do so, we recommend employing simple yet effective rehabilitation techniques.

1. Gently massage the most tense or painful areas of the neck without causing injury, using careful hand movements while seated or walking around the room. If the hands become fatigued, they should be shaken up and down for a certain duration, while continuing the massage for approximately 5 minutes.

2. Stand up (if this is difficult, continue sitting or lying down), extend your arms forward, comfortably support them at the elbows, and perform the first 'ideomotor' technique: mentally visualize your arms beginning to relax automatically, moving apart effortlessly without muscular effort. If the arms begin to move away from each other, this signifies the activation of rest and the initiation of stress reduction. Wait until the arms are fully separated from each other, then repeat this technique 3-4 times in succession. If you do not have the courage to perform this action, you will be unable to accomplish it. In this case, it is necessary to deepen the usual gentle warm-up exercises by taking several breaths in and out slightly deeper than normal. Clench your fists and repeat the open palm technique once more.

3. Regardless of whether the first technique is 'ideomotor' or not, spread your hands to the sides in the usual manner and perform the second 'ideomotor' technique: mentally adapt to the comfortable movement of the hands moving toward each other. Repeat this technique 3 to 4 times regardless of the result. If reception does not occur between repetitions, perform several simple and light warm-up movements, as in the previous case.

4. Lower your hands and mentally visualize one rising naturally. Then raise the other hand. If you are performing these techniques while standing, take a deep breath and relax as you raise your hands as high as you comfortably can. You will experience an inner lightness.

5. After completing the 'ideological' technique, immediately sit or lie down, regardless of whether the technique is effective or not; at that moment, the desired outcome occurs: relaxation and a sense of inner freedom. You have successfully relieved stress.

Your head will also feel light; you will experience freshness, vitality, and a sense of full strength. The basic method you have chosen is the simplest to perform and can be used independently, without undergoing the entire rehabilitation procedure. A single technique is sufficient to eliminate unwanted 'nervous disorders' at the critical moment, in an important situation, with a single imperceptible short motion. Relieve anger-related tension, quickly master self-control, and develop self-confidence.

How to enhance resilience to stress?

The stress resilience training course comprises five half-hour sessions conducted at times convenient for all participants; however, the preventive program should begin after the working day, not before it [7, 8].

The course's effectiveness is ensured by incorporating a specialized releasing 'scanning' exercise that facilitates the performance of the basic 'ideomotor' exercise.

The ‘ideomotor’ training itself is no longer used solely as a method for tension release, relaxation, or technique but also serves as a fundamental psychophysiological foundation for developing mobilization and self-regulation skills.

‘Smoking’ test.

When it is necessary to assess the initial nervous tension (stress level), it is sufficient to employ any one of the three ‘ideomotor’ methods described above. For example, stand up and extend your arms forward, mentally visualizing your arms gradually spreading smoothly to the sides. If they do not respond to your will, the connection between will and body is disrupted due to heightened nervous tension. You will need to execute several mild exercises.

Scanning of very subtle movements.

This exercise involves a specific sequence of repetitive periodic mechanical movements that allows precise identification of the most appropriate movement, as it requires a particular order.

1. Repeat any circular motion that provokes dizziness, to which you are accustomed and comfortable, for thirty seconds.
2. Perform any repetitive movements of the shoulder girdle for thirty seconds — these are easy and comfortable for you.
3. Perform chest movements for thirty seconds — it is effortless and pleasant for you.
4. Perform repetitive shoulder movements, such as arm circles.
5. Perform any repetitive movement at knee level for thirty seconds that is comfortable and convenient for you.

Repeat the thirty-second movement that appears easiest and most pleasant to you. This is your primary movement toward freedom. You may be familiar with everyday activities — now you are consciously performing what was previously done involuntarily during moments of nervous tension.

Psychological resilience [9].

When employing ‘IoT techniques,’ it is necessary to adhere to the following two rules.

1. If psychological tension impedes the execution of the desired ‘ideomotor’ movement, perform a brief inhalation and exhalation.
2. Once you achieve a state of calm, begin to develop stress resilience skills by mentally imagining the stressful stimulus that disturbs you and undermines your self-confidence; consequently, you aim to enhance your psychological resilience by overcoming fear. Simultaneously, observe the body’s reaction, which may present as various autonomic sensations (such as mild trembling, alterations in breathing, heart rate, etc.). Take a brief rest, pause from stress, and alleviate unpleasant sensations using techniques and physical exercises that are convenient for you. Repeat this process 2-3 times.

Now, after 2-3 repetitions of the exercise, the perception of the stimulus disappears, triggering an undesirable stress response in the body not only during training but also in real-life scenarios. In other words, your mental health has improved. Moreover, you will notice reduced fatigue and improved ability to cope with various stressful situations, as well as faster self-regulation.

Rest techniques. Derived from Latin, this term denotes rest, stress reduction, and psychotherapy, which are applied in meditation and autogenic training. This refers to the voluntary relaxation of all muscles in a relaxed posture, serving to divert attention from unpleasant thoughts and emotions and combining both physical and mental rest.

It is well established that human muscles are classified into two groups: involuntary (smooth) muscles and voluntary (striated) muscles. Involuntary muscles, such as those of the intestines and heart, function without voluntary control, whereas voluntary muscles, such as the biceps, triceps, and others, function under voluntary neural control.

It is very difficult to relax all voluntary muscles of the body simultaneously. When focusing on one muscle group (such as the leg muscles) and achieving their complete relaxation, it becomes apparent that other muscle groups (abdomen, facial muscles, etc.) remain tense. Attempting to relax these can paradoxically trigger contraction in the muscles that have already been relaxed. An untrained individual is unable to release muscle tension throughout the body, even during sleep, despite this being necessary for adequate rest.

Neuromuscular relaxation.

Progressive muscle relaxation is a technique that helps reduce muscle tension and, consequently, stress and anxiety.

Progressive muscle relaxation is a systematic method of progressively and regularly tensing and relaxing muscle groups throughout the body, aimed at achieving a state of complete relaxation.

Complete relaxation is achievable through two essential processes:

By tensing and subsequently relaxing the muscles, one generates a type of impulse that facilitates deeper muscle relaxation than what occurs under normal conditions.

This can be observed by comparing the states of muscle tension and relaxation.

Before beginning physical exercise, it is necessary to remove or loosen any clothing that restricts movement. Remove your glasses and contact lenses, and attempt to achieve maximal comfort. Gently recline and close your eyes. Primarily, focus your attention on the breathing process. Perceive how air enters through the nostrils into the lungs, how the chest and abdomen expand during inhalation, and how they contract during exhalation.

Chest. “Everything begins with the muscles. Take a deep breath and hold it. Then exhale completely and relax as you breathe. Release the tension... Let us

return to the usual routine... Have you ever experienced a tingling sensation in your chest when breathing? Have you ever experienced relief following surgery? Let us examine and evaluate this, as we will need to repeat the exercise. Breathe deeply... Very deeply... Hold your breath briefly and relax as you exhale. Take a deep breath and focus on the variations in your sensations to successfully repeat the process. Pause for 5 to 10 seconds.

Lower body segments (legs and feet)

Place both feet firmly on the ground. Raise your heels... Then lift both feet higher. Maintain this position and relax while breathing. Then gently press your feet down. Repeat this exercise. As you relax, you may notice a slight heaviness in the heels, indicating a relaxed posture.

Next lesson. Place both heels firmly on the floor and raise your toes as high as possible. Lift your toes and hold them in this position while inhaling deeply and relaxing. Repeat this exercise. From this moment, you may experience a tingling sensation in your legs. The muscles are relaxed. Break — 20 seconds.

Omba and Snow. Let us examine the thigh muscles. This exercise is very simple. Extend both legs straight out in front of you. If this is uncomfortable, you may gently stretch your legs in response. You should cultivate a sense of tension in the thighs. This exercise should be repeated.

Imagine pressing your heels into the sand on a beach to relax the opposing muscle group. Plant your feet firmly on the ground... More firmly... Allow yourself to feel more relaxed and at ease than you do now... Now, you need to relax in your environment. Let your muscles loosen. Focus on this sensation. Pause for 20 seconds.

Hands. At the same time, both hands are firmly clenched into fists. Clench both fists as tightly as possible. Hold, then release and relax... Repeat this several times.

Simply spread your fingers as wide as possible to relax the opposing muscle group. Relax... Repeat several times. Pay attention to any warmth or heat in your hands and arms. Rest for 20 seconds.

Shoulders. They carry a significant amount of stress and tension. This exercise involves mentally lifting the shoulders toward the ears in a vertical plane, attempting to bring the tops of the shoulders as close as possible to the ears. Raise your shoulders as high as possible, then relax. Focus on the sensation of heaviness in your shoulders. Release your shoulders... relax... Rest for 20 seconds.

Face. "Let us begin with the mouth. Smile as broadly as possible. It is necessary to be attentive to auditory perception. Maintain composure and relax... Repeat this several times.

Purse your lips as if kissing someone to relax the opposing muscle group. Rest and repeat this several times.

Now let us proceed to the eyes. You need to tightly close your eyes. Wait... Relax peacefully. Repeat this process [9].

The final exercise. Raise your eyebrows as high as possible. Keep your eyes closed during this. Raise your eyebrows. Hold and relax... Repeat the exercise. Spend a few minutes relaxing the face. You relax most of the major muscles of the body. You feel that your body is deeply relaxed. This is a positive sensation.

Conclusion

1. Depending on the type of tension, the factors causing mental strain, as well as the transformation of stressors, frustrations, and similar phenomena into a positive and mobilizing effect on the personality, contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of rescuers' performance.

2. Human behavior in hazardous situations is directly proportional to the adaptation of cognitive processes within the conscious system to the surrounding environment. The level of development of the adaptive psyche accelerates the advancement of cognitive processes, cognitive abilities, knowledge, intellectual capabilities, and habits.

3. It is critically important to utilize the positive role of psychotherapy in addressing stress-induced disorders among rescuers during the management of fire emergency aftermaths.

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服务作为一种动机
SERVICE AS A MOTIVE

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摘要：本文探讨了个人动机，重点关注服务，阐述了服务在动机层级中的特殊地位及其表现形式。文章指出，人们的精神追求发生了转变，道德观念也趋于简化，例如，人们热衷于自我实现，并试图从中挖掘创造潜能，将其视为人生的意义。文章论证了服务动机必须成为精神教育的持久目标，以及个人道德的核心，以维系文明。

关键词：人格，服务，服务动机，服务中的自我实现

Abstract. *The article presents personal motives, focusing on service, its special status in the hierarchy of motives, and its forms of expression. It notes a shift in spiritual aspiration and a simplification of morality, exemplified by a passion for self-realization and an attempt to uncover creative potential within it as the meaning of life. It demonstrates that the motive of service must be an enduring goal of spiritual education and the moral core of the individual for the preservation of civilization.*

Keywords: *personality, service, motive for service, self-realization in service.*

Personal motives have a complex multilevel structure. By their origin, motives are either biologically or socially conditioned; socially oriented motives may be subdivided into altruistic and egoistic. Egoistic motives include those related to approval, self-affirmation, power, personal benefit, and well-being, whereas altruistic motives include those of assistance and service. Among altruistic motives, the motive of service holds a distinctive position, being unevenly expressed in society during different developmental periods. The formation of the motive of service necessitates compliance with strict discipline and a rigorous style of upbringing, or life's ordeals. The antecedent of this motive is the motive of assistance, which is associated with love for people and the need to care for others, indicating a value-laden attitude towards humanity as a whole. Collectively, the motive of assistance is characteristic of a mature personality.

The idea of service among the Russian people is reflected in artistic literature, art, history, and the scholarly works of Russian philosophers. The motive of service

constitutes a red thread running throughout the entire history of Russia's development and serves as the internal axis of the personality. Service was historically associated with the acceptance of Christianity and the survival of the country surrounded by numerous enemies.

The following forms of service are distinguished: religious — service to God, social — service to people, and civic — service to the state (the Tsar, the Fatherland). The Russian idea of service is associated with spiritual culture, a sense of vocation, and a duty towards God, the people, and the Motherland. One can also identify particular forms of social service — service to art and science. Thus, the great Russian poet A. S. Pushkin wrote that he would long remain dear to the people because he awakened benevolent feelings with his lyre [4]. The nobility had military obligations and served the state. The high military art of the Russian people owes its evolution to the traditions of cultivating the motive of service as the moral foundation of the individual and society.

In the Soviet Union, despite the atheistic orientation of spiritual development, the tradition of cultivating this motive was preserved, which found its reflection in the heroic defense of the country, as well as in culture and education. The heroism of the Soviet people, labor and civic feats, and the significant achievements of the country in scientific and technological progress are inextricably linked.

The topic of self-realization of human potential in service was examined in the works of Russian philosophers N. A. Berdyaev and I. A. Ilyin [1], [2]. It is important to note the instrumental character of self-realization inherent in Russian culture and the subsequent substitution of the meaning of spiritual aspirations, manifested in the forgetting of service and a shift toward simplified morality — self-realization as the meaning of life and the realization of creative potential therein.

Aristotle wrote about achieving eudaimonia through the realization of one's potential capabilities. In Western scientific thought in the early twentieth century, self-realization began to be considered the ultimate goal of realizing individual abilities (K. Goldstein). In Western philosophy, self-realization is understood as both the process and the result of the embodiment of life's purpose. In this regard, spiritual development is narrowed to the pursuit of happiness through meditation, creativity, or, for instance, psychotherapy. A clear distinction exists between the sobornost of Russian spiritual life and the liberation of the Western individual's soul through individually oriented practices.

The preoccupation with self-realization as an autonomous value emerged in the 1990s. of the twentieth century, when a stream of psychological personality theories surged into Russia, disregarding such phenomena of the high morality of Russian culture as feats and self-sacrifice. The humanistic personality theory of A. Maslow and the needs pyramid [3], developed in the mid-twentieth century based on the American consumer society model, began to be positioned as paradigmatic, which

gradually led to the blurring of the moral foundation of the contemporary Russian individual. The temporary loss of the service motive due to the substitution of values and meanings of the spiritual aspirations of the individual is not merely a simplification of the intellectual sphere of the individual, but a deterioration of the soul, a loss of morality and ethics, constituting the foundation of the national ethical framework as a whole.

The prosocial altruistic service motive was replaced by a pro-individual, egoistic motive — self-realization. In the concept of self-realization as such, no evidently negative aspect was apparent at first glance; on the contrary, it testified to the individual's possession of a tertiary volitional quality — autonomy. However, therein lies the subtext of the rejection of communality, sobornost, and the unity of the people. The renunciation of collective responsibility has eroded the moral foundation of the Russian individual.

Russian society, as a whole, demonstrates resilience despite the influence of a foreign culture and seemingly develops the requisite immunity against the alien element. Volunteering, understood as selfless participation in the lives of others, constitutes a genuine embodiment of the motive of service and attests to the spiritual health of the nation.

The motive of service is spiritual both in essence and in origin, as it is frequently formed through deliberate education and requires special conditions for its reproduction. Service gradually becomes the central axis of the personality, safeguarding it from the disintegration of its moral core. The change in character occurs throughout the entire lifespan. In certain cases, an individual comes to service following significant losses, experiences, disappointments, and frequently despair, in the hope of finding external support upon realizing the impossibility of acting otherwise. In such cases, the activating factor is the moral imperative — conscience [5].

One of the traditional methods of cultivating the motive of service is the use of vivid examples of heroism and self-sacrifice in their various forms. Identification with the hero occurs automatically, under the influence of a strong emotional impression. However, a necessary condition for this is the cultural background, namely a profound immersion in Russian culture. From an evolutionary standpoint, this is not merely a method of motivation and the making of correct choices but a strategy that promotes the long-term survival of civilization. Socialization in a consumer society complicates the realization of a motive at such a level; service is not supported, ignored, ridiculed, or consigned to oblivion.

Thus, service should be a perennial goal of spiritual education, the moral core of the personality, and of human civilization.

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信息战背景下青少年的信息安全和心理安全
**INFORMATION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY OF YOUTH
IN THE CONTEXT OF INFORMATION WARFARE**

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摘要：本文致力于研究信息安全与心理安全问题，尤其关注学生群体。在现代信息战、操控技术日益增强以及信息流动不断加速的背景下，个人意识面临着受到负面影响的威胁，因此需要重视信息生态和信息卫生等概念。本研究分析了学生的信息安全与心理安全水平，并识别了影响其状况的决定因素，例如内控点和批判性思维的发展。结果表明，信息安全与心理安全水平高的学生拥有积极乐观的生活态度和良好的批判性思维能力，这表明他们能够抵御负面信息的影响。

关键词：信息安全与心理安全，信息战，批判性思维，操控技术，心理与教育安全，信息生态，价值取向，心理稳定性。

Annotation. *The article is devoted to the study of the problems of information and psychological security, especially among students. In the context of modern information wars, the intensification of manipulative technologies and the intensification of information flows, there is a threat of a negative impact on the consciousness of individuals, which requires attention to the concepts of information ecology and hygiene. The study analyzed the level of information and psychological security of students, identified the determinants of its condition, such as the internal locus of control and the development of critical thinking. The results showed that students with high information and psychological security have an optimistic life position and well-formed critical thinking, which indicates the presence of resistance to negative information influences.*

Keywords: *information and psychological security, information warfare, critical thinking, manipulation technology, psychological and pedagogical security, information ecology, value orientations, psychological stability.*

In the modern context, the issue of ensuring information and psychological security holds a leading position among the most urgent problems within the psychopedagogical field. The modern level of development of information technologies enables a significant impact on both mass consciousness and the consciousness of the individual [3; 4; 8; 9].

It is well known that the intensification of information flows, the increasing informational load on recipients' psyche, and the broadening spectrum of informational influences — considering the understanding of subtle psychophysiological mechanisms of perception and response of the target audience — are also employed to enhance methods of external control over personality. Such manipulations imply the deliberate modification of the system of values, motivations, and personal dispositions of respondents, which in the context of information warfare bears a negative semantic connotation [4; 5; 7].

The question of information ecology and information hygiene is highly pertinent; however, the realization of the concept of the ecological nature of the information environment in contemporary life encounters significant challenges within the domain of internet communications and the realities of virtual space. The complexity of information exchanges within the integrated informational environment is progressively increasing, which exponentially intensifies its influence on the human psyche, more frequently exerting a destructive impact on the unique life trajectory of the individual and restructuring it to conform with the global mainstream, particularly when the individual lacks sufficient 'informational immunity,' manifested, in particular, through critical thinking and reflective cognitive processes [1; 2; 6; 8].

As noted by researchers specializing in the media environment, mass communications, PR technologies, and issues of information and psychological security — such as A. V. Pocheptsov, R. Cialdini, A. V. Lyashuk, I. F. Kefeli, R. M. Yusupov, and others — an individual subjected to external controlling influence develops the illusion of identification and complete mutual understanding with the controlling system. The pseudo-values and pseudo-meanings subtly imposed by this system gradually become internalized as personal introjects, which the individual is unable to independently recognize [4-7].

As a result of such influence, including through the deliberate activation of 'Overton windows,' we obtain a 'reformatted' individual, an 'artificial nation' detached from their original cultural and historical heritage, as exemplified by 'post-Maidan Ukraine.' In fact, a substantial portion of the unified Slavic ethnos has been severed from the context of its own spiritual and cultural-historical

subjectivity through manipulative technologies of information warfare employed by their beneficiaries over recent decades.

The negative impact of informational content on the individual consciousness of representatives of various age groups is equally harmful and dangerous, but primarily affects the consciousness of youth, who constitute the creative potential and prospective development force of society. More than ever, in the context of the foregoing, the issue of information and psychological security of contemporary youth, particularly students, is brought to the forefront [3; 4; 5; 7].

The issues of information and psychological security, as well as the analysis of information wars and the mechanisms of their impact on both mass and individual consciousness, including within the domain of media communications, have been explored by scholars such as Borshchov N. A. (2011), Reshetnikov V. Ya. (2009), Nalchadzhyan A. A. (2010), Shatilo Ya. S. (2009), Lyashuk A. V. (2008), Shlykova N. L. (2004), Roshchin S. K., Sosnin V. A. (1995), et al. Information and psychological security of the individual as a semantic construct can be examined from multiple perspectives: philosophical, medical, cultural, and psycho-pedagogical. Overall, this phenomenon can be understood as the protection of an individual's vital interests within the information sphere, alongside the individual's awareness of negative informational and psychological impacts and the mastery of methods for their effective counteraction [3; 5].

Information and psychological warfare is a deliberate impact using information (oral, printed, video) on the consciousness and the emotional-volitional domain of individuals [3; 4; 5].

Given the extreme relevance of the topic under study, we conducted an investigation into the characteristics of information and psychological safety among student youth, positing that its basis would be the psychological resilience of the student's personality to negative informational influences, with the most significant determinants being an internal locus of control, adequately developed critical thinking, the formation of the value-semantic sphere, reflexivity, and an optimistic life position.

To test the working hypothesis, we conducted an empirical study among first-year students at universities of Luhansk and the Stakhanov Pedagogical College of LSPU (80 respondents), employing psychological interviews, selective observation, and the following instruments: the Rotter Internal-External Locus of Control Scale (LOC) adapted by E. F. Bazhin and colleagues (1984); the diagnostic methodology for assessing personality activity and optimism by N. Vodolpianova — M. Stein; the critical thinking diagnostic methodology by Yu. Gushchin and N. V. Smirnova; the questionnaire "Differential Type of Reflection," developed by D. A. Leontiev, E. M. Lapteva, E. N. Osin, and A. Zh. Salikhova (2009), and the diagnostic method for assessing the actual structure of value orientations by S. Bubnova, along with a proprietary questionnaire for the subjective assessment

of information-psychological security, which considered respondents' psycho-emotional reactions to negative informational content, their uncritical perception of information, and its impact on their behavioral responses.

As a result of the conducted diagnostics, two groups of respondents were distinguished: those with an adequate condition of information and psychological security — comprising 73 % of the entire sample (group 1) — and respondents with impaired information and psychological security (group 2-27% of students).

In the first group of respondents, the internal locus of control (measured by the general internality scale) prevailed in 60% of cases. These students considered significant events to be the result of their own actions; They felt responsible for the strategy being constructed for their own lives. In 25% of cases, the locus of subjective control fell within the range of medium values, and only in 15% was it external; these respondents did not identify a significant relationship between their own actions and life events and did not consider themselves capable of controlling these events.

According to the results of the personality activity and optimism diagnostic method by N. Vodopyanova — M. According to Steinha, among respondents with an adequate state of information and psychological safety, the personality type «Active Optimist» was identified in 55% of cases, while the personality type «Realist» was determined in 25% of young men and women; with only 10% of cases attributable to the personality types «Passive Optimist» and «Active Pessimist» respectively.

In 60% of cases, students exhibited an average level of critical thinking, and in 30%, a high level.

According to the «Differential Type of Reflection» questionnaire, systemic reflection predominated in this group (57% of cases), while the type «Introspection» was registered in 30% of cases; In 13% of cases, respondents exhibited quasi-reflexive characteristics.

According to the diagnostic methodology for the real structure of value orientations developed by S. Bubnova, it was possible to establish that in this group, within the individual profiles of students, significant were groups of values such as 'Love,' 'Communication,' 'Health,' and 'Help and Mercy towards others.' 'Social activity aimed at achieving positive changes in society.'

In the second group of respondents with compromised information and psychological security, according to the Subjective Level of Control (SLC) questionnaire by J. Rotter, adapted by E. F. Bazhin and colleagues. An external locus of control prevailed in 75% of cases, while in 25% of cases — as in the first group — the locus of subjective control was within the average range.

According to the methodology for diagnosing activity and optimism of personality developed by N. Vodopyanova — M. As reported by Shtein, 35% of students in group 2 were classified as 'Passive Optimists'; 40% exhibited the personality type 'Active Pessimist,' characterized by a heightened tendency to criticize others

and the world at large without attempting to effect change; 25 % of respondents were identified as realists.

According to the results of Yu. Gushchin's methodology for diagnosing critical thinking, in the majority of cases, the level was low (55 %); in 45 % of cases, an average level of critical thinking was recorded, with a tendency towards a low level.

According to data from the 'Differential Type of Reflection' questionnaire, quasi-reflection predominated in this group (45 % of cases), while the 'Introspection' type was recorded in 20 %; the 'Systemic Reflection' type was recorded in 10 % of cases; In 25 % of cases, respondents demonstrated a lack of reflexivity.

Within the value orientation system of respondents in this group, the profiles of 'Pleasant leisure, rest' predominated; 'Health,' 'Love,' and 'High material well-being' prevailed, whereas altruistic values and values of social activity were insufficiently represented.

Thus, respondents with an adequate state of information and psychological security predominantly exhibited an internal locus of control; An optimistic life position was present in 55 % of cases; critical thinking was adequately developed (60 % of cases exhibited an average level of critical thinking, 30 % a high level) alongside systemic reflection (57 % of respondents). Furthermore, altruistic and socially oriented values were notably significant within the value orientation profiles, contrasting with the findings from the group characterized by impaired information and psychological security, thereby supporting the validation of our working hypothesis.

In summary, it can be concluded that to increase the level of information and psychological security among students in the context of information warfare, it is essential to emphasize the development of critical thinking in contemporary youth, a conscious, active, and optimistic life position, as well as the formation of a value continuum that fosters resilience, personal optimism, and high social engagement.

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导师在塑造学员主观立场中的四种策略

**FOUR STRATEGIES OF THE MENTOR'S ACTIVITY
IN THE FORMATION OF THE MENTEE'S SUBJECTIVE POSITION**

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摘要：在当今社会发展阶段，指导不再仅仅被视为一种适应环境和加速职场学习的工具。在现代经济中，它正日益成为一种关键的社会程序，不仅促进个人和职业发展，也有助于个人获得积极的公民意识和主体性地位。有效的指导（“策略师”）能够帮助我们解决两个方面的任务：短期目标——培养必要的道德和职业素质；长期目标——激发被指导者的创造潜能，培养其持续的创造性活动 and 自我发展动力，即形成我们称之为“创造性”的主体性地位。

关键词：指导活动，导师策略，主体性地位，发展，共同活动，主体间关系。

Abstract. *At the current stage of society's development, mentoring is increasingly seen not merely as a tool for adaptation and accelerated learning in the workplace. In the modern economy, it is becoming a key social procedure not only for personal and professional development of a person, but also for gaining an active civic and subjective position. Effective mentoring ("Strategist") allows us to solve tasks both in the short term — the formation of necessary moral and professional qualities, and in the long term — the actualization of the mentee's creative potential, the manifestation of sustained motivation for creative activity and further self-development, that is, the formation of his, we call, "inventive" subject position.*

Keywords: *mentoring activity, mentor's strategy, subject position, development, joint activity, subject-subject relations.*

On May 21, 2025, the Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1264-r "On Approval of the Concept of Mentoring Development in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2030 (hereinafter referred to as the Concept)

[1] was published. The goals of mentoring are defined by: the development of the mentee's personality; the formation of his diligence, responsible attitude to work and its results, as well as to the traditional values of the Russian people; the formation of the mentee's necessary knowledge, skills and abilities.

The Concept reveals the basic concepts of mentoring and mentor. Thus, mentoring is defined as a socio-pedagogical technology for supporting a person's personal and professional development, and the formation of traditional Russian spiritual and moral values" [1, p.3]. A mentor is called "a bearer of significant experience, traditional Russian spiritual and moral values" [1, p.3]. At the same time, the document does not clearly indicate what exactly is considered "the development of the mentee's personality", which is the result of the mentor's activity with his ward (student).

In foreign literature, mentoring is usually described as a relationship between a mentor and a ward, in which a more experienced employee (mentor) provides career support and/or personal support to a less experienced employee (student) [2]. From this vision, it can be assumed that the management experience in the form of "professional support" and "personal support" should be positive. However, a number of researchers have noted in their works that mentoring sometimes leads to negative consequences [3; 4]. For example, some mentors may be overly harsh, picky about students, or set high standards for students, which may not contribute to student development [5; 6].

If we consider the meaning of the mentor's activity in production, helping his ward, then we propose to take as a basis some of the recommendations of N. S. Pryazhnikov [7], which he gave to an employee of an enterprise helping another in professional self-determination and formation. Here are some generalized positions: 1) focusing on the early effectiveness of the ward's independent activity at his workplace; 2) helping the mentee to master a new "role" for himself in the specific realities of industrial and socio-economic situations; 3) helping a newcomer to independently find the true meanings of their new work in the context of co-presence and shared activity with others (including in joint activities), building a full and decent life, where production is only a part of it; 4) mentor's self-development in the course of joint activities, "when helping another person find meanings becomes a condition for their own personal and professional development" [7, p.5].

Thus, the conclusion suggests itself that the result of the developing activity of a mentor (parent, educator, teacher, master of industrial training, supervisor) is the formation of the subjective position of his ward. However, it should be noted that in Russian science the very concept of a subject position is defined in different ways: as a characteristic of a personality, as a system of relationships, as a position of personal or professional self-organization, as a creative principle in a person, or as "authorship, self-construction, active transformative strategy of a personality" [8,

p. 95]. In line with the subject-activity approach (K. A. Abulkhanova, A. V. Brushlinsky, S. L. Rubinstein, and others), the subjective position of a personality is interpreted as an integral orientation of the subject to achieve independently set goals and objectives in activities, taking into account the existing socio-cultural conditions, available inclinations, abilities, and mastered ways of activity. [9]. Thus, the subjective position presupposes an individual's claim to the value of being himself, the master and steward of his own activities.

What kinds or types of subject positions are known today? For example, L. V. Levitskaya [10], in her study of the problem of professional self-realization of students, identifies two types of the subject position of first-year students: *the unformed position* and *the position of the subject of education*. In the study of S. A. Gilmanov [11], four types of subjective positions of students are identified, which can be considered not only as levels of manifestation of the position of a future professional, but also as certain factors of professional development:

1) the position of “*the subject of learning interactions*” (for this type, the main value is not the educational activity itself, but getting an adequate assessment);

2) the position of “*the subject of solving the problem*” (the student is looking for the right answer in a specific task, considering various options for its solution);

3) the position of the “subject of learning activity” (for this type, the key is the learning activity itself, and all tasks are perceived by the student in the context of the learning discipline);

4) the position of the “subject of professional education” (the student enters into educational interaction when it becomes possible for him to understand the meaning of educational tasks in order to master professional activity, when the position of the actual subject of professional activity begins to form).

We propose to consider the subject position of the mentee not as a static education, but as a dynamic process of personality transformation that takes place in joint activities with the mentor, characterizing the increasing measure of her authorship, initiative and responsibility both in professional activities and in social life.

S. I. Pozdeeva points out that “the traditional practice of mentoring does not fulfill its functions, i.e. it does not form the subject position of a specialist in its development and does not consolidate it in the profession” [12, p.87]. The author points out that the effect of this approach may be the opposite — mentoring may be ineffective: imitative or formal, with a predominance of authoritarianism, the formation of a novice's executive position to the detriment of independence and initiative, or even lead to the departure of the mentee not only from the enterprise, but from the profession.

However, we would like to offer a slightly different perspective. It seems to us that the mentor's activity, in any case, forms a certain subjective position of the mentee. But often not the one that we (or our management) would like to see.

Empirically, we have identified four types of the mentee's subject position, which can be formed under the influence of the mentor's activity strategy. The starting point is the type of relationship between the ward and the mentor, as well as the nature of the experience (knowledge, skills, competencies) that the mentor helps the mentee to appropriate and transform. The logic of appropriation and transformation of this experience served as the basis for our typology.

1. *Protest Type*. The mentee does not accept the mentor's demands, ignores requests, rules, and refuses to act according to the pattern.

2. *Imitative Type*. The mentee fully appropriates the mentor's modus operandi and tries to perform the necessary operations exclusively as he was trained by the mentor.

3. *Adaptive Type*. The mentee complements, refines, adapts the mentor's way of acting for himself, tries to make it more convenient for him to work.

4. *Inventive Type*. The mentee produces, invents his own way of doing something completely different from what the mentor conveyed, but productive.

Thus, we believe that the type of emerging subjective position of a mentor is not an accident, but the result of mentoring activities mediated by the mentor's strategy. What kind of strategies are these?

For example, Zerchaninova T. E., Tarbeeva I. S. [13], based on the Gatfield T. [14] model, in their work on the role of a supervisor in the scientific and educational activities of a graduate student, indicate that the success of such mentoring depends on the nature (style, form) of interaction between the supervisor and the graduate student. As components of such an interaction, the authors took control (structure/supervision) and support from a mentor and described a matrix of scientific leadership styles.: Pastoral, Contractual, Directional, Laisses-faire. (13, p. 140). However, another phrase of the authors attracted our attention: "Scientific leadership styles are ineffective only if they do not meet the needs and expectations of the supervisor and graduate student [13, p. 149].

Thus, it turns out that in order to achieve a certain result, a mentor must not only understand his interests, motives, attitudes, goals and results in the implementation of mentoring activities, but also correlate them (that is, represent them) with the interests, motives, attitudes and goals from the mentoring process of his mentor. That is, when considering the result of mentoring activities, we must proceed from a peculiar idea of the "intersection" of the interests, motives, attitudes, goals and results of the mentor and the mentee. Theoretical reflections have led us to the idea that a mentor in his activity must inevitably implement a certain type of goal-setting and behavior, determined by the development of his ideas about the results of mentoring activities for himself and for the mentee, which can manifest itself in four types (strategies): "*The Formalist*", "*The Dictator*", "*The Conniver*", "*The Strategist*" (see "Fig. 1").

1. “*The Formalist*” is, in our opinion, the most destructive strategy that can be formed by a mentor who does not have a clear understanding of both his activities as a novice’s assistant in production and his ideas about what the mentee can or should receive as a result of mentoring. In a way, we can even say that a mentor with such a strategy is not fulfilling his function, is out of place. As a result, the mentoring process is carried out in an unorganized, chaotic, aimless manner, and the mentee does not receive not only the necessary production skills, but also an understanding of the essence and meaning of the activity being mastered and his prospects at the enterprise. And it is difficult to call the mentor himself a real subject of mentoring activity.

2. “*The Conniver*” is a strategy in which the mentor tries to follow the mentee to a greater extent, goes along with him, strives to avoid or avoid awkward situations, conflicts, forgetting about the final goals. Here, as it were, the mentor and the mentee switch places. Bottom line: mentoring is messy, and the mentee gets only those skills that he considers most necessary for himself.

Fig. 1. Mentoring strategies

3. “*The Dictator*” is the opposite strategy to “*The Conniver*.” In this case, the mentor requires the mentee to follow “himself” as much as possible, according to the prescribed requirements and training schemes, presenting himself as an

authoritative specialist. In most cases, the mentor does not bother to ask himself what results the mentee wants to achieve, which he does not understand, causes difficulties or interest.

4. We see “*The Strategist*” as the most effective way for a mentor to behave in collaboration with the mentee. In this case, the mentor tries his best to take into account and compare his ideas about the results of mentoring activities with the ideas of the mentee. With this approach, the most positive and professional relationships are formed.

To test our strategy model, we conducted an empirical study. The respondents were mentors of the Moscow Metro State Unitary Enterprise. With the help of a questionnaire developed with the involvement of experts (heads of the organization) based on the ideas of the semantic differential, a list of 40 bipolar markers was formed. The respondents rated the mentor’s image according to each marker on a seven-point scale (encoded as from -3 to $+3$). A total of 90 employees aged 21 to 65 (51 men, 39 women) participated in the test survey.

During the analysis of the collected responses, the data was previously cleared: empty responses and other uninformative marks were encoded as “0”. The reliability and suitability of the matrix for factor analysis were verified (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin = 0.78; Bartlett’s test of sphericity: $\chi^2 = 1248.3$, $df = 780$, $p < 0.001$), which confirmed the adequacy of the data for latent structure extraction.

Based on the correlation matrix, an exploratory factorization (EFA) was performed with a fixed number of factors = 6; orthogonal (Varimax) and oblique (Promax) rotations were used for interpretation. To assess the stability of downloads, a bootstrap was performed (1000 replications): The standard error and 95% confidence interval are calculated for each download. The variable was considered to be stably associated with the factor at $|loading| \geq 0.40$ and CI not including “0”. Based on the results of the analysis, six groups of factors were identified, combining 40 markers.

Group 1 — Professional competence: capable, qualified, competent, educated, knowledgeable, skilled, experienced, efficient, prepared, smart.

Group 2 — Personal qualities: active, confident, proactive, purposeful, caring, adventurous, efficient, successful.

Group 3 — Communicative and social qualities: humane, sociable, helpful, attentive, interested, respected, selfless, helpful, noisy.

Group 4 — Creative and innovative qualities: creative, innovator, risk taker, developing, problem solver.

Group 5 — Organizational and volitional qualities: responsible, tough, guiding, leader, careerist.

Group 6 — Social status: recognized, in-demand, highly paid.

Next, we moved on to the second stage of verification. Based on standardized factor scores (z), a cluster analysis (Ward + K means) was performed for each

respondent, as a result of which four profile groups of mentors were identified: “*The Strategist*”, “*The Formalist*”, “*The Conniver*” and “*The Dictator*”.

Welch ANOVA and Games Howell post hoc checks showed statistically significant differences between the groups in key factors: group 1 “Professional competence”: $W = 12.37$, $p < 0.001$; group 3 “Communicative and social qualities”: $W = 18.05$, $p < 0.001$; group 4 — “Creative and innovative qualities”: $W = 14.22$, $p < 0.001$; group 5 — “Organizational and volitional qualities”: $W = 20.81$, $p < 0.001$ and group 6 — “Social status”: $W = 6.12$, $p = 0.001$.

Specific paired contrasts (Howell Games) confirmed the expected profiles. Thus, “*The Strategist*” significantly surpasses other groups in terms of “Creative and innovative qualities” ($p < 0.001$). “*The Conniver*” has the highest values for “Communicative and social qualities” and the lowest values for “Organizational strong-willed” ($p < 0.001$). “*The Dictator*” showed the highest indicators in terms of “Organizational and volitional qualities” ($p < 0.001$). “*The Formalist*” showed increased indicators of “Social status” ($p = 0.001$). Sixteen respondents had mixed characteristics and were classified as “borderline” or “mixed.” This seems quite natural, as not all individuals fit neatly into a single category; it likely reflects the existence of transitional or combined mentoring strategies.

Thus, our research has confirmed the theoretical justification put forward by us for the existence of four strategic behaviors of mentors: “Formalist”, “Conniver”, “Dictator” and “Strategist”. The empirical factors obtained fit seamlessly into the functional model of mentoring proposed in the scientific literature. And the highlighted constructs reflect the key resources through which the mentor implements motivational, educational, consulting and self-educational roles. At the same time, the cluster structure confirms that different profile types of mentors emphasize different sets of functions (for example, “Strategists” are focused on innovation and professionalism, and “Connivers” are focused on providing support to their mentors). The presence of a group of “mixed” respondents indicates the existence of transitional or combined mentoring strategies, which seems natural for the applied sample of employees of the enterprise.

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成熟人格的韧性作为发展战略能力的价值资源框架
**THE HARDINESS OF A MATURING PERSONALITY
AS A VALUE-RESOURCE FRAMEWORK FOR DEVELOPING
STRATEGIC COMPETENCE**

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摘要：本文论证了将心理韧性视为学生策略能力发展的重要价值资源基础的必要性。文章指出，当前高等教育教学领域在这一领域的研究进展不足。作者强调了心理韧性的多维性（包括参与度、控制感、风险接受度、关联性和文化背景），并指出“控制感”（即掌控环境的愿望）与“风险接受度”（即在不确定性下采取行动的意愿）之间存在矛盾，这种矛盾在学生阶段尤为突出。现有关于风险和不确定性条件下人类认知的研究表明，考试压力会选择性地干扰工作记忆（学生学习的认知基础）的功能。研究表明，心理韧性如同“认知盾牌”，能够在压力下保护记忆功能，否则策略能力将仅仅停留在陈述层面。作者强调，连接韧性和策略能力的关键机制在于学生进行“反思性停顿”的能力，这种能力有助于将自动反应转化为有意识的理性行动。文章总结认为，策略能力被视为韧性的元调节器，赋予韧性以方向性和意义性，而韧性则确保在不确定条件下实现策略能力。

关键词：策略能力，韧性，价值论方法。

Abstract. *The article substantiates the necessity of considering psychological hardiness as a value-resource foundation for the development of students' strategic competence. It is noted that contemporary research is marked by a shortage of new developments in this area for higher education pedagogy. The author highlights the multidimensional nature of psychological hardiness (involvement, control, risk acceptance, relatedness, culture) and identifies a contradiction between 'control' as the aspiration to manage circumstances and 'risk acceptance' as the readiness to act under uncertainty, a contradiction that intensifies during the student years. The reliance on extant research concerning human cognition under conditions of risk and uncertainty has demonstrated that examination stress selectively disrupts the functioning of working memory — the cognitive basis of student learning. It has been demonstrated that hardiness serves as a 'cognitive shield,' preserving memory functionality under stress, without which strategic competence*

remains merely declarative. The author highlights the idea that the key mechanism connecting hardiness and strategic competence is the student's ability to take a 'reflective pause,' which facilitates transforming automatic reactivity into conscious, rational action. The article concludes that strategic competence is construed as a meta-regulator of hardiness, imparting it with a directed and meaningful nature, whereas hardiness ensures the realization of strategic competence under conditions of uncertainty.

Keywords: *strategic competence, hardiness, axiological approach.*

Today, the developing personality encounters various extreme conditions—armed conflicts, natural disasters, social conflicts, and others. Crises during the maturation period are thus exacerbated by extreme situations, which negatively impact the individual's mental health. Therefore, hardiness must be regarded as a key component of psychological health and a value-resource basis for the development of the student's strategic competence. It should be noted that the hardiness of the maturing individual contributes to an improved quality of life and enhanced overall social adaptation.

With growing interest in this topic, we observe a lack of psychological research aimed at identifying specific factors that contribute to the development of hardiness in youth under extreme conditions.

The concept of 'hardiness,' unlike the concept of 'stress resistance,' is multi-dimensional and includes five elements— involvement, control, risk acceptance, connection, and culture. Recent research characterizes hardiness as a personality trait — measurable and developed in various environments and life circumstances: 'Often defined through endurance, resilience, and the capacity to withstand adversity steadfastly, individuals with a high level of hardiness demonstrate the ability to face challenges, control their environment, recover from setbacks, and maintain a sense of purpose and meaning even under difficult conditions' [2]. However, the current definition does not resolve the fundamental contradiction between "control" as the desire to manage circumstances and control the environment, and "risk acceptance" as the readiness to act under conditions of fundamental uncertainty. This contradiction becomes even more acute during the student age, when the maturing personality is compelled both to construct long-term plans and to adapt to unpredictable changes in educational and professional trajectories. We will also emphasize certain dependencies during this age range — financial and emotional — that underline the problem of the study. It is precisely this circumstance that makes hardiness a significant focus of pedagogical attention in higher education.

We believe that the solution to this issue lies within the very structure of strategic competence. If the hardiness of a developing individual can answer the question 'how to remain resilient under pressure from circumstances?', then strategic

competence provides answers to the question ‘how to construct an individual strategy for achieving results in the desired future?’. Strategic competence transforms ‘resistance to the pressure of circumstances’ into an active, value-conditioned transformation of the situation. A student consciously oriented toward the development of strategic competence not only accepts the academic challenge—but deliberately redefines it as a meaningful stage of growth, selects behavioral strategies, and determines their type of personal position in order to maintain a long-term perspective even during temporary difficulties. It is worth noting that R. Horwort [1] already wrote about types of personal positions in relation to the development of strategic thinking. In R. Harworth’s work, positions such as ‘leader,’ ‘contender,’ and ‘observer’ are distinguished [1, p. 73], with corresponding strategies assigned to each. For example, regarding the ‘leader’ position, R. Harworth described the thinking process as follows: ‘When a new contender enters the leader’s market, there is a temptation either to respond immediately with a barrage of tactical actions or to completely ignore the new player.’ However, before adopting either approach, it is necessary to conduct a thoughtful evaluation of the new participant, which will provide a range of options for strategically managing the situation’ [1, pp. 73-74]. Expanding on the author’s idea in the context of resilience in a maturing personality, we affirm that this logic can also be applied to coping with extreme situations and internal and external challenges encountered by the student. If in R. Khorworth’s response strategy the “new participant” is a competitor threatening the leader’s position in the market, then, in its pedagogical projection, the “new participant” comprises both external and internal challenges. External challenges may include examination stress, heavy academic workload, relocation, and others. There exists a number of psychological studies on examination/test stress that explicitly indicate that individuals with high levels of test anxiety exhibit working memory deficits under conditions of high cognitive load. Conversely, regarding the importance of working memory in the learning process, the authors state: “As a central cognitive system responsible for the temporary storage and processing of information, working memory integrates incoming signals from sensory memory, coordinates the allocation of attention, and provides critical informational support for carrying out complex cognitive tasks, thereby serving as a fundamental foundation for higher cognitive functions, including learning, reasoning, and problem-solving.” Its capacity and functional effectiveness directly modulate an individual’s cognitive efficiency and learning outcomes” [3]. Thus, conceptualizing working memory as the cognitive foundation of educational activity in the maturing individual is directly aligned with the logic of our study, since exam stress and test anxiety selectively impair working memory functioning, and this situation is exacerbated under conditions of high cognitive load and extreme circumstances. This means that even with a developed strategic competence, the implementation of a well-thought-out system of actions will be

cognitively blocked if the student does not possess a high level of hardiness. Thus, hardiness acts as a ‘cognitive shield’ that preserves the functionality of working memory under stressful conditions, without which strategic competence remains declarative.

Internal challenges include — doubts about one’s abilities, fear of failure, value and meaning conflicts, and others. Hardiness requires from the student a well-developed ability to sustain the pause between the stimulus (challenge) and their reaction—this is precisely the “thoughtful evaluation” that R. Harcourt highlights [1, p. 74]. It is precisely this ability to engage in a reflexive pause, transforming automatic reactivity (what R. Harcourt refers to as a “barrage of tactical actions”) or defensive avoidance (“ignoring”) into a conscious, value-driven action that, in our view, constitutes the core of the hardiness of the maturing personality. Moreover, this very ability acts as the logical link between hardiness and strategic competence: the latter equips the student with tools for a ‘thoughtful evaluation’ and trajectory planning, while the former provides the resources necessary to conduct this evaluation even under extreme conditions. This may sound paradoxical, but hardiness begins not with active behavior, but with a reflective pause. This is precisely the ‘thoughtful evaluation’ that a maturing individual needs to a greater extent.

Thus, the strategic competence of the maturing individual serves as a meta-regulator with respect to hardiness: it is precisely strategic competence that endows hardiness with a directed, meaningful, and reflexive nature. Without strategic competence, there is a significant risk for hardiness to become ‘endurance as an end in itself, unmediated by strategic goal-setting.’ In the absence of hardiness, students’ strategic competence remains declarative goal-setting, incapable of being realized under extreme conditions, as well as conditions of instability and uncertainty.

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青少年数字情绪调节：认知控制和情商的作用
**DIGITAL EMOTION REGULATION IN YOUTH:
THE ROLE OF COGNITIVE CONTROL
AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE**

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摘要：在快速数字化的背景下，年轻人越来越依赖数字工具来调节自身情绪状态，这种现象被称为数字情绪调节（DER）。经验表明，习惯性、不加反思地使用数字情绪调节与情绪传染、网络行为失控、回避型应对以及情绪不稳定性加剧密切相关。本文借鉴情绪调节过程模型、人际协同调节理论和情感计算理论，提出了一个三层理论框架：（1）反应性失调；（2）通过数字工具进行主动性自我调节；（3）交互式协同调节，其中数字环境或人工智能代理能够动态地与用户的情绪状态保持一致。我们认为，认知控制和情商是影响情绪调节层级变化的双重调节因素。本文概述了数字情绪调节的过程模型，并探讨了其对教育干预和以人为本的数字设计的影响。

关键词：数字情绪调节，协同调节，认知控制，情商，青少年，情感计算，过程模型。

Abstract. *In the context of rapid digitalization, young people increasingly rely on digital tools to regulate their emotional states, a phenomenon termed digital emotion regulation (DER). Habitual, unreflective use of DER is empirically associated with emotional contagion, online disinhibition, avoidance coping, and heightened affective instability. Drawing on the process model of emotion regulation, interpersonal coregulation theory, and affective computing, this paper proposes a three-level theoretical framework: (1) reactive dysregulation, (2) proactive self-regulation via digital tools, and (3) interactive coregulation, in which a digital environment or AI agent dynamically aligns with the user's affective state. We argue that cognitive control and emotional intelligence serve as dual moderators of progression through these levels. A process model of digital emotion regulation is outlined, and implications for educational interventions and human-centered digital design are discussed.*

Keywords: *digital emotion regulation, coregulation, cognitive control, emotional intelligence, youth, affective computing, process model.*

1. Introduction and Problem Statement

Contemporary youth, broadly defined as individuals aged 14-25, spend an estimated six to nine hours per day engaging with digital media. This figure has grown steadily since the widespread adoption of smartphones and social networking platforms [1]. Within these digital environments, emotionally salient stimuli are omnipresent. These include social comparison cues, algorithmically amplified negative content, peer feedback loops, and entertainment-driven emotional arousal. To manage the emotional demands of digital life, young people spontaneously employ a diverse set of coping strategies, such as listening to music, scrolling feeds, sending memes, blocking notifications, or retreating from online interactions. Wadley et al. [2] formalized this cluster of behaviors under the construct of digital emotion regulation (DER), defining it as the use of digital technologies to initiate, modulate, or terminate emotional states.

However, accumulating empirical evidence indicates that habitual and unreflective DER frequently produces the opposite of its intended effect. Four phenomena are particularly well-documented. First, emotional contagion: exposure to negatively valenced social-media content can rapidly propagate negative affect across users at scale [3]. Second, online disinhibition: the relative anonymity and reduced non-verbal cues of digital communication lower inhibitory thresholds, promoting impulsive, dysregulated communicative behavior [4]. Third, avoidance coping: digital distraction as an emotion-regulation strategy is associated with short-term relief but long-term increases in anxiety and decreased psychological well-being [5]. Fourth, technostress: chronic exposure to digital demands and perpetual connectivity is associated with measurable reductions in psychological well-being and productive functioning [6].

A core mechanism underlying these failures is insufficient metacognitive awareness. Young people generally lack explicit knowledge of how digital environments shape their emotional trajectories and when their self-regulatory strategies are maladaptive [7]. A particularly instructive case is video-mediated communication. Bailenson [8] demonstrated that the continuous processing of non-verbal cues in video calls imposes a form of nonverbal overload. This cognitive burden has no direct analogue in face-to-face interaction and systematically depletes the attentional resources available for emotion regulation. Compounding this, the dominant design logic of digital platforms optimizes for engagement rather than adaptive regulation. This creates a regulatory gap between the escalating affective demands of digital life and the capacities of adolescents and emerging adults, whose prefrontal regulatory systems remain neurobiologically immature until the mid-twenties [9].

Despite growing interest in digital emotion regulation, existing approaches remain largely intrapersonal and do not account for the hybrid nature of digital environments, where regulation unfolds within human–technology systems. The

present paper addresses this gap by proposing a three-level theoretical framework of DER: (1) reactive dysregulation, (2) proactive self-regulation, and (3) interactive coregulation. We argue that cognitive control and emotional intelligence function as dual moderators governing transitions between these levels. This paper makes three specific contributions: it reconceptualizes DER as a continuum from internal to distributed regulation, introduces key psychological moderators of regulatory transitions, and extends coregulation theory to human–technology interaction through a process model of underlying mechanisms.

2. Theoretical Framework: From Dysregulation to Coregulation

The framework integrates the process model of emotion regulation [10, 11] with interpersonal coregulation theory [12]. Gross treats emotion regulation as a sequence of five stages: situation selection, situation modification, attentional deployment, cognitive change, and response modulation [11]. Zaki and Williams [12] extended this model to dyadic contexts, showing that emotion regulation is often co-constructed through interaction. We apply this logic to the human-technology dyad in digital environments. On this basis, we identify three levels of DER:

Level 1. Reactive Dysregulation. The user responds passively to digital stimuli. Cognitive control is insufficient to override automatic appraisal [13], and low emotional intelligence prevents accurate identification of affective states [14]. Digital tools often amplify emotional arousal, leading to contagion or impulsivity.

Level 2. Proactive Self-Regulation. The user intentionally deploys strategies, such as curating playlists or setting screen-time limits, based on reflective goals. Executing these strategies against competing impulses requires intact cognitive control [13] and emotional intelligence [14]. This level aligns with the concept of controlled emotion regulation described by Mauss et al. [15].

Level 3. Coregulation. The digital environment or AI agent adapts to the user's emotional state in real time. Examples include suggesting a break or adjusting interface affordances. Coregulation is bidirectional, where the user and system mutually influence each other [12]. This level requires affective computing capabilities to recognize and interpret human emotions [16]. Recent advances in multimodal affect detection [17] make such interfaces technically feasible.

3. Key Mechanisms and the Role of Cognitive Control and Emotional Intelligence

We theoretically identify three psychological mechanisms underlying the progression toward coregulation (Table 1).

Attentional disengagement is dependent on the shifting component of executive function [18], specifically the ability to redirect attention from one stimulus to another. Users with low control remain captured by salient negative content, which is consistent with attentional bias research [20]. Appraisal support involves providing alternative interpretations of stimuli, a computational analogue of cognitive

reappraisal [11]. Inhibitory control is required to modulate automatic appraisals and entertain alternative framings [13]. Response modulation refers to system-initiated prompts. Such nudges rely on the user's capacity for willed control of behavior, what Norman and Shallice [19] termed the Supervisory Attentional System (SAS), to override impulsive tendencies.

Table 1. Psychological mechanisms of digital coregulation and their moderators.

Mechanism	Definition	Link to Cognitive Control	Link to Emotional Intelligence
Attentional disengagement	Redirecting attention away from overwhelming digital content	High cognitive control enables attentional shifting [18]	EI identifies when disengagement is adaptive
Appraisal support	System offers alternative readings of stimuli	Inhibitory control modulates initial negative appraisal [13]	EI facilitates accurate emotional labelling
Response modulation	System prompts adaptive behavioral response (e.g., delay sending)	Willed control (SAS) overrides automatic responses [19]; inhibitory control sustains compliance [13]	EI supports selection of contextually appropriate strategy [4]

4. A Process Model of Digital Emotion Regulation in Youth

Synthesizing existing frameworks [2, 11], we propose a five-stage process model:

- **Stage 1 (Trigger):** An emotionally salient event occurs within the digital environment. Examples include negative social-comparison posts, offensive comments, or rewarding peer validation. Both positive and negative extremes carry regulatory demands.

- **Stage 2 (Awareness):** The user registers an emotional shift. This stage is mediated by emotional intelligence, specifically the perceiving-emotions component [14]. Low EI may lead to a failure to notice the shift, disrupting subsequent regulation.

- **Stage 3 (Strategy Selection):** The user selects a strategy either habitually or reflectively. Three paths are available:

- **3.1. Dysregulation path:** passive scrolling, emotional venting, or digital avoidance. These strategies are associated with long-term affective instability [5].

- **3.2. Self-regulation path:** deliberate use of digital tools, such as curating playlists or silencing notifications. This requires intact cognitive control and sufficient EI [2].

◦ **3.3. Coregulation path:** system-initiated adaptation to the user's affective state. This requires adequate and ethical affective sensing [16, 17] and productive user responses.

• **Stage 4 (Implementation):** The strategy is executed. Successful implementation requires cognitive control to sustain goal-directed action against competing impulses [13].

• **Stage 5 (Monitoring and Feedback):** The user evaluates the emotional change. For individuals with low cognitive control, coregulation functions as an external scaffold, reducing regulatory burden through cognitive offloading [22].

The model predicts that coregulation is optimal when cognitive control is at least moderate. Conversely, for individuals with low cognitive control, the system compensates for limited endogenous capacity, functioning as a form of cognitive offloading in affective regulation.

5. Conclusion and Implications

This paper proposed a theoretical framework and a process model specifying how cognitive control and emotional intelligence jointly determine regulatory outcomes. Several conclusions follow. Dysregulation is a predictable result of the mismatch between user capacities and the design logic of engagement-optimized platforms [5]. The transition toward coregulation requires the cultivation of user cognitive-emotional skills [18, 21] and the integration of coregulatory affordances into digital environments [16, 17].

Practical implications span education, design, and research. In education, curricula should prioritize digital emotion regulation literacy to help students recognize how digital environments influence their affect. From a design perspective, developers should integrate coregulatory features, such as emotion-aware nudges, as standard platform components. Finally, the proposed process model requires empirical validation across different age groups and cultural contexts within digitally integrated societies.

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二元制教育背景下学生动机因素的动态变化
**DYNAMICS OF THE MOTIVATIONAL COMPONENT
OF STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF DUAL EDUCATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了当前与提升专业人才在劳动力市场竞争力相关的问题；概述了二元制教育模式在专业人才培养方面的优势；综合分析了培养当代生产环境下所需专业人才所必需的职业能力要素（动机、认知、研究、组织和管理能力）；并展示了二元制教育模式下学生动机要素的动态变化。

关键词：职业竞争力；劳动力市场；二元制教育模式；职业能力；动机要素。

Abstract. *This paper examines current issues related to enhancing the competitiveness of specialists in the labor market; the advantages of the dual education model for specialist training are outlined; the components of professional competence (motivational, cognitive, research, organizational and managerial), essential for preparing an in-demand specialist in the contemporary production environment, are synthesized; The results reflecting the dynamics of the motivational component of students studying under the conditions of dual education are presented.*

Keywords: *professional competitiveness; labor market; dual education model; professional competence; motivational component.*

Dual education is increasingly entering the practice of specialist training. Competitiveness in professional activity becomes the general guideline in the development of an individual as a specialist [1]. The modern labor market imposes a number of requirements on specialists, among which the possession of professional experience and minimal adaptation costs for employees at enterprises are prioritized. These requirements can be successfully fulfilled through the implementation of a dual training model for students at universities, namely under conditions of

simultaneous theoretical learning in the classroom and practical skills development at enterprises [2].

The incorporation of a professional growth trajectory within the educational process, implemented according to the dual model, not only promotes the formation of sustainable professional motivation among students but also ensures the practical focus of education. The degree of competency acquisition by students directly correlates with their capability to execute production tasks at the respective stages of career progression, which ultimately enhances graduates' readiness for professional activity and reduces the risks of personnel turnover.

We employ a comprehensive approach implemented through a system of qualification examinations, which facilitates the development of the motivational, cognitive, research, and organizational-managerial components of professional competence required for preparing a competitive specialist within the framework of the modern production environment.

In examining the process of training specialists within the framework of dual education, it can be asserted that the implementation of the developed professional growth trajectory entails the phased development of students' professional competencies. Correspondingly, this process is accompanied by subsequent validation of their competencies through qualification assessments conducted at partner enterprises.

The effectiveness of specialist training within the dual system of professional-pedagogical education was investigated experimentally at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of the Belarusian National Technical University (BNTU) in Minsk.

The motivational component is analyzed through the following parameters: 1) motivation to achieve success / avoid failure; 2) motivation for educational activities; 3) level of professional satisfaction.

The cognitive component includes the following parameters: 1) mastery of knowledge in professional activities; 2) independence in acquiring knowledge; 3) activity in acquiring knowledge.

The organizational-managerial component is studied through the following parameters: 1) leadership potential; 2) communicative qualities; 3) organizational qualities; 4) volitional qualities.

The research component is characterized by the following parameters: 1) the level of participation in scientific-practical conferences; 2) the degree to which rationalization proposal projects are focused on solving production tasks.

The experimental group (EG) comprised 62 students specializing in 'Engineering and Pedagogical Activity (Mechanical Engineering),' who were educated according to an enhanced dual model involving partner enterprises (the Polytechnic Plant, MTZ-HOLDING Holding (OJSC Minsk Tractor Plant 'MTZ')). The control group (CG), consisting of 58 individuals, received training through the traditional

program without active engagement of industrial resources and without an expanded mentorship system.

To confirm the hypothesis, it is necessary to identify statistically significant differences in the data between the control and experimental groups. In other words, the progress observed in the experimental group should be substantially greater than that in the control group, even if positive dynamics are also evident in the latter.

It is important to note that the traditional training system in the control group, despite the absence of dual education, nevertheless ensured the formation of key professional competencies; adaptation to the contemporary requirements of the enterprise; development of communicative skills; enhancement of achievement motivation.

Consequently, we consider that some increase in indicators within the control group will be apparent; however, this renders the comparative analysis particularly significant, as it demonstrates the efficacy of our methodology.

On the basis of the established criteria, we analyzed the dynamics of changes in both the experimental and control groups.

The experimental verification of the dual model for specialist training confirmed the validity of the initial hypotheses, demonstrating the practical significance and effectiveness of the proposed methodological modifications.

At the control stage of the experiment, an assessment of the effectiveness of the developed and implemented model for training specialists within the dual system of professional-pedagogical education was carried out using surveys, online testing, and the methodology “Determination of Personality Orientation towards Success Achievement/Failure Avoidance” (A. A. Rean) [3]; the methodology “Study of Learning Motivation in Higher Education” (T. I. Ilyina) [4]; the methodology “Degree of Job Satisfaction” (V. A. Yadov) (modified by N. V. Kuzmina, A. A. Rean) [5].

Let us examine in more detail the motivational component of students’ professional competence.

Three methodologies ensuring the reliability of the data were used for evaluation. The methodology by T. I. Ilyina, “Studying Motivation for Learning in Higher Education,” made it possible to identify students’ primary motives. The test developed by A. A. Rean, “Determining the Personality Orientation toward Success Achievement/Avoidance of Failure,” measured the orientation toward success or avoidance of failure, which is associated with students’ psychological resilience in the learning environment. The questionnaire by V. A. Yadova’s ‘Degree of Satisfaction with Profession’ evaluated the emotional engagement with the chosen specialty, which is critical for long-term motivation. All methods were applied during the control experiment (July 2025) for both groups, ensuring the comparability of the results.

A comparative analysis of the results from the control and experimental groups reveals significant differences in the structure of students’ motivation.

The analysis of the obtained data indicates that pragmatic motivation remains at an equal level in both groups (80%), reflecting a similar aspiration to obtain the diploma. However, learning motivation in the experimental group exceeds the control group's levels by 10 percentage points.

The most significant differences were observed in the domain of professional motivation. In the experimental group, this indicator reached 75%, which is 15 percentage points higher than in the control group. This substantial increase is directly associated with students' immersion in a real professional environment within the framework of the dual education model.

Notably, the dynamics of achievement motivation indicators show that in the experimental group, the aspiration for success increased to 70%, while the tendency to avoid failure decreased to 30%. This indicates the development of more constructive behavioral strategies among students enrolled in the dual education model.

Satisfaction with the chosen profession in the experimental group amounted to 84.5%, exceeding the control group's level by 5.5 percentage points. This fact confirms the positive impact of the practice-oriented approach on students' professional self-determination.

The results obtained demonstrate a significant strengthening of intrinsic motivation and professional engagement among students in the experimental group. The dual education model contributes to the development of a stable professional orientation and enhances satisfaction with the selected specialty.

The dual education model creates favorable conditions for the development of students' professional motivation through direct immersion in the work environment. Practical activities in enterprises enable students to observe real prospects for career advancement, thereby enhancing their commitment to professional development.

The availability of mentors from among experienced enterprise specialists contributes to the formation of a positive image of the profession. Students have the opportunity to acquire not only professional knowledge and skills but also value-based orientations characteristic of successful representatives of the chosen specialty.

The analysis conducted of the motivational component confirms the effectiveness of the dual education model in shaping a stable professional orientation within the personalities of future specialists. Systematic interaction with the production environment stimulates the development of intrinsic motivation to master the profession and build a successful career.

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在全球文化交流背景下，古筝音乐的创新与转型
**INNOVATION AND TRANSFORMATION OF GUZHENG MUSIC
IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL CULTURAL EXCHANGE**

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摘要：在全球文化交流日益频繁的背景下，古筝音乐正经历着显著的艺术创新、媒介转型和跨文化重新诠释的过程。本文探讨了古筝作为中国传统音乐的代表性乐器之一，如何在适应当代国际语境的同时，保持其文化特性。研究结合文化分析、音乐学观察和比较诠释，旨在识别当代古筝实践转型的主要方向。文章重点关注曲目结构、演奏技巧、教育传播、跨学科合作和数字传播等方面的变化。文章认为，古筝音乐的全球化并不必然导致传统的消亡；相反，它可能促进演奏语言的更新，丰富跨文化对话，并强化古筝作为中国文化记忆载体的作用。同时，文章强调，可持续的创新需要在创造性的实验与风格、美学和历史基础的传承之间取得平衡。研究结果对从事中国音乐遗产国际推广的传统音乐研究者、教育工作者、表演者以及文化机构具有参考价值。

关键词：古筝，中国传统音乐，文化交流，音乐创新，转型，全球化，遗产保护。

Abstract. *Against the background of intensified global cultural exchange, guzheng music is undergoing a visible process of artistic innovation, media transformation, and cross-cultural reinterpretation. This article examines how the guzheng, as one of the representative instruments of Chinese traditional music, preserves its cultural identity while adapting to contemporary international contexts. The study combines cultural analysis, musicological observation, and comparative interpretation in order to identify the main directions of transformation in present-day guzheng practice. Particular attention is paid to changes in repertoire structure, performance techniques, educational dissemination, interdisciplinary collaboration, and digital communication. The article argues that the globalization of guzheng music does not necessarily lead to the erosion of tradition; on*

the contrary, it may stimulate the renewal of performance language, enrich intercultural dialogue, and strengthen the instrument's role as a bearer of Chinese cultural memory. At the same time, the paper stresses that sustainable innovation requires a balance between creative experimentation and the preservation of stylistic, aesthetic, and historical foundations. The findings may be useful for researchers of traditional music, educators, performers, and cultural institutions engaged in the international promotion of Chinese musical heritage.

Keywords: *guzheng, traditional Chinese music, cultural exchange, musical innovation, transformation, globalization, heritage preservation.*

1. Introduction

The guzheng is one of the most recognizable string instruments in Chinese musical culture. With a history extending over more than two millennia, it embodies not only a distinct sound world but also a layered system of aesthetic values, performance conventions, regional traditions, and symbolic meanings. In the twenty-first century, however, the cultural environment in which guzheng music exists has changed substantially. Global mobility, digital media, transnational education, and the expansion of world music markets have created new conditions for the circulation of Chinese traditional music [2]. As a result, the guzheng is increasingly heard not only in conservatories and concert halls in China, but also in overseas classrooms, intercultural festivals, online platforms, collaborative projects, and experimental stages.

These developments raise an important scholarly question: how does guzheng music transform when it enters the field of global cultural exchange? The issue is not limited to simple geographic expansion. It concerns changes in repertoire, new forms of notation and presentation, modified performance techniques, intercultural cooperation, and altered systems of audience perception. In global contexts, the guzheng becomes both a traditional instrument and a contemporary cultural mediator. It carries historical memory while simultaneously participating in modern artistic production [3].

The purpose of this article is to analyze the innovation and transformation of guzheng music under conditions of global cultural exchange. The study seeks to identify the principal mechanisms of this process, to clarify its cultural and artistic consequences, and to demonstrate that productive transformation depends on the preservation of internal aesthetic logic. The article is based on analytical interpretation of scholarly literature, observations of contemporary performance trends, and comparative examination of traditional and modern guzheng practice.

2. Theoretical Foundations of Guzheng Transformation

The transformation of traditional music under globalization can be understood through several complementary perspectives. From the standpoint of cultural studies, globalization is not merely homogenization; it is also a dynamic field of

translation, adaptation, resistance, and selective borrowing. Traditional art forms often survive not by remaining unchanged, but by entering new social contexts while preserving their core semantic structures [3]. In this respect, guzheng music offers a useful case for studying how local cultural forms achieve international visibility without losing their cultural specificity.

From a musicological perspective, innovation in instrumental tradition usually occurs in at least three interconnected domains: sound production, repertoire construction, and performance context [1]. Sound production changes when performers expand techniques, timbral possibilities, or amplification methods. Repertoire changes when composers combine established idioms with modern harmonic language, cinematic textures, jazz elements, or electronic sound design. Performance context changes when music leaves ritual, pedagogical, or nationally coded settings and enters transnational spaces where audiences may not share the same cultural references. Each of these domains is highly relevant to contemporary guzheng practice.

At the same time, discussions of innovation in traditional music must address the problem of authenticity. Authenticity should not be reduced to mechanical repetition of past models. In artistic practice, authenticity is better understood as fidelity to an aesthetic worldview, performance logic, and cultural sensibility [6]. Therefore, the modernization of guzheng music can be considered legitimate when innovation grows out of the instrument's own expressive resources rather than replacing them with externally imposed effects.

3. Main Directions of Innovation in Contemporary Guzheng Music

One of the most significant directions of innovation is the expansion of the guzheng repertoire. Traditional pieces rooted in regional schools, narrative imagery, and pentatonic organization remain central to pedagogy and concert life. Yet modern composers increasingly write works that integrate the guzheng into chamber ensembles, orchestral textures, film scores, and intercultural performance settings [7]. In such works, the instrument is no longer treated only as a marker of historical Chineseness; it functions as an active participant in modern compositional discourse. This change broadens the semantic range of the instrument and attracts listeners unfamiliar with traditional repertoire.

A second direction concerns technique. Contemporary performers use extended methods such as percussive tapping on the soundboard, unconventional plucking patterns, glissando clusters, and combinations of traditional right-hand articulation with left-hand coloristic effects. These techniques enrich the expressive capacity of the instrument and help it interact with modern ensemble practice. Importantly, many of these innovations remain rooted in established guzheng gestures, such as vibrato, portamento, and ornamental nuance [5]. Rather than abandoning tradition, performers often magnify latent possibilities already present in the instrument.

A third direction is technological mediation. Recording technologies, microphones, sound processing, streaming platforms, and short-form video applications have changed the way guzheng music is produced and consumed. Digital circulation enables rapid international dissemination, but it also alters listening habits. Pieces are frequently selected, edited, or staged for visual appeal and algorithmic visibility. This creates both opportunities and risks. On the one hand, global audiences can encounter guzheng performance without institutional barriers. On the other hand, the reduction of music to fragmented visual content may weaken historical understanding and encourage superficial exoticization [8].

A fourth direction is interdisciplinary collaboration. The guzheng increasingly appears in projects that combine music with dance, theatre, digital art, poetry, and audiovisual installation. Such collaborations expand the communicative power of the instrument and position it within broader contemporary art discourse. They also make it easier to present guzheng music to multicultural audiences, since meaning is conveyed not only through sound but also through movement, imagery, and narrative framing.

4. Global Cultural Exchange and the Internationalization of the Guzheng

The internationalization of guzheng music is closely linked to educational and institutional exchange. Chinese conservatories, Confucius Institutes, overseas Chinese cultural centers, and independent music schools have all contributed to the teaching of the instrument beyond China. International students increasingly encounter the guzheng as part of broader interest in Asian music, intercultural performance, or heritage studies. This educational expansion has practical consequences: new teaching materials are developed, notation systems are adapted, bilingual explanations become more common, and online lessons make long-distance mentorship possible [8].

Global cultural exchange has also changed the social image of the guzheng. In earlier periods, the instrument was often presented to foreign audiences as a symbol of classical or national tradition. Today, it is equally likely to be framed as a flexible contemporary instrument capable of dialogue with jazz, new age music, popular music, experimental composition, and film media. This shift is significant because it moves the guzheng from a static representational function toward an interactive artistic role. Instead of serving merely as a cultural emblem, it becomes an agent of creative exchange [3].

Concert practice offers many examples of this transformation. Guzheng performers participate in intercultural festivals, university residencies, cross-border ensemble projects, and collaborative recordings. In these contexts, communication requires negotiation between different tuning systems, rhythmic expectations, improvisational habits, and audience competencies. Such encounters often generate hybrid forms. Some of them are highly successful because they respect the identities

of all participating traditions. Others remain superficial when the guzheng is used only as a decorative timbral sign. Therefore, intercultural success depends not on novelty alone, but on informed artistic dialogue [5].

It is also important to note that global exchange affects domestic practice within China. International recognition can stimulate renewed local interest, encourage curriculum reform, and motivate performers to study both regional styles and modern world music trends. Thus, the global journey of the guzheng does not move in a single direction outward; it also feeds back into the transformation of musical culture at home.

5. Challenges of Transformation: Between Preservation and Experiment

Despite its positive potential, the transformation of guzheng music under globalization is accompanied by several challenges. The first is stylistic dilution. When crossover production is driven primarily by market demand, there is a risk that the instrument's distinctive articulation, modal thinking, and narrative sensitivity will be replaced by generalized ambient textures. In that case, the guzheng may remain audible as a sound object but become detached from its cultural grammar [6].

The second challenge concerns pedagogy. Fast international dissemination sometimes encourages simplified teaching methods that privilege immediate performance over historical depth. Students may learn a small number of visually attractive pieces while lacking familiarity with regional schools, traditional aesthetics, and the philosophical background of Chinese music. Sustainable internationalization therefore requires more than performance training; it requires contextual education that includes history, terminology, listening practice, and interpretive reflection [7].

The third challenge is the imbalance between innovation and canon preservation. If institutions focus exclusively on new works and intercultural projects, the transmission of classical repertoire may weaken. Conversely, if institutions treat tradition as untouchable, young performers may perceive the instrument as culturally important but artistically limited. The most productive path lies between these extremes. Tradition should function as a living resource for innovation, while innovation should remain accountable to inherited standards of musical depth and expressive coherence.

A further challenge is representation. In global media environments, the guzheng is sometimes packaged through simplified images of Chinese culture intended for easy consumption. Such representation may increase visibility, but it can also reduce the richness of the instrument to stereotype. For this reason, performers and cultural mediators must pay attention not only to how the guzheng sounds, but also to how it is explained, staged, translated, and framed in public discourse [3].

6. Strategies for Sustainable Development of Guzheng Music

In order to promote sustainable innovation, several strategic directions can be proposed. First, contemporary composition for guzheng should be encouraged, but

such composition should be grounded in serious knowledge of traditional idiom. Collaboration between performers, composers, and scholars can help ensure that experimentation grows from the instrument's own structural and expressive possibilities.

Second, guzheng education should integrate performance training with cultural literacy. This means combining technique with study of repertoire history, regional schools, poetics of musical imagery, and comparative listening. In international settings, educational materials should be multilingual and should explain not only how to play, but also how to hear and interpret the music in relation to Chinese cultural concepts [4].

Third, digital dissemination should be used strategically rather than passively. Online platforms can be valuable spaces for archiving, teaching, outreach, and community formation. However, cultural institutions and performers should also create deeper forms of content, such as lecture-performances, documentary videos, annotated repertoire introductions, and interviews that reveal the inner logic of guzheng practice. Such formats can counterbalance the superficiality of algorithm-driven circulation.

Fourth, intercultural collaboration should be based on reciprocity. Successful artistic exchange requires time, dialogue, and mutual study. Projects that treat the guzheng as an equal partner in collaborative creation are more likely to produce durable artistic results than projects that use it as a decorative sign of cultural difference [2].

Finally, documentation and research should accompany performance development. Systematic study of changing repertoire, audience reception, teaching methods, and transnational performance practice will help preserve knowledge and support evidence-based policy in the field of traditional music development.

7. Conclusion

The innovation and transformation of guzheng music in the context of global cultural exchange reveal the vitality of traditional art in contemporary society. The guzheng is not a museum artifact fixed in the past; it is a living instrument capable of entering new artistic, educational, and technological environments. Its modernization can enrich both Chinese musical culture and international intercultural dialogue, provided that innovation remains connected to historical consciousness and aesthetic depth.

The study has shown that the transformation of guzheng music is expressed through expanded repertoire, technical experimentation, technological mediation, educational internationalization, and interdisciplinary collaboration. At the same time, these processes create risks of stylistic simplification, pedagogical reduction, and stereotyped representation. Therefore, the future of guzheng music depends on a balanced model in which preservation and innovation are not treated as opposites, but as mutually reinforcing principles.

In this sense, the global circulation of guzheng music should be viewed not as a threat to cultural identity, but as an opportunity to renew tradition through dialogue. When supported by scholarship, reflective pedagogy, and responsible artistic practice, the guzheng can continue to serve as both a symbol of Chinese heritage and a dynamic voice in the musical culture of the contemporary world.

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现代导师互动模式在教育学及其法律实施方面的探讨
**MODERN MODELS OF MENTORING INTERACTION
IN PEDAGOGY AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF THEIR
IMPLEMENTATION**

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摘要：本文基于指导互动的本质，对各种教学指导模式进行了分析和比较。文章描述了导师与学员互动的方式，并分析了传统指导、辅导、快速指导、标准指导和团队指导等指导模式的优缺点。此外，文章还探讨了在现代教育环境中实施指导的法律问题、指导的组织监管框架以及各种指导互动模式法律规范化的要求。

关键词：指导，指导模式，教学互动，导师，学员，法律法规，监管框架

Abstract. *This article presents an analysis and comparison of pedagogical mentoring models based on the nature of mentoring interactions. It describes approaches to mentor-mentee interactions, along with the advantages and disadvantages of such mentoring models as traditional mentoring, tutoring, flash mentoring, standard mentoring, and team mentoring. The article also examines the legal aspects of implementing mentoring in modern educational settings, the regulatory framework for its organization, and the requirements for the legal formalization of various mentoring interaction models.*

Keywords: *mentoring, mentoring models, pedagogical interaction, mentor, mentee, legal regulation, regulatory framework*

Mentoring young teachers and students — future teachers — is one of the key issues in modern education. Providing support from more experienced colleagues who understand the intricacies of entering the profession, grasp the challenges of overcoming the adaptation period when entering new professional conditions, possess personal experience in surmounting these difficulties, and master various mechanisms for interacting with newcomers during this challenging time — this is the primary task of mentoring.

Currently, extensive experience in pedagogical mentoring has been accumulated, allowing us to classify models and practices of mentoring activity [5]. It should be noted that a mentoring model reflects a particular approach to the interaction between a mentor and a mentee, while a mentoring practice reflects the implementation of a specific model in a particular organization.

There are numerous classifications of pedagogical mentoring models, distinguished based on various criteria. By implementation method, they include offline interactions, online interactions, virtual mentoring, and self-regulated mentoring. By direction of interaction, they encompass vertical, horizontal, and reverse models, as well as peer mentoring, collaborative, supportive, and developmental models. From a communicative perspective, they include the apprenticeship model, clone model, nurturing model, and friendship model. It is relevant to identify and describe the most commonly used pedagogical mentoring models, classified by the nature of mentoring interactions.

Materials and methods

The research methods are theoretical analysis and synthesis, comparison, classification.

Results and its discussion

Based on the nature of mentoring interactions, it is possible to distinguish traditional mentoring, tutoring, flash mentoring, standard mentoring, and the team model.

Traditional mentoring, which involves interactions between a mentor — an experienced specialist — and a mentee over a specified period (typically from two months to one year), aims to transmit traditions, rules, features of interactions within the educational organization, as well as professional experience and knowledge. The core idea of traditional mentoring is “do as I do”. In this model, the mentor shares experience, demonstrates correct methods of action, provides advice and ready-made solutions, monitors results, and helps correct mistakes; meanwhile, the mentee absorbs knowledge, replicates actions, learns through observation and practice, and thus occupies a learning position. This model assumes a high level of directiveness on the part of the mentor. Such an interaction model was typical even in the transmission of craft experience and gained wide adoption and success in Russia during the Soviet era across various fields (medicine, engineering, etc.),

including education. While traditional mentoring offers undeniable advantages — such as rapid and effective development of professional skills, a clear learning structure, and a low error rate in the mentee’s professional activities — it also has drawbacks: dependence on the mentor’s style and limited creativity due to the mentee’s low independence. Traditional mentoring is one of the most commonly implemented practices of pedagogical mentoring, for example, during students’ pedagogical practice [11], and in addressing the professional development challenges of young teachers in schools, colleges, and universities [1].

The tutoring model of mentoring involves more than simply transferring knowledge from a mentor (tutor) to a mentee; it helps the individual build a personalized educational trajectory based on their goals, interests, and characteristics. The tutor acts as a facilitator, helping define the mentee’s development goals by identifying (diagnosing) their interests and current level of development, planning actions, providing support, reflection, and assisting in selecting resources and learning strategies. The tutoring model emphasizes the mentee’s independence and conscious choice, which boosts motivation, accounts for individual characteristics, and develops lifelong learning skills. This model requires highly qualified tutors, takes more time than traditional mentoring, and is not always suitable for rigidly regulated programs. Nevertheless, the tutor mentoring model has gained widespread use in education (schools, universities, and continuing education).

Flash mentoring is a mentoring model in which the interaction between mentor and mentee is short-term and targeted: a single meeting or several short sessions aimed at solving a specific problem. This model emphasizes minimal theory and maximum practical recommendations. As various problems arise, the mentee can contact different mentors. The advantages of this model include time savings, quick results, and access to a variety of experts. However, flash mentoring often lacks in-depth problem solving; the outcome depends on the quality of the problem, and there is no emphasis on the mentee’s personal development. This model has become widespread in the corporate environment as a means of providing quick consultations, but is also used in education when prompt expert opinions are required.

Mentoring as a mentoring model involves more than just training a more experienced professional (mentor) to a less experienced one (mentee) [3]. It involves developing a partnership through the mentor’s experience, helping the mentee see the future, supporting their decision-making, and developing their thinking, not just their skills. The mentor acts as an expert, an advisor, and an inspirer all at once. The core principle of the relationship is “I’ll help you figure it out”, not “do as I do”. Mentoring relationships last for a long time, perhaps years. The implementation of this model depends largely on the mentor’s professionalism and personality, as the mentee often relies on the mentor’s opinion. Furthermore, implementing the model is very energy-intensive, requiring considerable time and

commitment from both participants. The model is widely used in education, particularly in mentoring students with disabilities.

The team mentoring model involves interaction between a group of mentors and mentees. Members of the mentoring team can bring different perspectives and diverse experience to the task. Mentoring in the team model is a collaborative process, where the main idea is to create a nurturing environment and showcase a diversity of experiences. Implementing this model promotes a diversity of perspectives and solutions; develops communication and teamwork skills; learns through real-world cases; and reduces dependence on a single mentor. At the same time, implementing this model requires coordinated efforts, allows for conflicting decisions, and creates a more intense development environment, requiring a strong communication culture. Team mentoring can be applied in various formats: mentor team → individual participant, mentor team → mentee team, and mentor team ↔ mentee team (mutual learning and experience sharing). The team mentoring model is used in corporate development programs, project work, and educational projects.

A comparison of pedagogical mentoring models based on mentoring interactions is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of pedagogical mentoring models based on mentoring interactions

Criterion	Traditional model	Tutoring model	Flash mentoring	Mentoring	Team model
Main goal	Transfer of experience and professional skills	Individual educational support	Rapid assistance in solving a specific task	Personal and professional development	Collaborative group development
Interaction format	Individual (one-to-one)	Individual	Short-term, targeted	Individual (sometimes blended)	Group-based
Duration	Long-term (months, years)	Long-term	Short-term (1 to several sessions)	Medium- or long-term	Long-term or cyclical
The role of the mentor	Expert sharing experience	Guide, navigator	Consultant on a specific problem	Senior partner, advisor	Team member / facilitator
Role of the learner	Learner mastering the activity	Active participant in learning	Person requesting help	Active participant in development	Equal member of the group
Nature of the relationship	Hierarchical	Partnership-based	Functional, professional	Trust-based, partnership-based	Collegial

Criterion	Traditional model	Tutoring model	Flash mentoring	Mentoring	Team model
Working methods	Demonstration, explanation, practice	Individual learning pathways, reflection	Consultations, advice	Dialogue, reflection, support	Project work, discussion
Focus	Skills and experience	Individual development and educational path	Specific problem	Personal and professional growth	Collective activity
Degree of formalization	High	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium
Advantages	Rapid acquisition of practical skills	Individualization of learning	Efficiency, flexibility	Deep personal development	Development of teamwork skills
Risks	Dependence, authoritarianism	Vague outcomes	Superficiality	Dependence on the mentor's personality	Diffusion of responsibility
Where to use	Universities, schools, secondary vocational education	Educational programs, tutoring	Courses, training sessions, projects	Universities, career development, management	Project-based learning, teams

Thus, various pedagogical models of mentoring interactions have become widespread in modern Russian education. Each is specific, aimed at solving specific mentoring problems, and has its own advantages and disadvantages. This diversity of models allows teachers to choose the one most suitable for achieving a specific goal, combine them, and find the best implementation options based on the desired results.

Legal aspects of implementing contemporary models of pedagogical mentoring.

At the present stage, the effectiveness of mentoring practices is also determined by the degree of their regulatory clarity. As A. G. Sobolev and T. Yu. Kudashova note, for a long time Federal Law No. 273-FZ of December 29, 2012, On Education in the Russian Federation, contained no specific provisions on mentoring. Therefore, regulation in the education system was shaped primarily at the level of subordinate legislation, methodological guidelines, and local documents of educational organizations [12, p. 38]. The absence of a unified legal standard increases the risk of legal uncertainty in defining the functions of a mentor and formulating the requirements applicable to them.

For general and secondary vocational education, an important benchmark was the target mentoring model approved by Order No. R-145 of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation dated December 25, 2019 [7]. These guidelines define mentoring as a universal technology for the transfer of experience, knowledge, skills, competencies, and values. Among the organizational forms identified are the pairs “pupil-pupil”, “college student-pupil”, “teacher-pupil”, “employer-college student”, and “teacher-teacher” [12, pp. 39-40]. From a scientific and pedagogical perspective, these forms are not identical to mentoring models: the traditional, tutoring, flash mentoring, mentoring, and team models describe the nature of interaction, whereas the normative forms establish the institutional framework within which this interaction is implemented.

An important step in the development of legal regulation in the field of mentoring was the adoption of Federal Law No. 381-FZ of November 9, 2024, which introduced Article 351.8 into the Labour Code of the Russian Federation on the specific regulation of the work of employees performing mentoring functions in the sphere of labour [6]. The law establishes that mentoring may be carried out only with the employee’s written consent, and that the content, duration, and form of mentoring work must be specified in the employment contract or in a supplementary agreement. It also provides for the possibility of additional payments for mentoring and grants the employee the right to refuse to continue mentoring before the agreed term expires. For educational institutions, this means a shift from a predominantly voluntary model of mentoring support to a more formalized system in which the mentor’s workload, timeframe, expected outcomes, and remuneration must be regulated.

However, in the new legal environment, different mentoring models require different degrees of formal regulation. The general legal basis for their implementation in an educational institution is Federal Law No. 273-FZ of December 29, 2012, On Education in the Russian Federation, in particular the provisions concerning the competence of the educational institution and its local regulations (Articles 28 and 30), as well as the rights and duties of learners and teaching staff (Articles 34, 43, 47, and 48) [8]. The traditional and mentoring models require the greatest degree of formalization as a work function: the relevant provisions of the Labour Code of the Russian Federation apply, including Article 351.8, introduced by Federal Law No. 381-FZ of November 9, 2024, together with the general rules on additional work and remuneration [4; 6]. Accordingly, for these models it is important to set out in local regulations and employment documents the goals of mentoring, the criteria for selecting mentors, timeframes, procedures for evaluating outcomes, and the grounds for terminating the relationship [6; 8]. The tutoring model is additionally grounded in the provisions of Law No. 273-FZ concerning learners’ rights, the duties of teaching staff, and the local regulation of the educational process. This model requires the formalization of procedures for diagnosis, support, reflection, and the allocation

of responsibility among the tutor, the administration, and the mentee [8]. For flash mentoring and the team model, the provisions of Federal Law No. 152-FZ of July 27, 2006, On Personal Data are especially important, since short-term consultations, group coordination, and information exchange raise issues of confidentiality, the scope of processed data, and access control [9]. These forms therefore require legal regulation of interaction procedures, areas of responsibility, and rules governing the processing of personal data.

Research on the legal regulation of mentoring in higher education shows that, in the absence of a unified local act, mentoring activities are implemented through a range of different forms and types of support [2, pp. 435-437]. O. S. Batova includes among them research mentoring, academic mentoring, a school for young teachers, the activities of a student scientific society, a departmental research group, and the work of an academic group supervisor. The researcher points to the need for a special local act on mentoring to be adopted at the level of the educational institution, one that would define the content, principles, forms, and types of mentoring, as well as a system of material and non-material incentives. Such an approach makes it possible to distinguish mentoring from the activities of a teacher and an immediate supervisor, thereby strengthening the organizational and legal status of mentoring activities.

In a broader socio-legal context, as I. A. Shesteriakov notes, mentoring is associated both with the transfer of professional experience and with the adaptation of a young employee or young specialist to the team, organizational norms, and professional culture [10, pp. 100-102]. Therefore, the legal framework for contemporary models of pedagogical mentoring should include not only a description of procedures, but also the establishment of the parties' responsibilities, motivation mechanisms, forms of incentives, procedures for completing mentoring, and tools for assessing its effectiveness.

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全球化背景下现代教育体系的创新与改革
**INNOVATION AND REFORM OF MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEMS
IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了全球化背景下现代教育体系的创新与改革。研究指出，全球互联互通加速了教育理念、治理模式、数字技术和质量标准的传播，同时也加剧了各国教育体系应对不平等、劳动力市场转型和文化多元化的压力。本文分析了教育改革的主要驱动因素，包括数字化转型、基于能力的课程设计、治理现代化、教师专业发展以及对公平和终身学习日益增长的需求。文章特别关注国际趋同与本土特殊性之间的矛盾：尽管全球化鼓励政策方向的共同发展，但改革只有在尊重文化传统、制度条件和社会需求的前提下才能取得成效。文章提出，教育体系的现代化应将技术创新与人文价值观相结合，在不削弱公共责任的前提下提高行政灵活性，并加强确保人人平等享有优质教育的包容性机制。结论强调，在全球化时代，成功的改革并非机械地照搬外国模式，而是需要批判性地进行调整、平衡治理和可持续的能力建设。

关键词：教育体制改革；全球化；数字化转型；教育创新；公平；终身学习

Abstract. *This article examines the innovation and reform of modern education systems under the conditions of globalization. The study argues that global interconnectedness has accelerated the circulation of educational ideas, governance models, digital technologies, and quality standards, while also intensifying pressures on national education systems to respond to inequality, labor market transformation, and cultural diversification. The paper analyzes the main drivers of educational reform, including digital transformation, competency-based curriculum design, governance modernization, teacher professional development, and the growing demand for equity and lifelong learning. Particular attention is paid to the contradiction between international convergence and local specificity: although globalization encourages*

common policy directions, reforms can only be effective when they respect cultural traditions, institutional conditions, and social needs. The article proposes that the modernization of education systems should combine technological innovation with humanistic values, improve administrative flexibility without weakening public responsibility, and strengthen inclusive mechanisms that ensure equal access to quality education. The conclusion emphasizes that successful reform in the global era depends not on mechanical borrowing of foreign models, but on critical adaptation, balanced governance, and sustainable capacity building.

Keywords: *education system reform; globalization; digital transformation; educational innovation; equity; lifelong learning*

Introduction

Globalization has become one of the most influential forces shaping education in the twenty-first century. Educational institutions are no longer isolated within national borders; instead, they operate in a world characterized by mobility of knowledge, rapid technological change, transnational competition, and intensified intercultural contact. As a result, governments and universities increasingly rethink educational aims, management structures, and teaching methods in order to prepare learners for participation in a globally connected society.

Modern education systems face a dual challenge. On the one hand, they are expected to improve quality, efficiency, and international competitiveness. On the other hand, they must preserve social cohesion, cultural continuity, and equal educational opportunity. Reform therefore cannot be reduced to a purely technical process of administrative adjustment. It is a strategic transformation involving values, curriculum, institutional governance, teacher professionalism, assessment, and the relationship between education and society.

This article explores the major directions of innovation and reform in modern education systems in the context of globalization. The purpose is to identify the most significant drivers of change, analyze the opportunities and risks associated with current reform trends, and formulate principles for sustainable educational modernization.

Globalization as a Driver of Educational Reform

Globalization influences education through economic, technological, cultural, and political channels. Economically, the transition toward knowledge-based development increases the importance of human capital, innovation, and flexible skills. Education systems are therefore pressured to cultivate analytical thinking, communication, digital literacy, and adaptability rather than reliance on rote learning alone. Labor markets increasingly require interdisciplinary competences and the ability to learn continuously across the lifespan.

Technologically, digital platforms, open educational resources, artificial intelligence, and networked communication have transformed access to knowledge and

modes of teaching. The classroom is no longer the only space of learning. Online and blended environments have expanded the possibilities of personalized instruction, remote collaboration, and cross-border academic exchange. At the same time, technology has made visible the inequalities of infrastructure, family support, and digital competence that separate students and institutions.

Culturally and politically, globalization has strengthened international comparisons of educational outcomes and increased the influence of transnational organizations, rankings, and policy frameworks. This has stimulated reforms aimed at accountability, transparency, and quality assurance. However, the global circulation of policy ideas does not automatically generate improvement. Imported reforms may fail when they are detached from local educational traditions, resource conditions, or social expectations.

Key Directions of Innovation in Modern Education Systems

One of the most visible reform directions is curriculum transformation. Contemporary curricula increasingly shift from content accumulation to competency-based frameworks. Instead of measuring success only by the reproduction of subject knowledge, modern systems emphasize problem solving, collaboration, creativity, ethical responsibility, and intercultural communication. This transition reflects the understanding that education should prepare learners not only for examinations, but also for complex participation in civic and professional life.

A second direction is the digital transformation of teaching and management. Educational innovation today includes learning management systems, digital assessment tools, virtual laboratories, adaptive learning software, and data-informed administrative decision making. When implemented responsibly, these instruments can improve responsiveness, broaden access, and support differentiated instruction. Nevertheless, digitalization should remain a means rather than an end. Without pedagogical redesign, technology may simply reproduce old practices in a new form.

A third major direction concerns the professional role of teachers. In a reforming education system, teachers are not only transmitters of knowledge, but also designers of learning environments, mentors, evaluators, and participants in institutional change. This requires continuous professional development, stronger research literacy, and supportive communities of practice. Reform policies that ignore teacher workload, motivation, and autonomy are unlikely to achieve long-term success.

Another important area is governance modernization. Education systems increasingly experiment with decentralized management, institutional autonomy, stakeholder participation, and evidence-based planning. Such measures can encourage innovation and local responsiveness. Yet excessive decentralization may also deepen regional disparities if local capacities differ substantially. For this reason, governance reform must combine flexibility with strong public coordination and equitable resource distribution.

Reform Challenges: Equity, Quality, and Cultural Balance

Despite the promise of modernization, educational reform under globalization is accompanied by serious contradictions. The first is the tension between quality enhancement and educational equity. Systems that pursue excellence through selective mechanisms, market competition, or performance-based financing may unintentionally widen social inequality. Students from rural, low-income, minority, or otherwise disadvantaged backgrounds often encounter structural barriers that reduce their access to high-quality institutions, digital resources, and extracurricular learning opportunities.

The second contradiction lies between global standards and local cultural identity. International cooperation and benchmarking are valuable, but education cannot become culturally neutral. Language policy, historical memory, ethical values, and national traditions remain essential components of educational content. Effective reform should therefore support openness to the world while preserving the cultural foundations that give education social meaning and legitimacy.

The third challenge concerns assessment. Many reform initiatives promote measurable results and accountability, yet overly standardized evaluation can narrow the curriculum and discourage creativity. If schools and universities are judged mainly by short-term indicators, they may prioritize test preparation over deep learning, innovation, and holistic development. Assessment reform should thus include formative approaches, diverse evidence of achievement, and recognition of social and emotional growth.

Strategies for Sustainable Education System Reform

Sustainable educational reform requires a balanced strategy rather than fragmented interventions. First, policy design should be evidence-informed but context-sensitive. Comparative experience is useful only when adapted critically to local realities. Policymakers need to assess institutional readiness, teacher capacity, financial sustainability, and social acceptance before scaling reform measures.

Second, digital transformation should be integrated with pedagogical innovation and social inclusion. Investment in infrastructure must be accompanied by teacher training, curriculum redesign, cybersecurity standards, and support for disadvantaged learners. Otherwise, educational technology may deepen rather than reduce inequality.

Third, reform should strengthen the status and competence of teachers. High-quality teacher education, mentoring systems, professional learning communities, and fair evaluation mechanisms are foundational for any lasting improvement. Educational systems become innovative when teachers are empowered to experiment, reflect, and collaborate, not when they are treated merely as executors of top-down directives.

Fourth, governance reform should promote accountability together with public responsibility. Educational institutions need room for initiative, but the state remains responsible for guaranteeing accessibility, fairness, and national development

priorities. Productive reform therefore depends on cooperation among ministries, local authorities, schools, universities, employers, families, and civil society.

Finally, lifelong learning must become a central principle of educational modernization. In a rapidly changing world, education cannot be limited to childhood and youth. Systems should create flexible pathways for adult learning, reskilling, and recognition of prior learning so that citizens can continue personal and professional development throughout life.

Conclusion

The context of globalization has made innovation and reform of modern education systems both necessary and unavoidable. Economic restructuring, digital transformation, cultural interaction, and international comparison have all intensified demands for more flexible, inclusive, and future-oriented education. Yet reform is meaningful only when it goes beyond imitation and addresses real social needs.

The analysis in this article shows that the most promising directions of reform include competency-based curriculum development, thoughtful digitalization, teacher professional growth, governance modernization, and a stronger commitment to equity and lifelong learning. At the same time, policymakers must carefully manage the tensions between excellence and inclusion, global integration and cultural identity, measurement and human development.

Therefore, the innovation of education systems in the global era should be understood as a comprehensive and value-oriented process. Its success depends on the capacity to combine international openness with local relevance, technological progress with educational ethics, and institutional change with human-centered development. Only under these conditions can modern education systems respond effectively to globalization while preserving their social mission.

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N. F. 布纳科夫对19世纪下半叶至20世纪初俄罗斯小学音乐教育理论发展的贡献

CONTRIBUTION OF N. F. BUNAKOV TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE THEORY OF MUSIC EDUCATION IN THE RUSSIAN PRIMARY SCHOOL OF THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIX — EARLY XX CENTURIES

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摘要：本文旨在探寻19世纪下半叶至20世纪初俄罗斯小学音乐教育理论发展的价值基础，并探讨了俄国教育家和方法论学家尼古拉·费多罗维奇·布纳科夫（1837-1904）的思想。文章阐述了布纳科夫关于教育理论的必要性，他认为该理论应建立在相关学科数据的基础上；他认为教学和育人是一门真正的艺术，需要与鲜活的人们进行细致的交流。文章还引用了布纳科夫关于公立学校任务的论述，他认为公立学校的任务不仅在于教授读写能力，还在于培养儿童的人格尊严、道德情操和审美情趣。在这一过程中，教堂歌唱课程和儿童参与东正教礼拜活动发挥着重要作用。

关键词：教育，教养，小学，审美情趣，教堂歌唱

Abstract. *In this article, in order to find the axiological foundations for the development of the theory of music education in a domestic primary school in the second half of the 19th — early 20th centuries, the ideas of the Russian teacher and methodologist Nikolai Fedorovich Bunakov (1837-1904) are considered. The work shows the teacher's thoughts on the need for a theory of educational affairs, created on the basis of data from related sciences; on the recognition of teaching and education as genuine art based on delicate communication with living people. The thinker's statements about the tasks of the public school are given, which consist not only in teaching literacy, but also in educating children in human dignity, moral and aesthetic feelings. An important role in this process belongs to the lessons of church singing, the participation of children in Orthodox worship.*

Keywords: *education, upbringing, primary school, aesthetic feelings, church singing.*

The development of the theory and practice of music education in a modern primary school is impossible without understanding the historical and pedagogical experience. Domestic school and pedagogy has great historical potential. Among the many personalities, the legacy of Nikolai Fedorovich Bunakov (1837-1904), a Russian teacher, theorist and practitioner of primary education, and an primary school methodologist, deserves special attention.

In one of his speeches at courses for teachers and primary school teachers, analyzing historical experience, the teacher noted that the need for literacy flared up in Russia after the reform of February 19, 1961 [1, p. 9].

Educational business, according to N. F. Bunakov is a practical activity, but it requires “animation” and creativity, has its own theory. This theory is constantly being developed, improved by practitioners and observer theorists. The theory seeks to substantiate its rules on the data of other sciences that have the study of man and human life as their content [1, p. 6-7]. The matter of teaching and raising children is a complex and delicate art, the material for which is “small living people and human souls, to approach which with inexperienced hands and with an empty head, without the confidence to give them good, would be a great sin” [1, p. 8]. The foundations of educational art are universal, but are embodied in living folk forms [1, p. 9].

The folk school, according to N. F. Bunakov, should strive not only to teach children literacy and some practical skills, it should “raise human dignity in the children of the people,” “prepare them for true human life” [2, p. 47], give the opportunity to show the universal human forces of their nature, open space to the application of thought, feeling and will [2, p. 94]. The people need a school with a broad program, capable of expanding their mental horizons and humanizing morals [2, pp. 355-366].

The school, according to N. F. Bunakov, should mean the student himself, as “a living human person, created in the image and likeness of God,” having individual characteristics. The basis of training should be “free, amateur development of the personality through the excitement and development of its natural forces” [2, p. 95].

The teacher noted the importance of psychology for understanding the nature of the child, studying mental life, developing the “theory of educational affairs.” Along with psychology, he considered anatomy, physiology and hygiene as important sciences in this regard — as the sciences that study the body, its composition, the processes occurring in it [2, pp. 91.92-93]. Taking care of the senses, controlling the acuity of hearing when placed on desks (for example, seating the hearing impaired near the teacher), he considered one of the most important responsibilities of education [2, p. 114, 118].

Exploring the nature of feelings, N. F. Bunakov distinguished between physical (sensations of pleasure, suffering, pleasant, unpleasant) and ideal feelings. The life of feeling begins with physical feelings, for example, pleasant combinations of

sounds, but in full enjoyment of beautiful sounds, works of art, is an ideal feeling, as it is determined not only by pleasant sensations, but also by ideas excited in our soul. Ideal feelings are higher-order mental phenomena closely related to the mental process, among them are moral and aesthetic feelings [2, pp. 207-208].

Serious attention N. F. Bunakov paid church singing at school. In 1890, in the article “Some features of peasant life and moral and religious concepts. The Law of God, Church Slavonic Reading and Singing at School” — the fifth chapter of the work “Rural School and Folk Life” — the teacher argued that church singing has a huge religious-moral and beneficial-educational value, contributes to the splendor of church worship, enhances the prayer mood, elevates the spirit [3, p. 386].

According to N. F. Bunakov, ordinary people feel the influence of church chants, often respond to how well to stand and pray in church, listen to the slender singing of children’s voices. At this time, “you just want to cry,” “you stand like in paradise.” Among adults there are always those who want to participate in the church choir, they diligently attend singing at the school, do not hesitate to study singing with children [3, p. 386-387]. N. F. Bunakov insisted on a serious, full respect for the teaching of church singing, on observing the same order in singing lessons as in other subjects [2, p. 259].

N. F. Bunakov noted that singing lessons help students not only better understand the “external meaning” of prayers and church chants, but also feel their inner meaning. In addition, singing classes at school, the participation of children in Orthodox worship in the church, help to raise more ennobled and accustomed to the order of peasant children: “Look at the boy after he learned to sing a little and began to go to the choir: and the same small, but not the same, — and in the face there is more clarity and meaning, and the speech is more restrained and more intelligible, and all the grasps, movements are softer, and it has become more polite, and more solid, and more beautiful” [3, p. 387].

Thus, in the works of N. F. Bunakov argued the importance of creating her own theory for the development of educational affairs based on data from other sciences. The teacher recognized the education and upbringing of children as a delicate art, the complexity of which consists in communicating with living people who have a human soul. The task of the public school, in his understanding, is not only teaching children to read and write, but also educating them in human dignity, preparing for real life. He saw the student as an individual, a living human person who was created in the image and likeness of God. N. F. Bunakov was sure that the basis of training should be the desire for amateur development of the individual on the basis of her natural inclinations. For this, he considered it necessary to study psychology, anatomy, physiology and hygiene. The teacher investigated the nature of human feelings, recognized moral and aesthetic feelings as feelings of a higher order.

He attached great importance to church singing in primary school, was convinced of the need for the most serious attitude to this subject. N. F. Bunakov noted the influence of singing lessons and the participation of children in the church choir on the children's better understanding of the meaning of church chants, the upbringing of nobility and worthy behavior.

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中国二元制职业教育实施特点
**FEATURES OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DUAL-SYSTEM
VOCATIONAL EDUCATION IN CHINA**

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摘要:在全球化和知识经济时代,职业教育面临着培养应用型、创新型人才的迫切需求。文章分析了中国二元制职业教育的核心要素,包括校企合作机制、课程设置、师资队伍建设以及评价体系。结合中国职业教育现状,指出当前人才培养模式存在的突出问题。探讨符合中国特色的二元制职业教育人才培养模式。

关键词:二元制,校企合作,人才培养模式,职业教育

Abstract: *In the era of globalization and the knowledge economy, vocational education faces an urgent need to cultivate applied and innovative talents. This article examines the core features of the dual-system vocational education in China, including mechanisms for school-enterprise collaboration, curriculum design, faculty development, and evaluation systems. In light of the current state of vocational education in China, it highlights prominent issues within the existing talent cultivation model. Furthermore, the study explores a talent cultivation model for dual-system vocational education that aligns with China's distinctive context.*

Keywords: *dual-system; school-enterprise cooperation; talent cultivation model; vocational education*

Against the backdrop of China's deepening industrialization, informatization, and internationalization, alongside an accelerating economic structural transformation, the development of vocational education has emerged as both a new trend and a key driver in the evolution of the industrial system. As the economy undergoes transformation and upgrading, accompanied by shifts in the mode of economic development, there is a growing need to cultivate a large number of high-quality application-oriented talents who can adapt to these changes and meet the demands of economic restructuring. However, due to various influencing factors, the supply side of talent cultivation and the demand side of industry remain misaligned in terms of structure, quality, and competence. A key underlying issue is the disconnect

between the education and talent chains on one hand, and the industrial and innovation chains on the other, which significantly constrains the effectiveness of human resource supply.

To a certain extent, the development of dual-system vocational education enhances the vocational skills of enterprise employees. Its scale and quality directly influence product quality, economic performance, and the pace of development. The quality of industrial products, the overall economic benefits generated, and the speed of social development are all closely tied to the level and reach of vocational education. Globally, the development of vocational education has yielded notable results. While economic growth has spurred the advancement of vocational education systems, vocational education has, in turn, contributed positively to socioeconomic development.

The dual-system vocational education model typically involves students who, after completing compulsory education and entering higher education, study vocational theory and general knowledge at a vocational school while simultaneously receiving technical and professional training within an enterprise. Its core features include deep enterprise engagement, the integration of theoretical and practical learning tracks, and school–enterprise collaboration in talent development, all of which contribute to high-quality employment outcomes for graduates. Some Chinese scholars have proposed a “tripartite synergy” framework for vocational education ecosystem development [1], emphasizing collaborative mechanisms between schools and enterprises, advancing cross-enterprise training platforms and professional mentorship teams, and restructuring competency-based evaluation systems.

As an essential component of China’s education system and human resource development strategy, dual-system vocational education plays a critical role in cultivating diverse talent, transmitting technical skills, and promoting employment, entrepreneurship, and economic growth. The Chinese government places high priority on vocational education, identifying it as a key area within national education development. A series of policies and reform measures have been introduced. The «National Vocational Education Reform Implementation Plan» (2019) outlined the blueprint for vocational education development in the new phase. The «Guidelines on Promoting High-Quality Development of Modern Vocational Education» (2021) established goals and actionable pathways for achieving high-quality development. In May 2022, the newly revised «Vocational Education Law» provided a legal framework to regulate and further advance vocational education. The government has also strengthened support for vocational education by increasing investment, establishing vocational education bases, and reforming curricula and assessment systems. These policies have created a favorable policy environment and provided financial support for vocational education development. The «Implementation Plan for Enhancing Industry-Education Integration to Empower Vocational Education

(2023-2025)» sets the target of establishing approximately 50 national industry-education integration pilot cities by 2025. These cities are expected to play a leading and catalytic role, with more than 10,000 enterprises recognized as industry-education integration entities across key sectors such as high-end manufacturing and information technology. However, challenges such as regional disparities and the high costs of enterprise participation continue to hinder the comprehensive implementation of the dual-system model.

The most distinctive feature of dual-system vocational education in China lies in the restructuring of the relationship between schools and enterprises. In the traditional model, schools served as the core, with enterprises acting merely as venues for student internships. In contrast, within the dual-system framework, there has been a progressive shift toward joint school–enterprise education provision, in which enterprises are deeply involved in the development of student training plans, curriculum design, instructional implementation, and assessment. Some institutions have gone further by establishing industry colleges in collaboration with enterprises, effectively binding schools, enterprises, and industries together. The central objective is to precisely cultivate the high-skilled talent demanded by enterprises. The dual-system vocational education model emphasizes the integration of theory and practice: students receive theoretical instruction at school while engaging in hands-on training within enterprises, with the two components complementing each other. This instructional approach not only helps students understand the practical application of theoretical knowledge but also deepens their comprehension and mastery of theory through problem-solving in real-world contexts. Consequently, this model fosters students’ innovative thinking and strengthens their ability to address practical challenges.

A curriculum developed in response to occupational needs constitutes the core pathway of dual-system vocational education. Currently, a notable issue in Chinese vocational education is the lag in program offerings relative to industrial development. Some institutions continue to adhere to traditional disciplinary structures that do not adequately align with the technical demands of emerging industries [2]. In response, the curriculum should be designed based on the knowledge required in production processes, following a sequence of “pre-internship, foundational theoretical study, specialized foundational theoretical study, industrial internship, specialized theoretical internship, and graduation internship and project.” The curriculum development process should incorporate a mechanism of full engagement by industry mentors, using authentic project cases to achieve an organic integration of theoretical instruction and production practice, ensuring that instructional content remains synchronized with the forefront of industrial development.

Teaching materials in the dual-system vocational education model are developed through scientific analysis based on the actual requirements of enterprise production

and the talent standards demanded by the current market economy. The content of these materials is aligned with production realities and contemporary needs, with data updated in a timely manner and case studies drawn from authentic production scenarios, supplemented by video materials to enhance learning. Given the rapid pace of technological advancement and the accumulation of practical experience in production processes, it is essential to gather extensive resources to enrich instruction and improve the quality of teaching materials. These materials must be delivered and discussed promptly to ensure that graduates are immediately able to meet the demands of the job market upon completion of their studies. In China, dual-system vocational education maintains a close connection with production practice and continuously strengthens the development of teaching materials in this regard [3].

Enterprises serve not only as training bases for students but also as collaborative training platforms for university instructors and enterprise engineers. By hosting university faculty for practical training and involving them in actual enterprise projects, where they work alongside enterprise instructors to guide students, the proportion of university instructors engaged in applied projects increases. This approach enhances instructors' practical competencies and helps them accumulate hands-on project experience, thereby contributing to the development of dual-qualified faculty. At the same time, it generates additional benefits for higher education institutions. The effective implementation of dual-system vocational education relies on a teaching workforce equipped with both theoretical knowledge and practical instructional capabilities. In China, emphasis is placed on cultivating "dual-qualified" teachers, requiring that vocational subject instructors hold both a teaching qualification certificate and a professional certification at the intermediate level or above.

Currently, China is exploring pathways for developing a contingent of "dual-qualified" teachers in dual-system vocational education with Chinese characteristics, focusing on the following aspects to establish a highly competent teaching workforce that provides human resource support for the high-quality development of vocational education.

First, the establishment of teacher certification standards. The formulation of certification standards for dual-qualified teachers adheres to the integration of educational, professional, and vocational dimensions. The educational dimension pertains to teaching competence, the professional dimension relates to disciplinary knowledge and expertise, and the vocational dimension concerns practical skills. Without a foundation in educational competence, the professional and vocational dimensions of teachers cannot be fully realized. Conversely, a lack of vocational experience, such as industry practice, hinders teachers' ability to translate academic theoretical knowledge into occupational practical skills.

Second, the development of diversified training models for dual-qualified teachers. Efforts are being made to explore multi-stakeholder coordination mechanisms

involving government, universities, vocational institutions, enterprises, and industries. Diversified funding channels are being expanded, training teams for vocational teacher preparation are being formed from multiple sources, practice bases for vocational teachers are being established through collaborative governance, and a multi-actor quality assurance system for vocational teaching staff is being constructed.

Third, the implementation of a flexible and open personnel management system for dual-qualified teachers in vocational education. Institutional autonomy is being expanded through the adoption of a president responsibility system and a comprehensive employment contract system. A personnel system is being introduced that allows for flexible entry and exit of staff, promotion and demotion based on performance, adjustment of compensation accordingly, and the emergence of outstanding talent.

Fourth, the establishment of a scientific and rational teacher evaluation mechanism. The evaluation of dual-qualified teachers should adhere to the following principles: developmental orientation of evaluation goals, emphasizing teachers' sustainable development by embedding evaluation throughout the entire process of teacher development and guiding dual-qualified teachers toward self-directed improvement and continuous growth; diversity of evaluation subjects, establishing a quality evaluation mechanism for vocational education teachers involving multiple participants, including vocational institutions, industries, enterprises, and social organizations, thereby enhancing the relevance and credibility of evaluation; and multidimensionality of evaluation content, conducting comprehensive assessments of teachers' professional ethics and vocational commitment, educational knowledge and instructional competence, and disciplinary knowledge and practical skills, which serve as important references for contract period assessments, promotion evaluations, and performance-based compensation decisions [4].

The evaluation system for dual-system vocational education in China is progressively moving toward the integration of curricula and professional certification. Upon completing institutional coursework and workplace training, students are required to participate in vocational qualification examinations administered by industry associations or vocational skills certification bodies. In some pilot institutions, students are awarded both a graduation certificate and a vocational qualification certificate upon completion. Concurrently, the assessment framework has expanded from a single-school model to encompass enterprises and industries, adopting a combined approach that integrates process-based assessment with summative evaluation. For instance, in automotive maintenance programs, students are jointly assessed by enterprise mentors and institutional instructors upon completing each training module, followed by a unified practical examination at the end of the term. This evaluation model places greater emphasis on hands-on competence and professional competence [5].

From the institutional perspective, higher vocational institutions, as an integral component of China's higher education system, remain predominantly oriented toward academic credentialing. The design of vocational programs often fails to account for the actual needs of enterprises and society, resulting in program structures that are, in some cases, misaligned with market demands. As a result, students in higher vocational institutions are not always equipped with the competencies required by enterprises upon graduation. Furthermore, most higher vocational institutions lack dedicated funding for school–enterprise collaboration, and the quality of instruction is not consistently ensured, which in turn limits their capacity to effectively meet enterprise needs.

From the enterprise perspective, school–enterprise collaboration in China is largely sustained through informal relational ties between institutions and enterprises. Enterprises often view such collaboration as a form of philanthropic engagement rather than a strategically planned endeavor, and effective mechanisms for ensuring its sustainability are lacking. In addition, due to frequent ambiguities regarding responsibilities and rights in collaborative programs, enterprises' interests are not always adequately protected during implementation, which diminishes their motivation to actively engage in school–enterprise cooperation.

From the government perspective, the absence of concrete implementation measures and well-defined cooperation management mechanisms has hindered the effective realization of school–enterprise collaboration. Although China has enacted relevant legislation pertaining to vocational education, such as the «Decision on Vigorously Developing Vocational Education» and the «Vocational Education Law», the lack of detailed implementation guidelines remains a challenge. Most local governments have not established third-party institutions to facilitate coordination and support, and the level of governmental backing for school–enterprise cooperation at the local level remains insufficient.

In China, dual-system vocational education extends beyond bilateral cooperation between schools and enterprises to encompass a mutually beneficial and synergistic partnership involving government, enterprises, and institutions, all working toward high-quality development through coordinated efforts. Different forms of dual-system vocational education must develop tailored instructional requirements and faculty resources in response to the specific needs of enterprises to fulfill the original intent of talent development. By establishing an accurate understanding of the dual-system vocational education model as the foundational starting point and implementing its precise requirements, it becomes possible to achieve a balanced alignment among government, enterprises, and institutions, thereby forming a dual-system vocational education talent cultivation model with Chinese characteristics.

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乌兹别克斯坦中等专业教育数字化
**DIGITALIZATION OF SECONDARY SPECIALIZED EDUCATION
IN UZBEKISTAN**

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摘要： 本文旨在分析乌兹别克斯坦独立初期中等职业教育的现状、不足和问题，以及为克服这些问题而采取的初步措施，并探讨新乌兹别克斯坦在教育体系数字化（特别是中等职业教育数字化）等方面的变革与改革。

关键词： 教育，数字化，创新，儿童，青年，培养，未来。

Abstract. *The purpose of this research article is to analyze the state, shortcomings, and problems of secondary vocational education in Uzbekistan in the early years of independence, as well as the initial steps to overcome them and the changes and reforms in the New Uzbekistan, such as the digitalization of the education system, particularly secondary vocational education.*

Keywords: *Education, digitalization, innovation, children, youth, upbringing, future.*

Currently, digital technologies are actively employed across all spheres of life. They facilitate the rapid development of the economy, banking sector, service industries, as well as the educational process. Among all citizens living in the country, including young children and pensioners, there exists a widespread conviction that digital technologies can solve all societal problems. In this regard, as emphasized by the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, ‘In order to achieve development, it is essential to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies.’ [1]

In the initial years of independence, the 12-year compulsory education system was integrated with the system of general secondary education, secondary specialized, and vocational education. In addition to general education, young people had the opportunity to acquire professional qualifications at colleges. During the initial period, certain achievements were realized within this system in the domain of secondary specialized and vocational education established in our country.

However, as a result of fundamental reforms in the New Uzbekistan, unresolved issues and deficiencies have been identified in the system of secondary

specialized and vocational education, which does not meet contemporary requirements and requires substantial reform. First and foremost, the challenges were examined, and the majority of them were as follows:

Primarily, most vocational technical schools were situated far from settlements, villages, and rural communities. This circumstance prevented students from attending classes regularly. Consequently, this led to a decline in the overall quality of education.

Secondly, there was a shortage of skilled master instructors, and most vocational colleges along with their training workshops lacked adequate laboratory equipment. The existing materials were also unsuitable.

Thirdly, there was a shortage of textbooks and instructional materials in vocational colleges. The existing textbooks were outdated and did not meet the requirements. New textbooks had not been developed or published for many years.

Fourthly, vocational colleges had not established a personnel training system aligned with the actual needs of regional economies. Consequently, the majority of trained personnel were unable to work in their respective specialties. The college education system was defined as uniform for all students, irrespective of their field of study. In other words, both a mechanic and a student specializing in electronics underwent a three-year course of study. In this framework, the duration of training did not correspond to the complexity level of the professions or to the process required to master them.

Fifth, the sector required equipping with ICT technology and digitalization in compliance with contemporary standards.

To address these issues, on January 25, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, issued a decree 'On Measures for the Radical Improvement of the General Secondary, Secondary Specialized, and Vocational Education System,' highlighting deficiencies within the secondary specialized and vocational education system. The challenges were presented openly and transparently. This represented a very important and timely initial step.

According to the decree, from the 2018-2019 academic year onward, compulsory general secondary education has been implemented based on an 11-year curriculum. Starting from the 2019-2020 academic year, admission to vocational colleges has been conducted based on the voluntary choice of graduates of the 11th grade of general education schools. Thus, the planned and continued enhancement of the operations of vocational colleges commenced.

Colleges were subsequently assigned to ministries, agencies, business associations, commercial banks, and large enterprises. A conceptual framework for development in each area of training was formulated, national qualification frameworks were established, and professional standards were introduced. The essence of the professional standard lies in identifying the skills and competencies required from

a worker for a particular job; on this basis, modular training curricula began to be developed. The educational process is constantly evolving. The objective is to establish the professional education system as a crucial component of economic development. In other words, the principal task is to prepare highly qualified workers, professionals, and mid-level specialists for the economy.

Another significant development in this sphere is that colleges now admit not only school graduates but also individuals of any age possessing secondary specialized or higher education who are considered at risk of unemployment. Their format has also undergone radical changes. Whereas colleges previously offered only full-time education, the reformed colleges have introduced, in addition to full-time, part-time, distance, and blended learning modalities. It would not be an exaggeration to state that this has led to both qualitative and quantitative transformations within education. One of the subsequent innovations concerned the duration of study. In the previous system, the duration of study in colleges was fixed at three years; however, currently, in connection with the increasing complexity of professions, it is established as a flexible period ranging from six months to two years. This innovation is highly relevant, providing every citizen with the opportunity to enroll and study in any discipline at any time, according to their needs. Professional training programs lasting from six months to one year, which require advanced technological preparation, are now financed by employers-customers, institutions, and organizations. Individuals without employer-customers have the option to finance their studies from personal funds. Secondary specialized education programs with a specialization duration of 1.5 to 2 years are being implemented partially as alternatives to higher education and partially on a contractual basis. Economically sustainable ministries, agencies, and corporations, as well as major employers, can provide additional scholarships and similar forms of support to college students within their internal capabilities.

Therefore, the current new vocational education system differs in several respects from the previous system. The primary and most significant difference lies in the fact that all institutions operated under a uniform three-year standard, irrespective of the volume of practical skills and the complexity of the professions.

Based on research findings in this domain, the new system can be classified into three categories:

The first category comprises a network of new institutions. These institutions are designated as professional schools. These are vocational-technical schools that provide basic vocational training in the senior classes of general education schools, operating in accordance with programs of primary vocational education.

the second category consists of educational institutions known as departmental colleges. It is well established that a substantial volume of investments has been directed toward the real sectors of the economy. All these regional investment projects are grounded in new, innovative digital technologies. The new jobs being

created are specifically designed to support these emerging technological processes. Allocated among ministries, agencies, and major employers, these institutions systematically train specialists for the newly established jobs through these colleges, thereby facilitating the implementation of their projects and the expansion of the production and service sectors.

The third category— educational institutions comprising a network of colleges. This fundamentally differs from the technical programs of the former USSR in terms of the goals and objectives of the educational programs, as well as the volume of knowledge, skills, and competencies developed through this program. Currently, students who have completed technical colleges are granted the opportunity to continue their education in the second year of a bachelor's degree program without entrance examinations upon graduation. Such a privilege did not exist in the former colleges.

According to the State Committee on Statistics, at the beginning of the 2019/2020 academic year, 239,200 students were enrolled in vocational colleges, with the highest number of students located in the Samarkand region compared to other regions — 29,100. 25.6 thousand people in the Fergana region. 23.9 thousand people in the Kashkadarya region. 23.7 thousand people in Tashkent city. In total, 468.8 thousand students graduated from vocational colleges in Uzbekistan in 2019. The largest number of graduates is recorded in the Fergana (54.6 thousand) and Samarkand (54.1 thousand) regions, while the smallest numbers are found in the Navoi (13.2 thousand) and Syrdarya (10.8 thousand) regions.

As of the beginning of the 2019/2020 academic year, the total number of teachers employed in vocational colleges amounted to 17,500. In Uzbekistan, the average student-to-teacher ratio is 14; Kashkadarya region exhibits the highest average with 31 students per teacher, whereas Namangan region has the lowest average student-to-teacher ratio¹.

Based on the analysis of the aforementioned points, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Firstly, the reforms in the field of secondary specialized education during the era of the New Uzbekistan have laid the foundation for substantial and fundamental changes.

Secondly, the regulatory legal acts adopted within the framework of the Action Strategy aim at the radical improvement and digitalization of the secondary specialized and vocational education system.

Thirdly, despite positive outcomes, certain sectors of secondary specialized education continue to require highly qualified teaching professionals.

¹ <https://kun.uz/news/2020/06/23/ozbekistonda-orta-maxsus-kasb-hunar-talimi-tizimi-boyicha-statistik-malumotlar-elon-qilindi>

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未来大学教师在与中国学生共事时所展现的职业文化的一些方面
**SOME ASPECTS OF THE PROFESSIONAL CULTURE
OF PROSPECTIVE UNIVERSITY EDUCATORS IN WORKING
WITH CHINESE STUDENTS**

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摘要： 本文探讨了与中国学生共事的大学教师的职业文化相关问题；在涉及中国学生的教育过程中，界定了大学教师的数字能力概念；分析了中国学生与白俄罗斯教师思维方式的差异；并总结了中国学生的教育特点，将其与基于斯拉夫思维和欧洲理性主义文化基础的白俄罗斯共和国教育传统进行了比较。

关键词： 职业文化；高等教育；中国学生；教育传统；数字文化；职业能力。

Abstract: *This paper examines issues relating to the professional culture of university lecturers working with Chinese students; it defines the concept of digital competence among university lecturers in the context of the educational process involving students from China; It identifies differences in the mindset of Chinese students and Belarusian lecturers; it summarizes the pedagogical characteristics of students from China in comparison with pedagogical traditions in the Republic of Belarus, which are based on the cultural foundations of the Slavic mindset and European rationalism.*

Keywords: *professional culture; higher education; Chinese students; pedagogical traditions; digital culture; professional competences.*

In contemporary educational research, the concept of ‘professional culture of a university educator’ is regarded as a complex, multi-level concept that goes beyond a simple set of pedagogical competencies [1]. In the context of the widespread digitalization of society and the transformation of the higher education system, a new aspect — “digital culture” — is being added to the set of competencies encompassed by the concept of “professional culture of a university educator”. As noted in studies, digital culture represents a set of knowledge, skills, values and ethical norms in the field of digital technology use, characterized by a conscious attitude towards technology and a critical perception of the information consumed

[2]. In the context of teaching, this means that digital literacy, regardless of other factors, cannot be regarded as a prerequisite for professional competence without established moral principles and an understanding of ethical boundaries [3].

At the current stage, the development of the higher education system in the Republic of Belarus is characterized by internationalization and the expansion of academic mobility; it places particular emphasis on training teachers capable of working effectively in a multicultural educational environment. One area of focus is cooperation with students from the People's Republic of China, driven by the strong partnership between the two countries and the increasing number of Chinese students studying at universities in the Republic of Belarus [4].

In this context, the development of a university educator's professional culture becomes not merely an internal requirement, but an essential prerequisite for effective intercultural interaction. Despite this, as practice shows, the issue of developing professional culture with a focus on working with international students remains insufficiently explored.

Thus, the relevance of the issue of developing the professional culture of future university lecturers in their work with international students stems from the practical need to train educators capable of establishing productive interaction, taking into account the educational, communicative and cultural characteristics of international students.

The differences in the mindset of Chinese and Belarusian students, as observed in practice and documented in studies of national traditions, are directly relevant to how the educational process should be structured and how the professional culture of a future lecturer should be shaped. The awareness that cultural codes manifest themselves in various everyday situations that make up the learning process (for example, in how a student completes an assignment, answers questions, responds to comments, etc.) is a key factor in creating an atmosphere of productive learning. Difficulties arise from a fundamental difference in the perception of authority and the 'teacher–student' hierarchy. Chinese and Belarusian cultural norms give rise to differing expectations regarding the role of the educator. Chinese students, brought up in a tradition of respect for their teacher (the tradition of 束脩 — *shùxiū* — a modest gift to the teacher), expect the teacher to take on a clear leadership role, to present the course material in a structured manner, and to assess the results of their work fairly. At the same time, a Belarusian educator, brought up in a European pedagogical culture, expects students to engage in discussion and actively participate in the learning process. What appears at first glance to be the passivity of a Chinese student may be interpreted by a Belarusian teacher as a lack of preparation or a lack of interest in the learning process; however, from a Chinese perspective, this is a sign of respect for the educator and adherence to a customary cultural norm.

Communication difficulties between a Chinese student and a Belarusian lecturer arise from significant differences in communication styles, which, in turn, requires the

teacher to develop intercultural competencies within the framework of their existing professional culture. Chinese conversational culture is characterised by the concept of ‘面子- miànzi’ (face), which involves the extensive use of non-verbal cues, the avoidance of directly expressing disagreement, and a desire to preserve the ‘face’ of one’s companion (给面子- gěi miànzi — to respect someone’s feelings). In turn, Belarusian linguistic culture, having absorbed both European rationality and Slavic emotionality, allows for a more direct expression of one’s own opinion, which, in turn, may be perceived by Chinese students as abrupt and confrontational behavior. Future educators, whose professional culture is shaped within the Belarusian intellectual landscape, must be aware that working methods familiar to the Belarusian mindset may be perceived by Chinese students as a lack of pedagogical professionalism. It follows that, for the successful development of the professional culture of a future university lecturer aiming to work with international students, the inclusion of an intercultural component is essential. A cross-cultural ‘portrait’ of a teacher encompasses not only knowledge of national traditions, but also an awareness of one’s own pedagogical attitudes, shaped by local culture, as well as their reinterpretation from an international perspective.

An additional barrier to successful interaction between Chinese students and lecturers in the Republic of Belarus is the language issue. In a situation where the educational process takes place in a language that is not the native tongue of one of the parties, a problem arises: which digital devices can be used to ensure optimal learning?

A non-native language (English or Russian) acts as an intermediary, characterised by a lack of understanding of the subject area’s specific features. When using English as a lingua franca, the professional syntax is significantly simplified for the teacher, leading to greater explicitness (understanding of meaning), but this, in turn, deprives the speech of specific professional markers that are key to a full grasp of the concept. For their part, Chinese students transfer the logical and syntactic structure of their native language into English, which can lead to misunderstandings on both sides. The teacher interprets the final result as an error, despite the fact that this is a manifestation of the difference in the syntactic structure of the two languages. In such an environment, both students and teachers turn to machine translation programmes (百度翻译, DeepL, 网易有道, Google Translate). These applications help to understand the terms of the tasks and the content of the texts, and reduce language barriers when encountering new material

However, when teaching technical subjects, where a lecturer’s professional practice must be geared towards the use of standardised terminology, the problem of academic inaccuracy becomes more acute. The ease with which technical terms can be translated using these applications ‘drives’ students into a dead end: they begin to use the suggested translation without checking or clarifying the definition of the required concept; as a result, their linguistic and professional skills simply deteriorate. It is worth noting that translators often struggle to choose the specific meaning of a term. For a lecturer with knowledge of the subject, the error will be

obvious, but for an international student learning a new language and subject, it will not be so clear. Chinese students, due to the characteristics of the local mindset, are not inclined to ask clarifying questions. This leads to a chain of misunderstandings, which are unacceptable when studying technical disciplines.

In these circumstances, the successful development of digital literacy among future teachers — which forms an integral part of professional culture — is vital when working with international students. The use of machine translation tools, diagrams and drawings helps to facilitate understanding of the material; the use of online resources and online testing allows typical errors in the material to be identified, which is particularly important for the teacher in pinpointing problem areas in the teaching of the subject. However, it is important to note that a high level of digital professional competence is not a universal measure. The use of messaging apps and online platforms is also shaped by the cultural characteristics of the students. Students may choose to conceal gaps in their knowledge, whilst the teacher, faced with a lack of questions, may interpret the general silence as understanding.

in a technical university, where the professional culture of the educator is oriented towards precision in the use of standardised terminology, the acquisition of digital and intercultural professional competences becomes an essential means of achieving success in their professional practice.

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以能力为基础的方法培养未来语言学教师的外语能力
**COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH TO DEVELOPING FOREIGN
LANGUAGE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PHILOLOGY
TEACHERS**

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摘要：本文基于能力本位法，探讨了未来语言学教师外语能力培养的主要原则。文章讨论了未来语言学教师外语能力的基本模式及其作为实现目标的手段。在此框架下，能力本位法阐明了未来语言学教师对外语能力内容的内在理解。能力本位法引入了新的教学模式，充分考虑了所有个体和个人偏好。

关键词：能力本位法，外语能力，未来语言学教师，语言教育，观察法。

Abstract. *The article examines the main principles of forming foreign language competence in future philology teachers based on the Competency-based approach. The fundamental patterns of foreign language competence in future philology teachers, which function as a means to achieve the objective, are discussed. Within this framework, the Competency-based approach elucidates the intrinsic understanding of the content of foreign language competence in future philology teachers. The competency-based approach introduces new forms of work that consider all individual and personal preferences.*

Keywords: *competency-based approach, foreign language competence, future philology teachers, language education, observation method.*

Contemporary realities demand that future philology teachers demonstrate a high level of foreign language proficiency. The development of foreign language competence depends on numerous factors. The fundamental principles of forming foreign language competence encompass the understanding of relevant approaches to its development. One of the relevant approaches is the competency-based approach.

The competency-based approach is characterized by the development of foreign language communicative competence, the ability to engage in foreign language and intercultural communication with native speakers, and entails genuine practical

proficiency in the foreign language [6]. The competency-based approach features a particular emphasis on the study of the culture of the target language and the ethical assimilation of its norms and rules, which is essential for the successful formation of foreign language competence in future philology teachers [8, p.12].

The competency-based approach presupposes a practical focus in the formation of foreign language competence and underscores the societal need for language education. Accordingly, the competency-based approach adheres to specific principles manifested in self-determination, self-actualization, and the development of individuality. The competency-based approach operates effectively in conjunction with practical work methods [2, p.132].

The new academic direction applies the competency-based approach in the development of foreign language competence. The competency-based approach is oriented toward the goals and objectives of education and is guided by concepts such as socialization, self-determination, and individualization. The competency-based approach constitutes the professional representation of the individual during the enhancement of language material. The competency-based approach is inextricably linked with the sociocultural approach. The sociocultural approach examines the culture of the language, cultural values, customs, and traditions; meanwhile, the competency-based approach is aimed at the development of intercultural communication skills within the framework of language culture [1].

The Competency-based approach implies the practical application of language knowledge to achieve professional objectives. The Competency-based approach constitutes a solution for future philology teachers to realize the primary function of a philology instructor [5, c. 107-108].

The Competency-based approach is grounded on several developmental platforms: the introduction of the distinction between the concepts of ‘competence’ and ‘competency,’ as well as ‘communicative competence’; the extension of the Competency-based approach into various professional domains; Achieving a demanded outcome through the competency-based approach. The competency-based approach defines the concepts of competence as knowledge, skills, and abilities related to the studied field, and competency as the possession of competence in professional activity [7, pp. 66-67].

According to psychological research, the competency-based approach serves as a means of overcoming personal and psychological difficulties. Within language education, the competency-based approach facilitates the overcoming of the language barrier [3, p. 223].

The primary objective of the competency-based approach is to emphasize personal growth and self-development. The focus shifts to the competencies an individual possesses rather than solely on the quantity of their knowledge. The competency-based approach defines the criteria for an individual’s success and their

performance in challenging situations. The competency-based approach entails the broadening of professional experience for future philology teachers [4, pp. 37-39].

In conclusion, it can be asserted that the competency-based approach fosters the essential skills and abilities of future philology teachers through self-determination, self-efficacy, and individuality within professional activity to achieve optimal outcomes in the development of foreign language competence. From a practical perspective, relying on the method of observing groups in full-time and part-time forms of education within the specialization of pedagogical education with the profile of English language training demonstrates an effective approach to forming foreign language competence through an activity-oriented, proactive nature of instruction. To effectively implement the competency-based approach, a series of didactic-practical exercises are distinguished:

1) Metaphorical cards titled ‘My feelings and desires’ — facilitate the selection of the essential lexical minimum for describing the image and provide practice in grammar for conveying the information-event depicted on the card;

2) reading stories about renowned and successful individuals, followed by a series of discussion-based exercises;

3) an exercise for enriching vocabulary entitled “Ball sprinter” (various types of balls symbolize different parts of speech);

4) an oral game entitled “Pantomime on the Screen,” wherein a voice-over narrator articulates actions that students are to perform;

5) the exercise “TV Presenter,” designed to enhance phonological and intonational skills;

6) creating a video blog to enhance speaking skills, emotional-intonational expressiveness, and the gathering of relevant information;

7) maintaining a personal diary to develop writing skills and expand vocabulary;

8) producing an advertising video clip for the sale of one’s own item;

9) public speaking in the target language (reports, lectures, presentations, etc.);

10) dubbing of films and animated series.

The competency-based approach is a methodological framework that enhances speaking and writing skills by considering personal motives and drives. An instrument of the competency-based approach is a specific activity aimed at achieving outcomes related to the mastery of foreign language skills. In forming foreign language competence in future philology teachers, the competency-based approach embodies the readiness and openness to acquiring new knowledge and skills in the linguistic domain. Furthermore, the competency-based approach can be characterized as a competence-activity-based approach. The competency-based activity approach emphasizes the achievement of foreign language competence through active engagement. Future philology teachers benefit from the use of the competency-based approach.

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以哈尔滨丧葬空间的象征意义为切入点，在亚太文化背景下进行田野调查
**THE SYMBOLISM OF HARBIN'S FUNERAL SPACE AS A FIELD
STUDY IN THE CONTEXT OF ASIA-PACIFIC CULTURES**

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摘要：亚太地区的研究涵盖了大量关于单一民族社区丧葬仪式的著作。然而，对于多宗教、多元文化的城市，即不同传统在同一空间共存的城市，相关研究仍存在空白。哈尔滨是一个独特的案例，东正教徒、穆斯林、犹太教徒和天主教徒在此共同生活、共同离世，丧葬象征意义也并非统一。本研究以日常生活人类学为基础，分析哈尔滨丧葬仪式的空间组织如何反映亚太地区特有的文化融合过程。本文的实证基础是2007年至2010年间在哈尔滨收集的田野资料，这些资料是通过访谈、照片记录和观察收集的，并辅以2019年的后续实地考察。作者重构了哈尔滨不同族群（包括俄罗斯族、华族和其他族群）对死亡空间的“挪用”实践，从而为该地区跨界日常生活研究做出贡献。本文探讨的问题在于，一方面，葬礼习俗高度仪式化且具有鲜明的民族特征；另一方面，俄罗斯、中国和欧洲的传统在哈尔滨多元文化空间中却真实存在共存和相互影响。文章着重分析了这一矛盾在日常实践中是如何得到解决的：葬礼仪式的空间象征意义究竟是界定了文化边界，还是模糊了文化边界？

关键词：哈尔滨，葬礼象征意义，田野调查，亚太地区，文化。

Abstract: *Research on the Asia-Pacific region includes numerous works on the funeral rites of mono-ethnic communities. However, multi-confessional and multicultural cities where different traditions coexist within a single space remain a lacuna. Harbin represents a unique case, where Orthodox Christians, Muslims, Jews, and Catholics live and die side by side, and where funeral symbolism is not unified. This study is grounded in the anthropology of everyday life and analyzes how the spatial organization of funeral rituals in Harbin reflects the processes of cultural syncretism characteristic of Asia-Pacific countries. The empirical basis*

of the article consists of field materials collected in Harbin between 2007 and 2010 through interviews, photo documentation, and observation, supplemented by a follow-up field trip in 2019. The author reconstructs the practices of “appropriating” the space of death by the Russian, Chinese, and other communities of the city, thus contributing to the study of cross-border everyday life in the region.

The problematic of the article lies in the contradiction between the high degree of ritualization and ethnic marking of funeral practices, on the one hand, and the actual coexistence and mutual influence of Russian, Chinese, and European traditions in Harbin’s multicultural space, on the other: Special attention is paid to how this contradiction is resolved in everyday practice: does the spatial symbolism of funeral rituals fix cultural boundaries or, on the contrary, blur them?

Keywords: Harbin, funeral symbolism, field study, Asia-Pacific region, culture.

The problematics of multicultural coexistence in Manchuria found theoretical understanding in the collective monograph “Entangled Histories: The Transcultural Past of Northeast China” (1), which emphasizes that “the coexistence of people of different nationalities, ethnic groups, and cultures in Manchuria was rarely harmoniously balanced or static; on the contrary, interactions were dynamic and complex.” It is important to note that this volume includes a special chapter, “Globalization of Death: Foreign Cemeteries in a Transnational Perspective” (1, pp. 59-79), devoted to foreign cemeteries in Asia and in Harbin in particular. However, the analysis of cemeteries therein is conducted from a historical-demographic perspective, without addressing the semiotics of funerary space.

Studies devoted to Russian Orthodox cemeteries in China examine Russian burials as “ambivalent remains” of the complex history of Russo-Chinese relations (2). The author analyzes how these cemeteries become sites of memory conflict and political interpretations.

Of particular interest in this context are works dedicated to the reconstruction of the Orthodox section at Harbin’s Huanshan Cemetery. This necropolis is unique as it remains the only functioning Orthodox cemetery on Chinese territory (3). Russian and Chinese researchers show significant interest in the restoration of Orthodox burials abroad. The complexity of such work is largely explained by historical specificity: until the mid-20th century, there was no established practice of creating cemeteries in China as such.

Funerary space in multicultural cities of the Asia-Pacific region often functions not only as a place of burial but also as a significant social node where different communities interact, assert themselves, or, conversely, mark boundaries. This is particularly evident in the study of Singaporean keramats — holy graves venerated by different ethno-religious groups. Harbin burials perform an analogous function. Like Singaporean keramats, which serve “not just as monuments of remembrance

for the dead, but also as rallying points for the living” (4), Harbin cemeteries — for both Russians and Chinese — become spaces where memory, identity, and intercultural connections materialize.

The study of Harbin’s symbolism in the Asia-Pacific context allows us to compare it not in isolation but as one variant of how different civilizational matrices encode the space of death. According to the Confucian canon “Lun Yu,” only the strict observance of parental funeral rites and sacrifices to ancestors lies at the foundation of popular virtue, returning it to its authentic basis (5, ch. I, 9). This position establishes a value framework in which the funerary rite of the Chinese is conceived not as a private family matter but as the foundation of public morality and social order.

The article by L. I. Isaeva (6), based on field materials, analyzes in detail the symbolism of objects — funerary clothing, ritual money, color schemes, as well as the ways of endowing objects associated with funerals with a life-affirming meaning. However, the author’s work practically does not address spatial symbolism. The present study fills this understudied aspect, shifting the focus from ritual objects to the organization of funerary space in multicultural Harbin.

In traditional China, each ethnic group had its own funerary rites. The majority of the population (Han Chinese) entrusted the organization of funerals to Buddhist monks and observed all mourning requirements associated with the Confucian canon. This funerary complex, albeit in modified form, underlies contemporary funeral rites.

Among the Harbin respondents we surveyed, about 7% identified themselves as Buddhists (7, p. 19). They prefer the Buddhist funeral ritual, which is connected with the Buddhist worldview — the concept of the transmigration of the soul (samsara). A Buddhist understands from the outset that birth itself is a slow progression toward death, that death is inevitable. Therefore, he prepares for its approach throughout his life, doing good and avoiding evil, to be reborn in a higher world. The life path of the Buddha serves as a model of such an attitude toward life and death for the believer.

As A. A. Maslov notes, in traditional China, many philosophical teachings, including Confucianism and Taoism, were formed on the basis of ancient mystery cults associated with journeys to the afterlife and funerary rites (8, p. 15).

In contemporary China, research shows that the boundary between “believers” and “non-believers” is blurred. Even those who do not identify themselves with any religion participate in rituals out of respect for tradition, family, or public opinion.

According to field observations, the body of the deceased is transported to the morgue immediately after preparations begin. The dwelling is prepared for the ceremony: all mirror surfaces are covered with white cloth, any objects of a red hue (including wall calligraphic inscriptions) and everything associated with merriment, joy, and celebration are removed. A photograph of the deceased is placed on a small table covered with a white tablecloth. Wreaths sent by friends, relatives, and colleagues are placed nearby — on the ribbons is often written “you will forever

remain in our hearts.” Candles are lit on both sides of the portrait, and fruits, sweets, and incense sticks are also placed on the table. Relatives stay awake the entire night, ensuring that the candles and sticks do not go out — those that have burned down are immediately replaced with new ones.

The next day, the house is visited by all who were acquainted with the deceased: friends, relatives of varying degrees of closeness, neighbors, colleagues, distant acquaintances. Each visitor expresses words of sympathy and leaves a monetary donation in any amount. The entire day is devoted to farewell — anyone who wishes may come in and honor the memory of the departed. A specially designated person keeps a record: recording the visitor’s name and the amount of money given. In exchange for the envelope with the donation, a small white flower is given, which is traditionally attached to one’s clothing.

In Harbin families professing Orthodoxy or Islam, burial is carried out according to the traditional rite with the body preserved in a coffin. However, such practice requires official permission, which is difficult to obtain under contemporary conditions. In China, there is a serious problem of land shortage for new burials, so state policy is oriented toward cremation. Even if a traditional burial has taken place, after three years the grave is opened, the coffin is removed, and the remains are cremated. The urn with ashes is typically placed in one of the columbarium niches. Such structures are located at Buddhist or Taoist temples, within the city limits, or directly on cemetery grounds.

The memorial meal is typically held either in the courtyard of the deceased’s former home or at a restaurant. A tent, tables, chairs, and a portable refrigerated coffin are rented. Catering staff are hired to feed the attendees. The number of dishes served must be odd, with rice and tofu being mandatory. Fish and soups are not allowed.

An important element of funerary symbolism in Harbin is the decoration of the bus that carries the procession participants to the farewell site or crematorium. A large cloth bow — white or black, depending on local tradition and the age of the deceased — is attached to the front of the bus. Sometimes a portrait of the deceased is placed above the bow, and a paper sign indicating the number of years lived is attached to the rear window of the bus.

Wreaths, both artificial and made of fresh flowers, are necessarily included in the procession. Of particular interest is the symbolic figure of an animal, made of flowers and reaching about one meter in height. If a woman has died, a cow is made: according to folk beliefs, it will drink dirty water, thereby purifying the deceased’s home. If a man has died, a horse is made — on it, the spirit of the deceased will, according to belief, go to work. This reveals the stable connection of funerary symbolism with gender roles and economic representations characteristic of Chinese tradition.

Items intended for burning are also loaded onto the bus — either the deceased's real personal belongings or their paper imitations (houses, cars, money, household appliances). On the ribbons of the wreaths, hieroglyphic inscriptions are traditionally written: “chen tong” (bitterness, sorrow) and “dao nen” (to honor memory with sorrow). These inscriptions mark the procession space as a zone of mourning, separating it from the everyday urban environment.

The practice of burning ritual money is widespread not only in China but also in other Asia-Pacific countries — Vietnam, Thailand, Cambodia, Malaysia, and Singapore — where the influence of the Chinese diaspora is significant. In Harbin, ritual banknotes are burned in specially designated furnaces at temple complexes, dedicating them to specific deities. When burning, the banknotes are treated like real money: they are not tied up but laid out in unfolded stacks. It is believed that using real money instead of ritual money brings misfortune.

Thus, already at the stage of moving through the city, funerary space begins to visually announce itself — through color, form, hieroglyphics, and symbolic objects. The bus with its bow, portrait, floral figures, and inscriptions becomes a mobile marker of the mourning boundary, crossing the public space of Harbin.

The conducted field study of the symbolism of Harbin's funerary space allows us to draw the following conclusions. The Chinese funerary rite preserves a high degree of ritualization, including a strict sequence of actions, color marking (white, black, red), spatial organization (crematorium — grave — columbarium), object symbolism (ritual money, paper imitations, animal figures), and numerical codes (number of dishes, days of commemoration). In the multicultural space of Harbin, there is a coexistence and mutual influence of traditional Chinese (Buddhist-Taoist), Orthodox, and Muslim funerary practices, while the Confucian value framework (duty of filial piety, veneration of ancestors) remains the semantic core uniting different confessional variants.

The spatial symbolism of the funerary rite in Harbin performs a dual function. On the one hand, it fixes cultural boundaries (division by confession, gender-marked animal figures, specific ways of handling ashes). On the other hand, it demonstrates the processes of cultural syncretism characteristic of Asia-Pacific countries: the use of Western images on ritual money (John Kennedy, Marilyn Monroe), Latin signatures on banknotes, the combination of Buddhist and Taoist elements in a single rite. The material side of the funerary rite (real and ritual money, food, household items) merges with the ritual-symbolic, forming a unified semiotic field. Even secular burials and urban columbaria retain the symbolic marking of space (photographs, names, locks, color scheme), which confirms the stability of traditional representations under conditions of urbanization.

The Harbin case shows that funerary space in the multicultural cities of the Asia-Pacific region acts not only as a place of memory but also as an active zone of

intercultural interaction, where traditions do not so much conflict as adapt to each other, creating hybrid symbolic forms. This makes cemeteries and columbaria an important source for studying the real, rather than declared, mechanisms of cultural coexistence in the region.

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普遍性和绝对性作为道德规范的属性
**UNIVERSALITY AND ABSOLUTENESS AS ATTRIBUTES
OF MORAL NORMS**

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摘要：本文分析了道德规范的本质。道德规范是价值调节的基础，它引导人们辨别善恶、是非，从而发展和维护人的社会文化品质。试图将违反道德规范的行为视为自由和个人身份的体现，不应被视为年轻人的妄想，而应被视为对社会性和个人自由本质缺乏理解的表现。

关键词：道德规范，法律规范，普遍性，绝对性，价值调节，社会文化品质，自由。

Abstract. *The article analyzes the essence of moral norms, which are the basis of value regulation, orienting a person to distinguish between Good and evil, right and wrong, to develop and preserve the socio-cultural qualities of a person. Attempts to present the violation of moral norms as a manifestation of freedom and individual identity should be regarded not as delusions of youth, but as a lack of understanding of the essence of sociality and individual freedom.*

Keywords: *moral norms, legal norms, universality, absoluteness, value regulation, socio-cultural qualities, freedom.*

Each sphere of public life has its own set of social norms governing human activity in this area. Failure to comply with any norms entails condemnation. However, only violations of legal norms are subject to penalties that alter a person's physical existence (fines, dismissal from work, imprisonment, etc.). This is due to the fact that the norms of law are designed to protect society from such human actions that pose an immediate threat to the physical existence of other people.

Unlike normative legal regulation, value regulation cannot be formalized and cannot be carried out using strictly formulated norms, templates or role models [1]. Good, Truth and Beauty as fundamental values of culture give meaning to any kind and product of human activity, if they find their embodiment in it. However, the fundamental feature of value regulation is that values are defined only as the ultimate goals and meanings of socio-cultural activities, but are not defined in the forms of

their actual implementation, which creates the very possibility of discrepancies in assessments on value grounds and an almost infinite variety of concrete historical interpretations and forms of values embodiment.

Value regulation is carried out through the assessment of human activity and its results based on the forms of values embodiment inherent in the cultural subject. However, whatever the forms of values implementation, moral norms, which are the basis of value regulation, orient a person to distinguish between Good and evil, right and wrong, to develop and preserve the socio-cultural qualities of a person [2]. Truly moral behavior presupposes a free and conscious choice of Good and avoidance of evil based on the deep conviction that only such a choice distinguishes a person as a cultural subject from a biological being guided by instincts. Only the conscious exercise of duty, conscious and voluntary adherence not to instinct, but to a moral norm, testifies to the non-randomness and non-automaticity of human behavior, its sociality and reasonableness.

At the same time, one of the main differences between moral assessments and truthful and aesthetic ones is their urgency. The question of how to act in order for an act to be morally justified requires an immediate decision, in other words: inaction in the field of morality is equated to immorality, and immorality has no statute of limitations.

It is possible to delay making truth assessments only in the field of professional cognitive activity, where the Truth is opposed, as a rule, not to lies, but only to delusion as an integral element of knowledge that has nothing to do with immorality. In all other spheres of public life that use already accumulated knowledge, a departure from the value orientation towards Truth does not lead to the transformation of a person into a biological being just because he simply dies, guided by his false ideas about the world. But that is exactly why no one is consciously guided by false ideas.

The ability of aesthetic assessments to influence the value content of human consciousness is quite obvious and dangerous when aesthetic assessments are an element of purposeful identification of the beautiful as ugly, moral as immoral, true as false. However, even in this case, the harm of even the most deceitful and immoral aesthetic assessments is offset by the intuition of Beauty that lives in every social being, just as the impact of false ideas is blocked by their practical application. As for immoral acts, people who commit them destroy not only themselves, but also the very essence of socio-cultural existence. Even if immoral acts do not fall within the scope of existing legal norms, their moral assessment cannot be postponed. Value regulation prescribes the subject of culture to distinguish Good from evil as quickly as possible, because delay means conniving at evil and carries with it the most terrible thing that can happen from a value point of view: damage to the socio-cultural essence of a person.

The moral norm, as the most fundamental of all social norms, orients a person towards the interaction and coexistence of individuals in a society (community of

people). Any moral norm restricts the manifestation of instincts, any one prescribes the subject to look at another person as a self-like being. At the same time, the attribute of a moral norm is its universality and absoluteness: a moral norm applies to all cultural subjects without exception and has no spatial or temporal framework, because it directly points to the social essence of a person and prescribes this sociality to be preserved.

It is universality as an attribute that is the absolute difference between morality and immorality. Actually, immorality consists in the fact that someone begins to be guided by such rules that set him or her apart from the community of people around him or her, and give certain advantages in the implementation of life plans. Any domination: economic, political, ideological, psychological, etc. — is based on a real denial of the universality of moral norms. That is why any attempt to formulate moral norms only “for oneself”, to come up with some kind of “non-communal morality” indicates an overt or hidden desire to dominate others, immorality, leading, ultimately, to anti-sociality and biological dominance. This is confirmed by the fact that no criminal wants to be judged according to the same standards that guided him when committing a crime. And not a single ruling class wants to be subjected to precisely those unfair, non-universal demands that it itself makes on the exploited classes.

Moral norms are formulated as absolute, universal and unchangeable only because they relate to the fundamental basis of human life and do not have any other mechanisms for their maintenance except conscious choice, i.e. the goodwill of the cultural subject himself [4]. Public opinion through violent methods can shape and maintain morals, but not morality. This is the difference between the norms of morality and the so-called prevailing mores as a set of ordinary, everyday, traditional rules of behavior.

In the space of socio-cultural existence, the very possibility of an unpunished violation of a moral norm is illusory, and this illusion arises only because punishment is postponed. The real punishment for immorality is the loss of sociality. But neither an individual nor a social group turns into a herd of animals all at once. The illusion of impunity for immorality arises in each specific case because an immoral act has been immersed in a socio-cultural space built on the basis of morality for a certain period of time. However, every immoral act inevitably “shrinks” the sphere of morality and brings the final disintegration of the socio-cultural space closer.

Since sociality and morality are inextricably linked, all moral issues have an immediately obvious value content. No law, institution, or order is meaningful in terms of value if it does not comply with moral standards. However, the value content of economic or political activity should be judged solely on the basis of an analysis of specific actions and their results, rather than the intentions proclaimed by the subjects of the activity themselves. A person is able to justify any vice as a virtue

and any lie as the truth, but he is unable to turn the false content of his statements into the true one, and the depravity of his own actions into a universal moral norm.

Like all universal categories, the category of “good” characterizes only universal, invariant features of human life, namely, everything related to the preservation and development of the social essence of man. But, like other categories, “good” is ontologically indeterminate when it comes to applying this category to the analysis of a specific single phenomenon. It is this feature of all categories that ensures freedom of thought and forms of values embodiment of various cultural subjects.

everything that is perceived as moral is simultaneously perceived as universal and universally valid. However, what is perceived as moral by one subject may be perceived as morally neutral or immoral by another subject. As society develops, it becomes obvious that there is a wide range of possible behaviors within which sociality does not decrease, and that it is within the range of “non-diminishing sociality” that all cultural and historical differences in understanding what is Good exist.

Yet, in the everyday consciousness of most people, social norms are often identified with the rules of etiquette or “good manners”, which are desirable to follow or have in certain conditions, but not at all necessary. Brought up on such an idea, modern young people know, as a rule, that their freedom ends where the freedom of another person begins. However, this principle is interpreted in the spirit of the relationship between the violator of the law and representatives of law enforcement agencies: as long as the police do not stop, the violator is free in his illegal actions; and when the violator was stopped, then his freedom came to an end. At the same time, freedom of will is understood solely as arbitrariness and violation of any norms and rules at will.

Meanwhile, the violation of social norms is not a reason for pride or emotion at the inevitable disobedience of the younger generation, but a sign of social underdevelopment, inevitable only due to the incompleteness of the process of socialization and a lack of understanding that the emergence, existence and development of socio-cultural existence is possible only because unconditional biological instincts are opposed by social norms limiting instincts. The equal probability of both instinctive and socio-cultural forms of behavior of members of society indicates either the incompleteness of the process of socialization, or the beginning of social degradation.

A person who is aware of himself as a socio-cultural being should know that any violation of a social norm, and even more so of a moral norm, is a reason for serious reflection about what is the cause of the violation: the social underdevelopment of the offending subject or the heroic resistance of a highly developed personality to such social mores that lead to the degradation of human social qualities? For a person, there is nothing more humiliating than the identification of free will with the automatism of instinct. Therefore, attempts to present any violation of a social norm as a manifestation of freedom and individual identity should be regarded not

just as delusions of youth, but as a lack of understanding of the essence of sociality and individual freedom [3].

Humanity exists only because in every generation people are born who follow the path of Truth, Good and Beauty in all circumstances of life.

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国潮作为一种广告策略：文化自信、品牌竞争与中国消费者欲望的重塑
**GUOCHAO AS AN ADVERTISING STRATEGY:
CULTURAL CONFIDENCE, BRAND COMPETITION,
AND THE REFRAMING OF CHINESE CONSUMER DESIRE**

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摘要：本文以中国市场为例，探讨“国超”（或称“民族潮流”）这一广告策略，并结合概念分析和二手数据解读。文章指出，“国超”并非仅仅是在广告中运用中国传统元素，而是文化自信、市场定位、情感叙事和平台特定传播等策略的巧妙融合。研究表明，中国消费者并非完全排斥外国品牌，而是同时评估其质量、地位、情感关联性和文化尊重程度。在此背景下，李宁的崛起展现了本土品牌如何将中国元素转化为可扩展的身份认同；而麦当劳、苹果和阿迪达斯等外国品牌则表明，参与“国超”需要深度本土化，而非表面装饰。文章最后总结道，“国超”之所以成为一种强大的广告逻辑，是因为它将文化从背景装饰转变为核心的说服资源。

关键词：国超、广告策略、中国品牌、文化信心、李宁、阿迪达斯中国、消费者行为。

Abstract. *This article examines Guochao (国超), or the “national trend,” as an advertising strategy in the Chinese market and combines conceptual analysis with secondary data interpretation. It argues that Guochao works not simply as the use of traditional Chinese motifs in advertising, but as a strategic fusion of cultural confidence, market positioning, emotional storytelling, and platform-specific communication. The paper shows that Chinese consumers do not reject foreign brands outright, instead, they evaluate quality, status, emotional relevance, and cultural respect at the same time. In this environment, Li-Ning’s rise illustrates how a domestic brand can turn Chinese elements into a scalable identity, while foreign brands such as McDonald’s, Apple, and Adidas demonstrate that participation in Guochao requires deep localization rather than surface decoration. The article concludes that Guochao has become a powerful advertising logic because it transforms culture from background decoration into a core persuasive resource.*

Keywords: *Guochao, advertising strategy, Chinese brands, cultural confidence, Li-Ning, Adidas China, consumer behavior.*

Guochao, often translated as “China Chic” or the “national trend,” has become one of the most influential concepts in contemporary Chinese advertising. Yet it is not just a visual style. Lin (2025) shows that Guochao should be treated as a form of “culture on display,” in which products circulate as symbols of identity, memory, and belonging. Wang (2022) similarly argues that Guochao combines “guo,” linked to Chinese historical and material culture, with “chao,” linked to youth, trend, and hybrid fashion language. Therefore, Guochao is best understood not as decorative nationalism, but as a strategic way of making brands culturally persuasive.

The article argues that Guochao works as an advertising strategy because it turns cultural confidence into market value. It helps domestic brands build symbolic authority, and it compels foreign brands to move from surface localization to deeper cultural relevance. The available statistics show why Guochao became commercially powerful. According to the Statista chart based on a 2020 survey, 66% of respondents in China preferred local brands, while 28% preferred foreign brands and 6% were unsure (Statista, 2025). This already indicates that domestic brands had gained important symbolic ground by 2020.

At the same time, the 2024 ChemLinked survey reveals that foreign brands still hold a strong position in quality-based perception. The main reasons for choosing foreign brands were high quality (72.83%), brand fame (67.39%), and superior experience (28.80%) (ChemLinked, 2024). However, the reasons for choosing local brands point directly to the logic of Guochao: 81.25% selected support for domestic products or patriotism, 57.50% high cost-effectiveness, 56.25% easy access, and 32.50% good service (ChemLinked, 2024). More than 90% also expressed willingness to increase consumption of domestic brands in the future (ChemLinked, 2024).

These figures are important because they show that Guochao does not eliminate rational consumer judgment. Chinese consumers still value quality and brand fame. What changes is the structure of persuasion. Domestic brands now compete not only on price, but also on cultural closeness and emotional legitimacy. In such a market, advertising becomes decisive because it is the main place where brands demonstrate whether they understand the values, aesthetics, and social mood of Chinese consumers.

Li-Ning is one of the clearest examples of Guochao as a systematic advertising strategy. Sun (2022) identifies three central elements in the brand’s rise: the use of Chinese elements in design and promotion, the visible “China Li-Ning” logo, and co-branding with international celebrities or brands.

The strategic value of these moves lies in their combination. Li-Ning did not simply decorate products with traditional references. It reworked embroidery, lantern imagery, silk, mahjong motifs, and other Chinese elements into youth-oriented fashion language (Sun, 2022). The result was especially attractive to younger consumers, who were also highly active in digital word-of-mouth. In this way, Li-Ning’s audience became part of its advertising mechanism.

Figure 1. Share of consumers having preference of brands in China in 2020, by origin of brand.

Figure 2. Reasons for choosing foreign brands and local brands in China.

The “China Li-Ning” logo played an equally important role. Instead of hiding origin behind abstract global branding, Li-Ning made national identity explicit. In Guochao, this is persuasive because purchase can be interpreted as both style and support. At the same time, Li-Ning did not reject global fashion codes. Wang (2022) treats Li-Ning as one of the key “Chao” brands because it mixes Chinese symbolism with contemporary streetwear rather than presenting tradition as a static heritage object. Sun (2022) also identifies 2018 New York Fashion Week as a milestone in the brand’s international repositioning. This made Li-Ning important not only as a domestic success story, but also as a new visual model of exportable Chineseness.

Guochao also changes how foreign brands must advertise in China. They can no longer rely on prestige alone, they need cultural credibility. The Chinese New Year campaigns discussed by Dao Insights make this especially clear.

McDonald’s used a Chinese ink wash animation created with the Shanghai Animation Film Studio, turning a fast-food campaign into a respectful engagement with a traditional artistic form (Dao Insights, 2022). Apple’s short film “The Comeback” connected iPhone features with a story about homecoming, family support, and creative ambition, which made the product meaningful through a Chinese social narrative rather than through surface ornament (Dao Insights, 2022). Red Bull’s campaign recognized awkward holiday interactions and family questions, while iQOO linked esports culture with reunion values, Douyin turned the platform itself into part of the festival through participatory challenges and filters (Dao Insights, 2022).

Nike’s China strategy, as described by Zhu (2022), also shows the strengths and limitations of a global sportswear brand. Nike effectively used e-commerce, athlete endorsements, youth-oriented communication, and Chinese New Year themed products. Yet Zhu (2022) also notes that domestic brands such as Li-Ning have become a direct threat. The reason is not only price or distribution. Domestic brands can now offer fashion relevance together with stronger cultural intimacy.

The recent case of Adidas China suggests that Guochao has entered a new stage. According to RADII, adidas China’s “New Chinese Style” collection for Chinese New Year 2026, shown through the “Power of Three” runway at Shanghai Fashion Week, used jade buttons, Tang-inspired silhouettes, palace-skirt hems, cloud-pattern quilting, and brass hardware associated with antique jewelry (Wong, 2025). The report stresses that this was not a superficial use of motifs. Instead, Chinese aesthetics were integrated into a modern streetwear language meant to resonate with a global, culturally aware audience.

This case matters analytically because it shows that Guochao is no longer only about domestic substitution. It is also shaping the design logic of foreign brands. RADII presents Adidas’s strategy as part of its “global genes, local innovation”

philosophy, driven by its Shanghai creative center (Wong, 2025). In other words, Chinese style becomes not a local add-on, but a source of wider brand renewal. This helps explain why Asian-inspired adidas collections can become visible well beyond China: when Chinese cultural references are treated seriously, they gain both local legitimacy and global appeal.

The evidence examined in this article shows that Guochao works as an advertising strategy through three interconnected mechanisms. First, it gives brands symbolic proximity to consumers by making products feel culturally familiar and emotionally relevant. Second, it creates differentiation: Li-Ning's success demonstrates that cultural meaning can be a stronger long-term advantage than imitation or price competition alone. Third, it rewards narrative depth over decorative borrowing. The strongest campaigns use real social situations, festival emotions, and design intelligence rather than empty visual clichés.

At the same time, Guochao should not be romanticized. Daxue Consulting notes that domestic brands may still face criticism for weak quality, plagiarism, or inflated prices, which means that cultural symbolism cannot replace product performance (Daxue Consulting, 2024). For this reason, the most successful Guochao strategy is not nationalism by itself, but the alignment of quality, storytelling, design, and cultural confidence.

Thus, Guochao should be understood as a mature advertising framework in contemporary China. It has changed how local brands compete, how foreign brands localize, and how consumers interpret value. In today's Chinese market, culture is no longer a background detail in advertising. It has become one of its central persuasive forces.

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文化记忆：研究的理论和方法论基础
**CULTURAL MEMORY: THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL
FOUNDATIONS OF RESEARCH**

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摘要：本文探讨了文化记忆作为一种社会文化现象的理论基础。基于经典方法（M. Halbwachs、J. Assmann），作者识别了文化记忆的关键特征。文章特别关注文化记忆与其他相关概念的区分。文章提出了一个研究问题：尽管“文化记忆”概念已广泛传播，但其在实证研究中的应用仍需更深入的分析。通过对白俄罗斯哈廷纪念馆和中国南京大屠杀纪念馆的比较分析，揭示了二者在文化记忆构建机制上的差异。结论部分探讨了文化记忆再生产的几种机制。

关键词：文化记忆，文化遗产，认同，理论分析，记忆场所

Abstract: *This article examines the theoretical foundations of cultural memory as a socio-cultural phenomenon. Based on classical approaches (M. Halbwachs, J. Assmann), the author identifies the key characteristics of cultural memory. Particular attention is devoted to differentiating cultural memory from related concepts. The article formulates a research problem: despite the broad dissemination of the concept of ‘cultural memory,’ its application in empirical research necessitates more detailed analysis. Based on the comparative analysis of the memorial complex ‘Khatyn’ (Belarus) and the Memorial Hall of the Nanjing Massacre (China), differences in the mechanisms of constructing cultural memory are revealed. The conclusion addresses several mechanisms of the reproduction of cultural memory.*

Keywords: *cultural memory, cultural heritage, identification, theoretical analysis, lieux de mémoire.*

In contemporary humanities, the concept of ‘cultural memory’ has become one of the most prevalent analytical frameworks. However, despite the widespread use of this concept, there exists an opposing aspect: how can the study of cultural memory be distinguished from the analysis of historical events or the examination of cultural heritage? This article presents theoretical and methodological reflections aimed at elucidating the concept of ‘cultural memory’ and identifying its key characteristics.

In the contemporary world, ways of engaging with the past are transforming significantly, largely as a result of globalization and digitalization. The study of cultural memory acquires particular significance as it plays a key role in socio-cultural processes and in the formation of self-determination amid the crisis of traditional identity. Cultural memory functions as a mechanism that enables society to preserve its uniqueness in the face of the homogenization of contemporary trends. The purpose of this article is to analyze the theoretical foundations for studying cultural memory as a socio-cultural phenomenon.

As wrote M. Halbwachs, referring to research in psychology that addresses memory, notes with considerable surprise that the individual is treated therein as an isolated entity. It may be necessary, at the initial stage of understanding our psychological operations, to study solely the individual by severing all their connections with the society of their peers. However, individuals typically acquire, reconstruct, recognize, and situate their memories precisely within society” [1, p. 28].

The theoretical foundation of this study incorporates the concepts of M. Halbwachs on social frameworks and Y. Assmann on the distinctions between communicative and cultural memory. Methodologically, this study is grounded in the principles of systemic analysis and comparative methodology, which enable the identification of similarities and differences between cultural memory and related concepts.

In contemporary scholarship, cultural heritage is defined as the aggregate of tangible and intangible objects created by preceding generations, possessing historical, cultural, or spiritual significance, and transmitted to future generations. Unlike cultural heritage, cultural memory is understood as a continuous process of recreation: «for cultural memory, it is not the factual but the recreated history in memory that matters, and only it» [2, p.55]. Its nature is processual, subjective, and dynamic; it exists in living communication and remembrance.

Cultural memory functions as a complex source that combines knowledge, symbols, and rituals, which ensure social cohesion and the integrity of identity. Researchers emphasize that ‘the authentic connection constituting the human community arises from collective spiritual property: shared memory, customs, and traditions developed over centuries’ [3, p. 48].

T. Ragozina analyzed the concepts of ‘cultural memory’ and ‘historical memory’ within socio-philosophical and humanitarian discourses, highlighting that cultural memory is ‘an immanent property of the sociocultural organism (society), consisting in its capacity to preserve itself in all its forms, reproducing the conditions of its own existence throughout all stages of development’ [4, p. 14]. Historical memory, by contrast, reveals how society remembers and engages with the past — through commemorations, literature, monuments, and other forms of ‘reminding,’ which frequently construct a desired portrayal of the past.

When comparing various types of memory — historical (which centers on the factual reproduction of events), collective (which emphasizes group experience without in-depth analysis), or social (which underscores the impact of different social structures) — the concept of cultural memory attains a universal and profound significance. Important characteristics of cultural memory include: symbolism—cultural memory is embodied in symbols and mythological models that simplify complex phenomena. Constructed nature — cultural memory is a product of construction, in which various social and governmental institutions function as agents in its creation. In this context, memory is not natural; it is formed intentionally. Materiality—the creation and dissemination of cultural memory depend on the support of various institutions, such as museums and schools, which ensure the accessibility of memory through exhibition and cultural displays. Sacredness — reference to cultural memory occurs through the «return» to the sacred experience of ancestors. Such rituals as memorial services, moments of silence, parades, salutes, and guard changes at iconic sites unite the present and the past.

In 1969, the Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn’ was established in Belarus, serving as a clear example of constructed cultural memory. Materiality is represented by the memorial itself, sacredness is expressed through regular flower-laying ceremonies and the ritual of the «moment of silence», construction is manifested in the fact that the Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn’ is considered a symbol of all burned villages. As researcher S. Ushakin notes, Khatyn becomes a ‘place in-between’ — situated between the Soviet narrative of heroic resistance and the post-Soviet search for authentic national identity [5, p. 212]. As an example, consider the model of cultural memory in China based on the Memorial Hall of the Victims of the Nanjing Massacre (established in 1985) [6]. Similar to the Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn’, this memorial was established on the initiative of the state. However, the mechanisms of constructing cultural memory differ significantly.

The first difference concerns chronology and political context. While the Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn’ was established during the Soviet period and later reinterpreted in the post-Soviet era, the Nanjing Memorial, by contrast, was created as a direct response to attempts to revise military history. This indicates that Nanjing’s cultural memory serves as an instrument of foreign policy identity, whereas the Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn’ remained for a prolonged period an internal Soviet narrative.

The second distinction pertains to the role of documentality. The Nanjing Memorial emphasizes scientific evidentiality: a wall inscribed with 300,000 victims’ names and exhibition artifacts [6]. The Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn’ operates through artistic imagery and metaphors (the sound of bells, the ‘cemetery of villages’).

The third distinction concerns the evolution of memorials. The Memorial Complex ‘Khatyn,’ established in 1969, has virtually not altered its architectural concept and remains a ‘frozen’ monument of the Soviet era. The Nanjing memorial, conversely,

has undergone three extensive reconstructions (1995, 2007, 2015), each time altering its semantic focus: from an accusation of cruelty to the theme of peace, and subsequently to the narrative of victory [6].

The comparative analysis presented demonstrates that cultural memory constitutes a universal mechanism for constructing identity, utilizing different methods of influence within distinct national contexts: symbolic generalization (Belarus) and documentary evidence (China). At the same time, both examples corroborate Y. Assmann's thesis that cultural memory is a product of active construction rather than a 'natural' archive of the past.

Currently, cultural memory confronts numerous challenges that may result in the loss or distortion of cultural heritage. These challenges necessitate the creation of new technologies for the preservation and restoration of cultural exemplars, as this facilitates individuals' experience of unity with the past, comprehension of their position within history, and the preservation of the uniqueness of their culture.

The development of tourism and the art industry sector, which draws attention to historical monuments and traditions, serves as a vivid example of the materiality of cultural memory and its integration into contemporary life.

Theoretical analysis enables us to draw the following conclusions:

First, cultural memory is neither a passive archive nor a mere aggregation of personal memories. It is a dynamic mechanism.

Second, cultural memory can be studied through several interconnected components: symbolism (rituals, narratives, myths, memorial sites), institutionalization (museums, schools, media, state structures), and materiality (monuments, exhibitions, architectural ensembles).

Thirdly, it is essential to distinguish cultural memory from related concepts (historical memory, cultural heritage, collective memory) to conduct rigorous research.

Fourthly, the comparative analysis of Belarusian and Chinese examples demonstrates that the mechanisms of cultural memory (symbolism, materiality, institutionalization) are imbued with differing content across national contexts. In the Belarusian case, the mechanism of symbolic generalization predominates, whereas in the Chinese case, the mechanism of documentary evidence is paramount. However, in both cases, cultural memory assists the state in uniting the people and affirming its values.

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当代大众传媒环境中的少数族裔语言
**MINORITY LANGUAGES IN CONTEMPORARY MASS MEDIA
ENVIRONMENT**

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摘要：本文对楚瓦什语在线资源（博客和网站）进行了研究。作者分析了其语言特征、主要主题和体裁，以及其他语言的影响。研究表明，楚瓦什语博客圈有助于推广和保护楚瓦什语。作者们成功地将楚瓦什语使用者聚集在一起，为他们提供了一个可以自然地使用和发展本语言的空间。他们还在传播历史文化内容方面发挥着重要作用，从而支持了本语言的生存发展。

关键词：博客，楚瓦什语，媒体研究，互动性，语言借用，语言认同

Abstract. *This article offers a research of Chuvash-language online resources (blogs and websites). The authors analyze characteristic linguistic features, prevailing topics and genres, interference of other languages. The results of the study show that the Chuvash-language blogosphere contributes to promoting and preserving of the Chuvash language. Authors manage to unite Chuvash speakers and provide them with a space where their language can be naturally used and developed. They also play an important role in dissemination of historical and cultural content supporting viability of their native language.*

Key words: *blogging, Chuvash language, media research, interactivity, borrowing, linguistic identity*

The digital environment has affected dissemination of information creating new discourse spaces. One of them is blogging that has transformed into a powerful

means of communication that makes information available to different audiences. Therefore, research of blogging in regional languages becomes especially acute. The Chuvash language, being a regional language of an ethnic minority in Russia, is a relevant study object. At the moment it faces usage narrowing, competition on the part on global and Russian mass media, however, online platforms provide new opportunities to use the language in modern life. According to the French researcher R. Colonna “nowadays digital visibility of a minority language determines its real viability: being away from screens entails the risk of being out of mind” [1]. This paper studies how the traditional Chuvash language interacts with new genres in the blogging environment.

Blog messages are a classical study object in media linguistics. We can clearly see how the scientific interests of linguists shifted from studying the language of the Net to studying the language used on the Net. First it was perceived as a new variety of jargon, but as years passed the attitude changed. The Net is no longer viewed as a technical data dissemination channel, but as a modern social and cultural environment. [2] Functional spheres of the language are broadened by bloggers as native speakers and not by government institutions. Our research is also based on Bakhtin’s studies of genres and theory of conversational genres [3]: blog post, stories, online diary, chat are conversational genres emerging in the digital environment, so analyzing them enables to identify lasting stylistic and thematic models in the Chuvash-language segment of the Internet. Another key concept used in our study is Karaulov’s linguistic identity [4]. A blogger has a linguistic identity and his speech represents the Chuvash-speaking community. At the same time the communication should meet interface requirements. Blogging is a digitized communication footprint available for profound research [5]. The channel owner acts as a culture broker conveying certain ethnic elements that are embedded in modern speech practices [6, 7]. Thus, a blog can act as a digital archive that actualizes the community’s cultural memory [8].

The goal of the research is to study blogging as a tool of the Chuvash language development while there is no comprehensive philological description of this field. To achieve the goal the following issues are considered in the paper:

- in terms of the language we consider what characteristic features of Chuvash-language blogs are; how interference of the Russian language is displayed; whether there is an online standard of the Chuvash language;
- in terms of genre and thematic distinctiveness we have studied what themes and genres are the most popular ones in the Chuvash blogosphere; whether there are genres unique for the Chuvash-language environment; what rhetorical devices and methods of interaction with the audience prevail.

Having analyzed blogging in detail will enable to assess the ability of Chuvash-language blogs to represent contemporary Chuvash identity that combines

traditional key elements of Chuvash culture культуры (“тăван” / native, “хăйне уса панă” / distinctiveness, “чăвашлăх” / Chuvashness) with global trends.

To achieve the set objectives a comprehensive methodology was used. It combined qualitative and quantitative approaches, in particular, corpus study (selection of texts from blogs in Chuvash); linguo-stylistic analysis (studying blogs in order to find out key topics, genres, evaluations, neologisms, borrowings, dialect words, purely Chuvash or Chuvash and Russian language(s) of blogging).

From the sociolinguistic point of view, the Chuvash language is characterized by stable diglossia: it is mainly used in everyday social interaction and traditional spheres. This pattern can also be seen in the digital space where the topic of communication directly affects the choice of the language that is used. Despite the fact that the Chuvash-language blogosphere fails to cover the complete range of contexts, it manages to create an alternative environment for informal use of the language and community mobilization [6].

The authors define Chuvash-language blogging as online public activities performed mainly in the Chuvash language aimed at a certain audience. Chuvash is used in this context not only as a means of communication, but also as a value to be preserved and promoted. Blogging in Chuvash is often an attempt to enhance the prestige of the language in the world where the English-language mass culture dominates. So, in addition to communication, it is important to contribute to community consolidation and support of ethnic and cultural identity in the virtual environment. According to foreign researchers technologies don't just mediate communication, but fundamentally transform such social categories as community, authority and identity. Thus, Chuvash-language blogging is a social and cultural practice in Chuvash that uses the Internet to support viability and contribute to development of the Chuvash language.

The study was based on materials from Чаваш пики / Chuvash woman says blog (t.me/s/chuvash_piki), Чаваш халах сайче website (chuvash.org), and Виталий Михайлован чăвашла сайчĕ website (chuvsite.ucoz.ru). The website Виталий Михайлован чăвашла сайчĕ is targeted at a more specific audience. Its content is widely used at schools (e.g., 74 schoolchildren registered to take part in Улăп contest). The telegram channel Чаваш пики has 871 subscribers. The website Chuvash.org has the largest audience as it is available in Chuvash, Russian, English and Esperanto enabling it to attract from several hundred to thousands of users per month.

The analysis of Чаваш халах сайче website in terms of the language and genres shows that the whole content of its Chuvash version is represented in the Chuvash language, consequently, authors of the website aim at preserving the Chuvash language. The stylistic analysis demonstrates that they use expressive means typical of the journalistic writing (news are written in a neutral tone), conversational style (Chuvash proverbs, e.g., Пăчăрăн пырши тухсан та виçĕ кун пурнасăн / Even if a hazel

grouse's intestines go out, it wants to live for three days), popular science style (in the historic segment where information about outstanding personalities is provided).

According to the analysis, Чăваш пики / Chuvash woman says blog is a blog devoted to culture and education. It is written in an informal conversational style with elements of editorial style in the posts about the language, history and culture. The author uses first person narration, shares her personal thoughts, addresses subscribers using 'thou' which sounds friendly and intimately. The blog's strategy is Chuvash-Russian bilingualism. Almost every post is given in the two languages (first in Chuvash, then a Russian translation/explanation). The blog's vocabulary focuses on modern reality and everyday activities: the author uses words related to the digital world (account, repost, like), conversational words and in Chuvash lessons lexical mistakes are explained. The blogger doesn't just use the Chuvash language, she compares it with other languages (Turkish, Tatar) in order to emphasize similarity, or vice versa, uniqueness and adapts it for contemporary reality suggesting equivalents of new concepts. In terms of genres, there are educational microblogs (lessons), linguistic, cultural, social and political comments.

The website Виталий Михайлован чăвашла сайчĕ (chuvsite.ucoz.ru) is the author's educational and local history resource devoted to preservation of the Chuvash language. The texts are written mainly in the official, business, popular science and journalistic styles: the texts are structured, they contain exact dates, names and facts ("Çулĕ унан ытла та вăрам пулчĕ çав. 1671 çулта, çутă Çавал аслă Атăл шывне юкса тухнă тĕлте тăван халăхпа сывпуллашса вилĕмсĕрлĕх çулĕ çине тухнăранпа виçĕ ĕмĕр ытла, тĕплĕнрех каласан, 340 çул, иртрĕ.") / His path was too long. Since 1671, when, having waved farewell to his native people at the place where the clear Tsvil flows into the great Volga River, he set out on the path of immortality, more than three centuries have passed, 340 years, to be more precise.

Use of the conversational style in greetings and when addressing the website visitors creates a friendly atmosphere (Хапăл тăватăр-и, ырă тăванăмăрсем! / Hello, dear fellow-countrymen!). Analyzing the vocabulary, we can notice terms related to the Chuvash culture (Улăп / Chuvash warrior, купас / a traditional musical instrument), borrowings (интернет урлă / through the Internet, Браузерлисем / browser games). The website offers materials for students (quizzes and contests), electronic Chuvash textbooks with educational articles (biographies of Chuvash poets, description of traditions, song lyrics) and news (Кун тарам/ Current day). The audience consists of schoolchildren, teachers, local history experts. The website displays relevant Chuvash content in a variety of genres; however, its design (uCoz platform) is out-of-date and interactive features are restricted (comments in some sections are disabled).

The contemporary Chuvash linguistic identity is a bilingual middleman between the literary standard of the Chuvash language and innovations that it

experiences. Combining Chuvash and Russian words he creates and maintains the Chuvash identity in the Internet environment. The linguistic identity of a Chuvash-language blogger promotes the standard language and creates new speech practices. The online space becomes the key environment for demonstration of the updated ethnic and cultural identity ensuring language continuity and its relevance for young generations.

The analysis of Chuvash-language blogging enables to single out characteristic linguistic features: providing cultural and historic content authors comply with the standard contributing to dissemination of the standard Chuvash language, while in entertaining materials standards may be ignored and the conversational style with borrowings from the English language (стрим тум / to stream, лайк чӑрма / to like, тренд ҫине ҫӳлеҫ / to hit the trend) or Chuvash and Russian elements in one sentence prevails. It demonstrates actual speech practices of bilinguals.

As far as topics and genres are concerned, the content related to the Chuvash identity prevails, e.g., materials on Chuvash history, cuisine, music. Authors inform the audience about dances, songs, myths, history. Some of the most valuable content samples are stories of old people about life of the Chuvash in the past that cannot be found in mainstream mass media.

The main speech strategy is saving the Chuvash language from falling into disuse. It is achieved by use of certain emotionally attaching words like эс / thou (to address the reader), тӑвансем / one's people, kin, хӑмӑрӑмсем / our people (informal address to Chuvash people); appeals to common symbols, historic personalities, jokes that are understood only within the ethnic group. In digital communication the literary Chuvash language is used as online standard that combines focus on the written Chuvash language, borrowings and loan translations from Russian and English as well as conversational elements. The Chuvash identity is represented through the synthesis of key cultural concepts with relevant topics and genres of the digital age.

The analysis of Chuvash-language blogs shows that in the Chuvash-language blogosphere the same genres as in Russian-language blogs are used. It is not surprising as Chuvash blogs function in the same digital formats. The most widely used genres include linguo-cultural microblog teaching the Chuvash language, ethnic and cultural educational blog with structured explanation of cultural codes (ritual ceremonies, mythology, traditions, symbolism) to the youth, a personal diary aimed at boosting the popularity of the language where the author acts directly as the language promoter and defender by sharing personal stories, thoughts and experience, turning their private utterances into a public language-saving activity. Thus, the uniqueness is in filling the blogs with cultural and identity-creating content in the Chuvash language as well as in evident educational mission of the projects.

Chuvash-language blogging faces certain challenges: none of the analyzed blogs is created exclusively in Chuvash, bloggers cannot avoid using Russian, some people in the audience accuse bloggers of contaminating the language with Russian borrowings or of extreme purism. Besides, the audience of Chuvash blogs is not so large as the audience of Russian ones.

To sum up, Chuvash blogging combines traditions and innovations, standard and usage norms, ethnic peculiarities and global trends. Blogging has become the most important sphere to adapt the Chuvash language to the reality of the XXI century. Despite certain difficulties and its bilingual nature, it maintains the language in the public domain enabling to pass it down to younger generations. Structured research of blogging is necessary not only for academic description of the phenomenon, but also for developing effective strategies aimed at support of the Chuvash language.

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屠格涅夫的《猎人笔记》系列小说中英雄们的演讲，体现了俄罗斯民族准则。

**THE SPEECH OF THE HEROES FROM I.S. TURGENEV CYCLE
“NOTES OF A HUNTER” AS A REFLECTION OF THE RUSSIAN
NATIONAL CODE**

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Bryansk State University named after Academician I.G. Petrovsky

摘要：本研究以俄罗斯民族语言为视角，探讨屠格涅夫的《猎人笔记》系列故事的语言特征。分析了词汇、语法和句法工具在塑造反映社会等级、心理状态和民族精神的人物语言形象中的作用。重点关注农民朴实自然的口语与贵族矫揉造作的语言之间的对比。研究表明，屠格涅夫通过人物生动的语言和口语，揭示了俄罗斯精神和民族性格中蕴含的深刻矛盾及其丰富多样的表现形式。

关键词：俄罗斯民族语言，民族性格，语言，言语，屠格涅夫，《猎人笔记》

Abstract: *This study is devoted to the study of linguistic features of the cycle of stories by I.S. Turgenev “Notes of a Hunter” from the perspective of expressing the Russian national code. The role of lexical, grammatical and syntactic tools in creating speech portraits of characters reflecting social hierarchy, psychological states and national mentality is analyzed. Special attention is paid to the juxtaposition of the living, folk speech of the peasants and the artificial speech of the nobility. The study demonstrates how I.S. Turgenev, through the language and lively colloquial speech of the characters, reveals the deep contradictions of the Russian soul and the national character embodied in the diversity of its manifestations.*

Keywords: *Russian national code, national character, language, speech, I.S. Turgenev, “Notes of a Hunter”.*

Russian thought raised the problem of defining the specifics of the Russian national character in the second half of the 18th century, which was largely due to the need to understand the identity of Russian culture under the active influence of Western traditions. P.A. Plavilshchikov suggested that the existence of its own national character began to be questioned due to excessive imitation of

foreign models [Yunusov, 2002, p. 5]. This position was shared by N.I. Novikov, who opposed “gallomania” and advocated respect for national history as the foundation of national identity. It was through the reproduction of historical facts and their artistic interpretation that researchers of that time, such as M.V. Lomonosov and G.R. Derzhavin, went to comprehend the foundations of national identity.

At the beginning of the 19th century, A.I. Turgenev made significant clarifications to the understanding of this problem, arguing that the “spirit of the people” must necessarily be expressed in a literary work through images drawn from national history [Turgenev A.I., 1980, pp. 44-47]. The Romantic theorist O.M. Somov developed this idea, believing that literature is intended to become a “telling picture of the mores” and customs of the people [Somov, 1978, p. 264]. By the middle of the century, the issue of national dominance had finally moved into the spotlight of major writers. Pushkin pointed out that “the climate, the way of government, the faith” give each nation a special physiognomy, which is inevitably reflected in the “mirror of poetry” [Pushkin, 1962, vol. 6, p. 267].

The most important contribution to the development of ideas about nationality was made by N.V. Gogol, who emphasized that true nationality does not consist in describing external attributes, such as a sundress, but in the very “spirit of the people”, in their way of feeling and speaking [Gogol, 1994, vol. 7, p. 261]. Gogol brought the concept of nationality closer to “national identity”, which was reflected in the lexicographical practice of V.I. Dahl [Dahl, 1979]. V.G. Belinsky saw the secret of national identity in the “manner of understanding things”, and therefore in the manner of expressing them through language [Belinsky, 1958, pp. 197-202]. Grigoriev complemented these judgments by considering the people as “a whole national personality” with a typical physiognomy [Grigoriev, 1990].

Philosophical discussions in the middle of the 19th century between Slavophiles and Westerners also revolved around the question of the “mystery” of a national character. A.S. Khomyakov saw the basis of the Russian mentality in “conciliarity” and Orthodoxy [Khomyakov, 1994, vol. 1, p. 517]. Representatives of the democratic trend, such as N. A. Dobrolyubov and D. I. Pisarev, associated the national character primarily with the interests of the common people, primarily the peasantry [Dobrolyubov, 1970]. This desire to connect the concept of national with a specific social group and its speech element became decisive for the literature of that time.

A special role in determining the character of a people through language was proved by the outstanding linguist A.A. Potebnya, whose ideas that language is the primary factor of nationality were developed in the works of D.N. Ovsyaniko-Kulikovskiy [Potebnya, 1895; Ovsyaniko-Kulikovskiy, 1989]. In modern studies of the XX-XXI centuries, this approach has been transformed into the study of the language system as a determining factor of national identity. As V.V. Kolesov

notes, the mental characteristics of the Russian word allow the recipient to identify national types of thinking and behavior [Kolesov, 1995, p. 14].

In the context of these theoretical assumptions, the collection of short stories by I.S. Turgenev “Notes of a Hunter” seems to be a unique object of analysis. According to one of the first biographers of the writer N.M. Gutyar, this work made a significant impression on all strata of society precisely because of its deep insight into popular life [Gutyar, 1904]. In this cycle, the language and speech of the writer’s characters act not just as a means of communication, but as the most important category in which the psychological makeup and national traditions of the people are fixed. A systematic approach to the study of the speech composition of the work allows us to consider the “Notes of a Hunter” as a “bundle of culture” and a reflection of the Russian national code [Stepanov, 1997, p. 40]. The study of the cognitive structures of the text and artistic concepts in Turgenev’s stories makes it possible to identify the mechanisms through which the “national element” is embodied in the poetic language of the writer.

Let’s take the example of some stories from the series “Notes of a Hunter”, how the Russian national code is expressed through the use of various linguistic means by the writer.

Thus, in “The Choir and Kalinich,” Khor’s speech is full of sentences of a complicated structure, in which one can note as a complicating component the appeal: “What, father, do you want to pay off?” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 12]. Khor is ironic about his own appearance. For example, he compares shaving a beard to mowing grass, which “can be mowed” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 12]. In his dialogues with the hunter-narrator, a patriarchal view of the family structure is manifested, where “the woman is a worker” and “the peasant is a servant” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 13]. The conciseness and accuracy of the hero’s definitions attest to his practical mind and ability to adapt to any conditions, which is one of the facets of national character – the ability to survive and thrive despite circumstances. Also, Khor, talking about his trade, says: “We trade little by little with butter and tar...” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 12]. The use of the diminutive forms of the adjectives *maslichko* and *degtishko* reflects not tenderness, but a specific national acumen, a desire to minimize one’s successes in front of an outsider, which is an important feature of the national code – caution and cunning.

A completely different aspect of the national code, the resignation and obliteration of the individual in the face of fate, is presented in the speech of the Bitch from the story “Lgov”. Analyzing his answers to questions about numerous job changes (coachman, cook, fisherman), we note that they use elliptical sentences. For example:

- Who demoted you from the coachmen?
- And the new lady” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 94].

The use of these constructions and the humble tone (“I’m sorry,” the old man stammered” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 99]) reflect the tragic side of popular life – the habit of submission, where personal will is completely dissolved in the will of the lord. This “silent” patience of the Bitch contrasts with the brisk but empty speech of the “educated” domestic Vladimir, whose insinuating intonations: “Allow me to recommend myself ...” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 90], betray a claim to a social status alien to him.

The tragedy of the national worldview is most acutely manifested in the dialogues of the story “Raspberry Water”. The speech of the peasant Vlas, who lost his son and did not receive relief from his rent, is devoid of external drama, which increases the depth of his grief. When asked about his son’s death, he answers using partial constructions: “He died. The deceased” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 43]. As an antithesis to the *narodnaya pravda* cited, Tuman’s speech is filled with nostalgia for the “illustrious” past, which, in turn, manifests itself through the direct use of outdated vocabulary by the narrator (excellency, chamber junker uniform, etc. [Turgenev, 2014, p. 41]). His language is the language of a man whose consciousness is completely shaped by serfdom, where the greatness of the master is the only measure of the value of life. It is worth noting that the name Stepushka and its use in a diminutive form emphasize the status of an “extra person” who lives out of charity, whose personality in the national consciousness is perceived through the prism of pity and gentleness. In addition, Tuman uses the phraseological unit “he turned his tongue around” in his speech [Turgenev, 2014, p. 40], describing Stepan’s tongue-tied speech, since he stuttered (“And ... and... and ... neither... nothing” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 40]). This is not just a physical disability, but the linguistic embodiment of the hero’s social paralysis. His inability to pronounce a word reflects the dumbness of a whole stratum of people deprived of the right to vote. These and metaphors (“a man on his own mind” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 12]) may indicate that the Russian national code in Turgenev’s language is inextricably linked with concrete-figurative, rather than abstract thinking.

A special place in the cycle under study is occupied by the speech characteristics of landowners, whose artificiality is opposed to the organics of folk speech. In the story “Ermolai and the Miller’s Wife,” Mr. Zverkov uses French vocabulary (for example, “Coco”, “mon cher” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 31]) and a didactic tone, arguing about the “path of truth” for his servants. His hypocrisy is exposed in the dialogue, where he describes his “kindness” to Arina, whom he himself ruined.

Similarly, Arkady Pavlich from the story “The Burmistr” uses similar expressions “Pardon, mon cher” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 154], which conceal cold cruelty towards peasants. This gap between the form (French speech) and the content (serfdom) highlights the disunity of the nobility and the people, which became one of the problems of national identity in the middle of the 19th century.

In the story “Odnodvoret Ovsyannikov”, Ovsyannikov’s speech is full of archaisms and historicisms (for example, *odnodvoret*, *nobleman*, *surveying*), which emphasizes his connection with the Catherine era. Turgenev also puts aphorisms into the mouth of his hero (“a lot of water has flowed away” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 75]). Turgenev uses the full forms of adjectives and participles when creating Ovsyannikov’s portrait, which gives the studied text a slow rhythm consonant with the unhurried passage of time in Russia in the middle of the 19th century.

In the story “Kasyan with a Beautiful Sword” it is worth noting the phonetic and lexical features reflecting the spiritual side of the Russian character – meekness and non-possessiveness. Kasyan’s lines are filled with diminutive suffixes: *horse*, *grass*, *birds*, *barley*. If we consider the hero’s speech in the phonetic aspect, we can detect its “singability”: the author notes that his voice is “sweet, young and almost feminine” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 134]. In Kasyan, Turgenev embodies the foolish type of Russian man, a wanderer, whose strength lies not in action, but in contemplation and prayerful attitude towards nature.

In the story “Pyotr Petrovich Karataev”, the vocabulary of the hero is contrasting: from the sublime to the colloquial (“there was a soul, a golden soul” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 289], “she got upset”, “self-improving” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 291]). Morphologically, this is emphasized by the author’s abundance of verbs in the narrative with the semantics of action and interjections (Ah!, Oh!, Ugh!). The syntactic structure of the text under study is characterized by an abundance of elliptical sentences and unfinished, discontinuous constructions: “Matryoshka... And what a girl she was! Where did it come from!” [Turgenev, 2014, p. 289]. From this we can conclude that Karataev is the embodiment of a spontaneous principle that cannot create, but is capable of deep, almost sacrificial suffering, which, in turn, is reflected in the mentality of the Russian person.

Thus, the analysis showed that each level of language in I.S. Turgenev’s cycle “Notes of a Hunter” carries a multifaceted semantic load. Syntactic constructions reflect the polar states of the Russian soul: its desire for order and tradition, on the one hand, and a spontaneous impulse, on the other. The lexical and morphological levels, saturated with archaisms, dialectisms and diminutive forms, record the organic connection of the characters with the natural environment and way of life and their contemplative attitude to the world.

The genre specificity of the Hunter’s Notes, emphasized in the title, allowed Turgenev to create a unique form of speech portraiture, where the nature of the hunter-narrator’s perception of reality becomes the organizing center. It was this “subjective principle” and the complexity of the transmission of nationally labeled speech structures that determined the evolution of the interpretation of this work of art.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the concept of national character in the studied cycle is not static; it is revealed in the dynamics of text generation, in the collision of

various speech elements. The speech of Turgenev's heroes is not just a means of communication, but a living embodiment of the Russian code, which captures the ability of the people to preserve the spiritual vertical under any historical circumstances. The prospect of this research is seen in the further study of the evolution of this concept in later genres of the writer, which will allow a deeper understanding of the universal and national-cultural value of the creative heritage of I.S. Turgenev.

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